

Ing. Dipl.-Ing. Christoph Pilz, BSc

Performance Assessment Framework for Vehicle-to-Everything as a Sensor (V2XaaS)

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Supervisor
Assoc.-Prof. Dipl.-Ing. Dr. techn. Gerald Steinbauer-Wagner
Institute of Technical Informatics
Autonomous Intelligent Systems Group

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*NIPSILD: Nicht in Problemen, sondern in Lösungen denken.
(transl.: Think in terms of solutions, not problems.)*

– Erich Bahn

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Abstract

Vehicle-to-Everything (V2X) communication can extend the Field of View (FoV) of a traditional Automated Vehicle (AV) by extending the perception of onboard sensors with shared information. This information can be active speed limits, accident notifications, or perception data shared between vehicles. There are no limits on what can be shared. In fact, the community encourages sharing information about one's surroundings.

However, when using Vehicle-to-Everything-as-a-Sensor (V2XaaS), the Automated Driving (AD) stack in an AV must be aware of the currently provided quality of the information shared via V2X communication to avoid degradation of overall performance and especially safety. Specifically, oversharing information leads to loaded communication channels, and sharing data with low accuracy may be useless.

Related research provides only in part an overview of the components involved V2XaaS and their performance, let alone a metric to rate the quality of individual influencing factors or the overall quality. Specifically, related research in the AD domain gives the impression of primarily focusing on improving perception results and assuming that the V2XaaS framework does not affect the quality of the data available. In contrast, the V2X domain gives the impression of expecting perception data to be perfect and only having to deal with wireless communication characteristics.

The work in this thesis aims to provide a sound foundation for integrating and evaluating V2XaaS systems. This includes an overview of the components involved, the performance linked to each component, and a metric to rate the Quality of Service (QoS) provided by the surrounding V2X field.

The work defines the components of V2XaaS and their key performance indicators. This analysis led to the setup of a demonstrator system for laboratory and field experiments that was used to perform an extensive systematic analysis of components. This analysis aims to provide well-founded ranges for the performance indicators, focusing on accuracy and delay. Those well-founded areas are then used to create a metric rating the QoS of the surrounding V2X field.

The resulting metric allows the AD system of an AV to adapt its behavior depending on the quality of the surrounding V2X field, which in turn allows it to keep up or even improve comfort, performance, and safety.

With the systematic evaluation, we aim to ease and broaden the application of V2XaaS. Even more, the contributions we made allow AD systems to have an indicator of the QoS that V2XaaS can provide at a specific moment.

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CHAPTER 1

Introduction

The Knight Industries Two Thousand (K.I.T.T.) of the famous 1980s TV series Knight Rider is one of the biggest icons for Automated Vehicles (AVs). Companies in cities such as San Francisco (USA) and Shanghai (CN) show the future of transport with automated taxis. But, as fans of Knight Rider know, K.I.T.T. was also able to communicate. K.I.T.T. could chat with Michael Knight, but K.I.T.T. could also interface with computers. He did so to interface with video feeds to gather intel and locations of people and other vehicles. The application of Vehicle-to-Infrastructure (V2I). Even more, K.I.T.T. was able to talk to another AV, his brother Knights Automated Roving Robot (K.A.R.R.), or his non-canon sister Knight Industries Road Agent (K.I.R.A.). This is Vehicle-to-Vehicle (V2V), even though not always under the best circumstances during the series and audiobook.

Nowadays, in the 2020s, we can already move around with AVs in specific areas. We can also use Vehicle-to-Everything (V2X) communication for data exchange. For example, the Volkswagen ID series can send and receive specific messages for positional information, driver information, or general notifications and emergencies, which means there are already talking vehicles. Additionally, intelligent infrastructure is increasing, mostly in European cities, with one of the current flagship projects on the highways in Austria provided by the Autobahnen- und Schnellstraßen-Finanzierungs-Aktiengesellschaft (ASFiNAG).

This thesis will investigate the involved topics of Automated Driving (AD) and V2X communication, highlighting the synergy between both, with a special focus on Cooperative Awareness (CA), i.e., sharing of ego vehicle data, and Collective Perception (CP), i.e., sharing of onboard sensor information. Specifically, it will stress the benefit of the synergy between AV and V2X by highlighting (i) how the components can be aligned for an efficient underlying connection, (ii) how the performance of the overall combined cooperative system can be improved, and (iii) how an automated system can rate the quality of the surrounding V2X communication field.

1.1 Motivation

Modern vehicles are equipped with an increasing number of sensors and computing systems. Baidu (CN), BMW (DE), Cruze (US), Robosense (CN), Tesla (US), and Waymo (US), to name a few, are shaping the cars of the future. While some are more successful than others, there

are already companies in China and the United States of America (USA) operating fleets of vehicles with AD functionality.

Following the definition of AD levels by the Society of Automotive Engineers (SAE) (J3016) [1], shown in Figure 1.1, the K.I.T.T. is a full level 5 AV, capable of making its own decisions. Put in perspective, the currently available and operating AD taxis are only level 4 because they are bound to operate in a specific area and require guidance by an operator in some rare traffic scenarios.

Figure 1.1: The Levels of Driving Automation, as defined by SAE J3016 [1].

Stepping from one SAE level to another can be done with onboard sensors only, similar to how a human operates a vehicle. However, while each vehicle should be able to fulfill basic driving needs like a human, it is advantageous to integrate factual information that can be received via wireless communication channels. This wireless connectivity is not mandated to be integrated. However, additional information may increase comfort and safety, as the vehicle can receive information outside the Field of View (FoV). As later chapters will explain, this information can be transmitted between vehicles and others, such as other vehicles and infrastructure. In short, this is V2X communication, as shown in Figure 1.2.

Figure 1.2: Simplified explanation of V2X communication. The blue and red vehicles are equipped with V2X and can share information. In this case, it is perception information.

From a general stance, integration of V2X communication into AD systems sounds straightforward. However, looking more directly at the involved fields of research, one can see that research in the area of AD typically deals with perfect wired communication but imperfect data. Specifically, the components of an AD system within an AV are typically wired. Wired connections generally allow higher bandwidths and are less prone to data loss. Hence, typical implementations expect data to always arrive, except if it is not sent by the other node. Research in the area of V2X deals with perfect data but imperfect wireless communication channels. Specifically, most research in the V2X domain focuses on data transportation, less on the actual payload. Except if the payload influences the communication, e.g., due to big packets.

This is the point where this work chimes in. We found the gap between the research and development domain of AD and V2X, which made me interested in the opportunity to analyze it with deeper dedication. Hence, we systematically analyzed the core concept of AD software stacks from early robotics until State of the Art (SOTA) implementations and wireless sensor systems from early submarine trackers to Internet of Things (IoT) networks. The result is the concept of sensing, transmission, and fusion. From this perspective, integrating received V2X data into an AD stack is as simple as integrating a sensor. Integrating sending of V2X data is as simple as sharing debug information. This is Vehicle-to-Everything-as-a-Sensor (V2XaaS).

V2XaaS comprises many applications, such as sharing traffic jam warnings, detected objects, or planned maneuvers. However, implementing all existing and proposed standards is a high effort. Hence, this work focuses on CA and CP, which is optimal, as those applications are

most performance-critical. The application of CA is in major parts SOTA. In contrast, CP was only recently released as a full standard.

The performance analysis from analyzing the V2XaaS system provides many interesting insights, such as the basic delay of components and subcomponents in low traffic conditions or with high channel load. However, specifying the current Quality of Service (QoS) of the V2XaaS system is complex. Knowing about the QoS of the surrounding V2XaaS systems is even more complex. In short, the surrounding V2X field is missing a metric to pinpoint its QoS.

We tackled the challenge of missing QoS metrics for the surrounding V2X field by analyzing the performance results and by identifying key indicators for QoS. Those indicators are then filled with details from the performance analysis to design a metric to rate the surrounding V2X field for its current provided QoS.

1.2 Research Questions

The vision of this work is to assist the domain of AD to create an AV, such as K.I.T.T. from Knight Rider, as discussed initially. This can be graphically represented as shown in Figure 1.3. My mission is to provide the basis for integrating V2XaaS into an AD stack. This comprises three separate elements. First, identifying and defining the components necessary for V2XaaS and integrating V2XaaS into an AD stack. Second, quantifying the benefits and weaknesses expected by V2XaaS. Third, providing a metric for the quality and applicability of V2XaaS to the AD system. The three Research Questions (RQs) guiding the course of this work are discussed in the following.

Figure 1.3: Vision, Mission, and Goals of this thesis.

RQ1 What are the components of V2XaaS, and how do they interact and influence each other?

The baseline of every analysis is the definition of the system itself. RQ1 asks for the fundamental components of V2XaaS. The analysis deals with a review of sensor systems in the automotive domain, across to IoT systems, and down to early maritime sensor networks to detect submarines. In the process, commonalities are identified and applied to the automotive domain.

The analysis leads to the development of a general concept. This general concept highlights the dependencies between the core components, i.e., sensing, communication, and fusion. This allows cross-dependency discussion from the earliest steps to the final application on a top level. Further investigation then identifies subcomponents, such as sensor data acquisition, object detection, or packing and unpacking transmission data.

This finer-grained detail allows the discussion of different implementations and their effects on the overall processing chain. RQ1 is finally connected to RQ2 by implementing one of two combinations of favorable subcomponents with SOTA available technology. The other favorable combination relies on Millimeter Wave (mmWave) technology, which is still not ready for field tests at the time of writing.

RQ2 What performance can one expect from V2XaaS, and where are its limitations?

In RQ2, we use the V2XaaS stack, implemented to connect RQ1 and RQ2 to analyze critical performance parameters. Most prominently, those parameters revolve around accuracy and delay.

The gathered performance metrics are used to compare V2XaaS data to the performance of the onboard sensors, as well as to expectations from simulations and field tests in related research. The discussions allow for a more complete and detailed picture of the system. This also includes critical discussions on the performance in loaded V2X channels and the threat of adversarial senders.

Finally, the benefits of the FoV extension through V2XaaS are highlighted, put again in perspective compared to onboard perception performance, and in contrast to important discussions on security and trustworthiness.

RQ3 How can one rate the quality of V2XaaS for the decision process of an AV?

The core of RQ3 deals with the QoS of V2XaaS. Following RQ2, we know how the V2XaaS system, defined in RQ1, performs under several conditions. However, different use cases have different performance issues. AVs in traffic jams deal with loaded channels and redundant information. In contrast, AVs on highways may suffer from a lack of information.

Hence, RQ3 aims to provide a general metric to rate the quality of the surrounding V2X field. The desired rating should describe the quality of the provided input data for specific driving situations of the ego-vehicle.

The final goal is to allow the AD system in an AV to decide from a simple indicator if the data provided by V2XaaS improves the already available onboard data or if the integration of additional data should be avoided.

1.3 Contributions

This work focuses on V2XaaS and its most prominent applications CA and CP, as they are some of the most accuracy-dependent and time-critical applications of V2XaaS, as will be discussed in Chapter 2.

The work leading to this thesis was published in several publications. They are listed below to provide an overview, ordered by the four categories: (i) V2X components, (ii) V2X demonstrator setup, (iii) V2X performance, and (iv) V2X rating. This also matches the Chapters 5–7, where a more in-depth overview is presented. The following writing style is from a personal perspective to highlight my contributions. This should in no part diminish the work of my co-authors. Every publication is a team effort, independent of whether I was a main or co-author.

[RQ1][First Author] The components of cooperative perception – a proposal for future works is a broad literature research on the elements necessary to realize CA and CP. Here, we analyzed the necessary core components towards their data, delay, and accuracy perspectives, which will be highlighted in Chapter 5. Here, I created the idea, concept, core research, and text, with focused contributions from Andrea Ulbel and Gerald Steinbauer’s guidance on paper writing. In detail, CP is analyzed from a systems perspective to provide an overview of the challenges that must be addressed. Starting from the system level, the individual components of sensing, communication, and fusion are analyzed for existing challenges and approaches to addressing them. This work analyzes the approaches for strengths and weaknesses and, most importantly, the unanswered questions. Finally, questions are raised about the interaction of components. In summary, this paper provides a comprehensive overview of existing CP research, existing challenges, and open questions that had not been addressed then. ([2])

[RQ1, RQ2][First Author (Chapter)] Vehicle Communication Platform to Anything – vehicleCAPTAIN is a toolbox designed to tackle various challenges in the research and development of V2X communication that we presented within a chapter of the *The InSecTT Book* by Karner et al. [3]. Here, we discuss the core software contribution of this thesis, the vehicle Communication Platform to Anything (vehicleCAPTAIN) toolbox, which was designed and implemented by me, with the focused contributions of my students. The latter are guided under my supervision to implement several parts for use cases, as indicated in GitHub [4]. In detail, V2X is on the verge of being integrated as an integral part of modern vehicles. However, the battle for the final V2X radio technology is still not decided, and the available message standards are complex, hindering research and development. Hence, this work provides a toolbox for early-stage development within V2X, called vehicleCAPTAIN. The vehicleCAPTAIN toolbox comprises (i) a set of software that mitigates the need to adapt for different V2X hardware vendors by decoupling and simplifying implementation, (ii) a set of libraries that supports encoding and decoding of messages, and (iii) a set of software bindings to enable development with Robot Operating System (ROS) 2. All software is provided as Free and Open-Source Software (FOSS). Within this work, we prove the functionality of

the toolbox with classic end-to-end tests, as well as Qosium, a quality-of-service testing application. Finally, we highlight the applicability and benefits of the vehicleCAPTAIN toolbox for early-stage V2X research and development.

[RQ2][First Author] Collective Perception: A Delay Evaluation With a Short Discussion on Channel Load provides a systematic view of the full delay chain from a sensor-detectable event until awareness of that event can be reached in another Intelligent Transport System Station (ITS-S). Here, I created the idea, concept, core research, and text, with focused contributions from my colleagues Peter Sammer and Udo Grossschedl building the vehicleCAPTAIN development kit, Esa Piri helping with major discussions on details with wireless interfaces, Gerald Steinbauer on revising the paper, and Lukas Kuschnig, Alina Steinberger, and Markus Schratte integrating parts of the software into the vehicles of the Virtual Vehicle Research GmbH. In detail, this paper aims to provide a systematic view of the delay chain involved. We implemented CP into two street legal Automated Driving Demonstrators (ADDs) to provide insight into the components' delay. The implementation allowed us to gather highly accurate QoS measurements for V2X communication in practical field environments and to gather a set of delay measurements for a working CP system, accompanied by scalability discussions. The results provide a basis for evaluating the delay impact of single components and the applicability of CP use cases from the perspective of time advantage. ([5])

[RQ2] Positional Accuracy Provided by State-of-the-Art Cooperative Awareness and Collective Perception provides an analysis of the accuracy that can be provided by a CA/CP system. Here, I created the idea, concept, core research, and text, with focused contributions from my colleagues Alina Steinberger, Lukas Kuschnig, Markus Schratte, and Thomas Neumayr, helping with integration into the AD stack, and Gerald Steinbauer revising the paper. In detail, CA and CP deal with the exchange of perception data within V2X. The achievable and needed accuracy has then not been analyzed in detail. The baseline for accuracy was only the data from simulations, recommendations provided by standards, or various perception datasets with a disconnect between localization accuracy and perception accuracy. We therefore extended a SOTA AD platform with CA/CP functionality in that work. We then deployed it on two street-legal ADDs and did an extensive field test to acquire data. With the data, we show the achievable accuracy of SOTA systems and discuss the requirements for future implementations. ([6])

[Support RQ2] Transnational Testing, Operation and Certification of Automated Driving Systems: Perspective from testEPS and Central System EUREKA Projects – Mid-Term Results is about testing AD systems in general and the usage of V2X in specific. The research conducted for this paper confirmed the vehicleCAPTAIN's performance in other V2X scenarios than CA/CP. Here, I provided the vehicleCAPTAIN toolbox and aided the setup, orchestration, and evaluation of tests from V2X perspective. In detail, this conference paper presented the mid-term results of the two EUREKA projects, "testEPS" and "Central System". The underlying goal is to highlight the integration of V2X technologies into SOTA

vehicle stacks. Related to this thesis is the need for a performant V2X system regarding delay and connectivity. Furthermore, use cases used various V2X messages handled by the vehicleCAPTAIN, confirming the need for lightweight and message-independent hardware and software. ([7])

[Support RQ2] Centimeter-level GNSS Positioning Using C-ITS for Correction Data Delivery: An Experimental Study is about the integration of Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) correctional data received via Radio Technical Commission For Maritime Services Extended Messages (RTCMEMs). Here, I provided the vehicleCAPTAIN toolbox and aided the setup, orchestration, and evaluation of tests from V2X perspective. In detail, a study including test drives was performed to analyze V2X as a novel way of transmitting GNSS correction data into common vehicles and AVs to achieve centimeter-level GNSS positioning accuracy. The results of using V2X and the vehicleCAPTAIN toolbox are compared to traditional 4th Generation Mobile Networks (4G) mobile internet connection methods. The results published from this thesis show the need for low delay V2X communication as the delay of RTCMEM messages may cause inaccuracies in the interplay between GNSS onboard hardware. ([8])

[SupportRQ3] Shaping Automated Driving to Achieve Societal Mobility Needs is about the AD domain and how it forms future mobility needs. Here, I provided the vehicleCAPTAIN toolbox and aided the setup, orchestration, and evaluation of tests from V2X perspective. I also provided an analysis around the complexity of V2X, the challenges of integration for researchers and engineers, and the need for explainability for the end user. In detail, we discuss the application of Infrastructure to Vehicle Information Messages (IVIMs) to trigger the AD state of the AV in a psychological study. The study shows that V2X messages must possess low delay and be accurate in their application to not confuse the passengers. Switching from an AD state to the human driver may cause safety risks. Specifically, the QoS of the V2X system has to be guaranteed. In turn, the AD system also requires explainability, leading to rating metric, discussed in RQ3. ([9])

[RQ3] Addressing the need to describe the Surrounding Vehicle-to-Everything Field based on Channel Utilization and Information Influence presents additional QoS data for channel load and specific edge cases to discuss eight major factors that influence the surrounding V2X field. It combines all the insights gathered from the interaction of components over the performance to the applicability in use cases. Here, I created the idea, concept, core research, and text, with focused contributions from Lukas Kuschnig, Alina Steinberger, Thomas Neumayr, and Markus Schratte, aiding integration, Peter Sammer, building the newest generation of vehicleCAPTAINS, Esa Piri and Christophe Couturier, providing really helpful discussions on wireless channel behavior, and Gerald Steinbauer guiding paper writing. In detail, V2X can provide additional sensor information for AVs. We address the question, how can an AV decide if the surrounding V2X field can reliably provide qualitative, relevant, and trustworthy information? The AD software needs a straightforward solution to decide if the V2X information source should be integrated or avoided in a specific driving

situation. Hence, this work provides a metric to rate the V2X field by combining previous and related research with new information on edge cases, such as loaded channels. The resulting V2X field rating metric is a starting point for the AD system to decide if sensor information from the V2X field should be directly incorporated or handled with care. ([10])

Additional Contributions and noteworthy achievements.

- The vehicleCAPTAIN toolbox is available as a FOSS release via GitHub [4]. It is steadily growing.
- The integration of V2X functionality into the vehicles of the Virtual Vehicle Research GmbH was organized by me in close cooperation with Markus Schratter.
- The vehicleCAPTAIN development kit is now in its third version. I organized the build process in close cooperation with Peter Sammer. Twelve kits are available at the time of writing
- The vehicleCAPTAIN toolbox was an Open Innovation Contest Laureate awarded by the Intelligent Secure Trustable Things (InSecTT) project in 2022.
- The vehicleCAPTAIN toolbox won the Styrian Innovation Award in 2024.
- The vehicleCAPTAIN toolbox is basis for most V2X projects at the Virtual Vehicle Research GmbH.
- The master theses of Andrea Ulbel, *Analysis of V2X performance and rollout status with a special focus on Austria* [11] and Alina Steinberger, *Enhancing Automated Vehicle Safety Through Cooperative Awareness and Collective Perception* [12] were supervised by me.
- The Bachelor theses of Nives Krizanec, Patrizia Neubauer, and Loarda Tragaj were supervised by me, with the evaluation of the latter two pending.

1.4 Thesis Structure and Organization

This thesis aims to answer the RQs stated previously in this chapter. The goal is to systematically overview the components and performance of V2XaaS to find a metric to rate the QoS provided at a specific time. A special focus is on the CA and CP services as the most accuracy-dependent and delay-dependent use cases. In Chapter 2, we will introduce important terms and the general involved background for this work. Chapter 3 accompanies this with a general introduction to the evaluation framework, onto which all other chapters build.

The main part comprises a more in-depth introduction of the vehicleCAPTAIN toolbox in Chapter 4 before the three core chapters focus on the respective RQs. The first RQ is targeted by Chapter 5, which will provide in-depth information on the components involved in V2X, followed by Chapter 6, which uses the evaluation framework to provide performance metrics for V2X, with a special focus on CA and CP scenarios. The third and final RQ is then dealt with

by Chapter 7, where the identified influencing factors are discussed in detail and combined into a rating metric to provide insight into the quality of the surrounding V2X field.

In Chapter 8, we will then discuss the RQs, with the information provided in previous Chapters 5-7. In Chapter 9, we take a step aside to highlight the most important related research used for this work and discuss related research not already integrated into the core pillars. Finally, Chapter 10 will summarize the work of this thesis by concluding the work and providing an outlook on future works.

CHAPTER 2

Background and Terminology

In this chapter, we introduce common terms relevant to this work. The following sections directly reference the discussed terms when needed. Many terms are common in the respective AD and V2X domains. But they may not be in the respective other domain.

The background and terminology will explain the most common terms. The explanations are intended to provide a common basis for understanding this work. Conceptual and implementation details will follow in Chapter 3. Section 2.1 will provide the most common terms from the AD domain. Beginning with more common terms, such as AD itself, followed by more details necessary to follow the discussions in this work. The second Section 2.2 introduces important concepts for the V2X domain. It explains common terms, such as V2X, before providing more in-depth information on important concepts.

2.1 The Domain of Automated Driving

Automated Driving (AD) is the basic concept of a computer-controlled passenger vehicle, which we call Automated Vehicle (AV). When using a set of proof of concept AVs for demonstration purposes, we call them Automated Driving Demonstrators (ADDs). The following sections will describe the principle of an AV using the example of Autoware [13]. The sections will go into detail on the singular components, i.e., (i) the sensing, (ii) the localization, (iii) the perception, (iv) the planning, and (v) the vehicle control.

2.1.1 Sense-Plan-Act

Autoware [13] is an AD software stack based on the ROS¹. Autoware implements the Sense Plan Act (SPA) cycle in its fundamental core. SPA is a core concept known from early robotics, as discussed by Kortenkamp et al. [14]. It states that a robot has to sense its environment, plan its actions, and perform an action. This concept directly applies to AD. As shown in Figure 2.1, Autoware uses the same concept. Sensors like cameras, lidar, or radar are shown in the bottom left. The sensors are used for localization and perception. The result is then used for planning and for controlling the vehicle.

¹<https://www.ros.org/>

Figure 2.1: The Autware [13] architecture, with the underlying concept of sense-plan-act.

Autware was used in several development stages for this work. This thesis will describe the most recent implementation in Chapter 3. The papers linked to this thesis and lined out in Section 1.3 highlight more specific stages of implementation. Among others, the Autware stack was equipped with V2X communication capability.

2.1.2 Sensing

An AD stack, such as Autware, discussed in Section 2.1.1, uses sensors to gather environmental information. Sensors like cameras can be passive, similar to how humans perceive the environment. But they can also be active, such as lidars or radar. The difference is in their information, such as depth information or general resolution. The following paragraphs summarize a brief overview, with the aid of example hardware shown in Figure 2.2 and example sensor data in Figure 2.3.

Cameras

A camera provides information about the environment as a picture, similar to what a human eye can see, as shown in Figure 2.3. This can be used for scene description or object classification, i.e., to describe what kind of object is in the picture. If additional information, such as mounting positions, is known, also three-dimensional (3D) information can be extracted, as discussed by Hartley et al. [16]. Finally, cameras are cheaper than other sensors as they are easy to produce and small in form factor.

Figure 2.2: Photographs of sensors mounted to a vehicle, as shown by Schratter et al. [15]). In the left image are two cameras (red circles) and two lidars (yellow circles). In the right image are three radar sensors (yellow circles).

Figure 2.3: Sensor view of an AV, as shown by Schratter et al. [15]. The top row is a high-resolution lidar output. The sensor image is comparable to a camera feed with such high resolution. Compared to cameras, lidars provide depth information, resulting in a point cloud, as shown at the bottom. The fine-grained dots are from the lidar point cloud. The thick overlaid dots are radar responses.

Radars

A radar sensor sends out high frequency Electromagnetic (EM) waves. As shown in Figure 2.3, solid objects reflect those waves, and radar provides distance and angle information. Modern radars use sophisticated signal processing methods to calculate object distance, angle, and speed. Compared to cameras, the low frequency of radars makes them an excellent adverse weather option. However, the low resolution makes extracting size information or classifying objects difficult from radar data.

Lidar

Finally, lidars combine the best of both worlds. A lidar sensor emits laser pulses. SOTA sensors have a rotational configuration. The laser is rotated 360° . Also, multiple laser rays are stacked above each other to provide multiple lines. The resulting echo of measurements is called a point cloud. It is a set of points gathered around the sensor in a 3D space. With sufficient lines and measurements per line, the sensor image is comparable to cameras with depth information, as shown in Figure 2.3. Lidars' high possible resolution and precision make them highly valuable for accurate sensor data. However, lidars are expensive compared to cameras and radars.

2.1.3 Localization

Localization estimates one's pose, i.e., position and orientation, for a given coordinate frame. For a human, imagine having a city map and finding your position on the map via landmarks, such as buildings or street names, and the orientation via a compass. The same concept applies to AVs. An AV has different means to find its position worldwide. The most common approach is GNSSs. Satellites are equipped with highly precise clocks. This timing signal is received via a GNSS receiver. The offset between the signals is compared to triangulate the position. The orientation can be estimated with a second GNSS reference point.

Localization can also be done with a lidar sensor and its point cloud. One needs an appropriate map, called a High Definition (HD) map, to localize via lidar. This HD map is a point cloud of an area. Specifically, the area one wants to localize must be pre-recorded with a lidar. In a follow-up processing step, the point cloud is reduced to specific features, such as the edges of buildings. The final product is a 3D map. If a vehicle aims to localize itself, it uses the active lidar image and compares it with the pre-recorded map to find its pose, e.g., with the aid of the Normal Distributions Transform Monte-Carlo Localization (NDT-MCL) algorithm provided by Saarinen et al. [17].

2.1.4 Perception

Perception typically means the extraction of information from sensor data. To be specific, data from sensors, such as cameras, lidars, and radar, are used to extract information. This can be traffic light signals from camera data, movement data from radar, or extraction of objects, such as pedestrians or vehicles, from lidar data. Perception is the process from an object being

detected by the sensor via the processing of the data until the data is available to be used in other parts of the AD system.

2.1.5 Planning

Planning is the act of decision-making [18,19,20,21], within the domain of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Computer Science (CS). The general idea of an automated or autonomous system is to reach one or more specific goals with a set of possible actions. Section 2.1.1 discussed in the context of SPA how sensing is necessary to have knowledge about the environment and how acting changes the current situation. Planning is the step in-between, to find an action appropriate to the current situation, to achieve the goal that initially required SPA. Within an AD system, we typically need three components for the planning step: (i) the localization, as a basic reference; (ii) the perception, describing the surrounding environment; and (iii) the mission plan, stating specific goals that require a plan.

For this work, it is important to understand that the clearer the picture of the surrounding environment, i.e., the picture gathered by perception, the better the planner's output toward the overall mission.

2.1.6 Controlling

Controlling is the final component of SPA. It is the driving controller of the AV. Controlling a vehicle is called drive-by-wire in the automotive engineering domain. Specifically, drive-by-wire directly controls steering, braking, and acceleration actuators. The respective controllers strongly vary between implementations. This can mean direct steering and brake pedal control or a high-level controller that uses the current and reference positions to calculate the driving path.

2.2 The Domain of Vehicle-to-Everything Communication

Vehicle-to-Everything (V2X) communication is the wireless interlink between a vehicle and everything else, such as infrastructure, other vehicles, network backends and pedestrians. The following sections explain the terms involved, guided by Figure 2.4. Terms revolve around (i) the general definition of V2X, (ii) the domain of Intelligent Transport Systems (ITSs), and (iii) the involved standards and technologies.

2.2.1 Vehicle-to-Everything

The term V2X is the collection of all special forms of V2X communication links. This work uses a subset of those communication links, which are (i) the V2V communication, meaning the communication between two vehicles, (ii) the V2I communication, meaning the communication between vehicle and infrastructure, such as intersections and traffic lights, and (iii) the Vehicle-to-Network (V2N) communication, meaning the communication between the vehicle and the network, which is typically a central traffic backbone.

Figure 2.4: Interaction of V2X components. Diagram showing important terms, explained in Section 2.2.

2.2.2 Intelligent Transport Systems

The term Intelligent Transport System (ITS) is the general term for intelligent traffic appliances. When such ITSs are interconnected for cooperation, one uses the term Cooperative Intelligent Transport System (C-ITS). In the specific domain of AD, one can also use the term Cooperative Connected Automated Mobility (CCAM). A singular ITS entity that can communicate and cooperate, typically by having V2X transmission capability, is called an ITS-S. If a specific ITS-S is the center point of concern, we call it ego vehicle.

Going further to use cases, two important concepts for this work are the Cooperative Awareness (CA) and Collective Perception (CP) services. CA is targeted towards awareness. The idea is that all involved ITS-Ss actively provide information about themselves, ranging from the pose over dimensions to special configurations. This information is primarily ground truth, such as the length and width of a vehicle or its payload. CP, on the other hand, is the sharing of perceived information. Related to, sharing information gathered by onboard sensors and processed by the onboard perception stack, such as detected cyclists, pedestrians, or other vehicles.

2.2.3 Standards and Technologies

V2X communication has its early origins in the 1970s, getting more concrete in the 1980s [22,23], with early-stage systems of modern GNSSs. Soon later, the term inter-vehicle communication was introduced, but it took until the millennium change until Dedicated Short Range Communication (DSRC) was introduced [24]. In recent years, the standardization actions by the European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI) got more track with

Intelligent Transport Systems in the 5GHz band (ITS-G5). While the physical layer is still debated, the standardized format of messages is used across physical layer technologies. The message payload is encrypted via the Abstract Syntax Notation One (ASN.1) standard and message specifications are publically available via the standardized documents and via the ETSI repositories [25].

Parallel to this, there was also much development on physical interfaces. In the early 2000s, the wireless communication standard 802.11 was extended with 802.11p. Over the last decade, a similar effort was made by the 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP) to adapt the mobile network standard, which resulted in the PC5 extension of the Long Term Evolution (LTE) standard. Updates to both standards resulted in the specification of 802.11bd and Cellular Vehicle-to-Everything (C-V2X). The latter is based on the 5th Generation Mobile Networks (5G) standard. When comparing the literature, one can find that the later stages of both technologies have big similarities, each with advantages in minor areas. Which technology is finally going to win has not yet been decided. However, it is largely irrelevant for the applications presented in this thesis, as the message specifications are the same, and both technologies use the same frequencies in the band of around 5.9 GHz, showing comparable performance.

CHAPTER 3

Evaluation Framework

This work uses the ADDs of the Virtual Vehicle Research GmbH, with an adopted Autoware stack for AD functionality and the vehicleCAPTAIN toolbox for V2X communication. This chapter will present an overview of the test setup and the equipment used for testing, such as Qosium and Y-Ghost.

This chapter summarizes the setup used for evaluation in involved publications dealing with performance [3,5,6,10]. The evaluation framework is the same for all tests. More details are provided in follow-up chapters where applicable. Section 3.1 will describe the hardware setup of AVs under test, with Section 3.2 adding the software perspective. Section 3.3 will then introduce the QoS measurement software used to analyze the performance of the V2X communication. Afterward, Section 3.4 will introduce the V2X communication platform vehicleCAPTAIN, followed by Section 3.5, introducing the V2X platform used for single ITS-S channel loading. Next, Section 3.6 will point out a few important details necessary for the validity of results before Section 3.7 finally discusses the integration into the used integrated measurement setup.

3.1 Automated Driving Demonstrators

The ADD setup is best described in previous publications [6,10]. The Virtual Vehicle Research GmbH has two vehicles with hardware and software components allowing street-legal AD in Austria. The computing hardware for both vehicles is three-year-old mid-range consumer hardware, as shown in Table 3.1.

Table 3.1: Hardware setup – ADDs. As shown in Pilz et al. [10].

Type	Ford Fusion	Ford Mondeo
CPU	Intel i7-9700K	Intel i7-11800H
GPU	Nvidia RTX 2070	Nvidia RTX 3070 Mobile/Max-Q
RAM	32GB DDR4	32GB DDR4

The Ford Fusion, shown in Figure 3.1, is equipped with four lidars, an Ouster OS2-128, three Ouster OS1-64, two FLIR Blackfly S Full-HD cameras, and six TierIV C1 cameras. The lidar point clouds are typically fused, and the result is fed into the object detection. The camera data is then used to label detected objects. However, for this work, we use the single OS2-128 lidar for object detection to have a minimal test set without the multi-sensor setup as overhead to avoid system loads. The processing software for this setup will be discussed in Section 3.2.

The Ford Mondeo, also shown in Figure 3.1, has a configurable sensor platform and is equipped with sensors, depending on the use case. This work uses a single Ouster OS2-128 lidar to detect objects. The processing of information is similar to the software within the Ford Fusion, as discussed in Section 3.2.

Figure 3.1: The Ford Fusion (left) and the Ford Mondeo (right), each equipped with an Ouster OS2-128 (yellow circle) and V2X antennas (red arrow), as presented by Pilz et al. [10].

3.2 Automated Driving Software

The used ADDs are equipped with the Autoware Universe [13] stack and extended with CA/CP capability, as presented in Pilz et al. [6]. The perception pipeline, shown in Figure 3.2, is essential to this work. The primary source for object detection is the lidar sensor. The lidar sensors' raw data is pre-processed and distributed to the localization and perception modules. The output of the localization module, discussed in Section 3.6.2, is used by the Predict-Plan-Act system and the V2X gateway components. The localization provides the geographically-referenced pose of objects for Collective Perception Messages (CPMs) and the ego-vehicle pose for Cooperative Awareness Messages (CAMs).

In parallel, the sensor data is used for object detection. After a pre-processing stage, including filtering techniques such as ground-plane-removal and a compare-map-filter, the output is fed into a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) for 3D object detection [26,27]. In the final step, called shape fitting, the shape of the detected object is refined.

Figure 3.2: The logical data flow in the Autware Universe assisted V2X implementation, running on the ADDs, as shown in Pilz et al. [6].

At this point, we must mention two different configurations of the perception pipeline for the Ford Fusion and the Ford Mondeo. The Ford Fusion uses a downsampled point cloud to reduce Central Processing Unit (CPU) load during processing for older hardware. This slightly reduces accuracy. However, the perception pipeline of the Ford Fusion introduces object validation techniques to remove obvious false positives. Tracked objects are fed back to the shape fitting to deal with under-segmentation and over-segmentation. This process results in optimized shape-fitting, which improves the result. In general, different configurations like these influence the accuracy of the perception, as discussed in Pilz et al. [6].

The detected objects are now fed into the local tracking algorithm. At this point, the process is similar to the localization process. The data is distributed to the Predict-Plan-Act system for vehicle control and to the V2X gateway, which creates the CPMs. The CA/CP data sent is received by the other vehicle with the V2X gateway. The CAMs and CPMs are converted to object data, similar to the local data. This data is then fed into the global tracking. The global tracking runs parallel to the local tracking and fuses the locally tracked data with the CA/CP data received via V2X. This allows to have two parallel data sets. One with local data and one fused with data from V2X. The current implementation relays the CAM and CPM data to the Predict-Plan-Act system.

3.3 Qosium QoS Measurement Software

Qosium¹ is a passive measurement solution, as introduced in previous works [5,10]. Qosium taps into the network traffic for measurement without interfering with the transmission and can measure the QoS for any Internet Protocol (IP) or Ethernet-based application over any network technology in real time. This allows us to conduct the measurements without modifying the communication system.

Qosium is a passive QoS measurement software, as introduced in previous works [5,10]. Qosium taps into the network traffic for measurement without interfering with the transmission and can measure the QoS for any IP or Ethernet-based application over any network

¹<https://www.kaitotek.com>

technology in real time. This allows us to conduct the measurements without modifying the communication system. The measurement solution does not have limitations on applications for measuring or network technologies over which the measurement is conducted. The statistics are one-way, which means that both directions are measured separately and simultaneously.

The measurement agents, Qosium Probes, are installed onto two vehicleCAPTAINs for our evaluations. This setup allowed us to measure QoS statistics, such as delay, jitter, packet loss, and Packet Loss Bursts (PLBs). PLB refers to sets of consecutively lost packets. However, as discussed in the following, the probes are not connected directly to the V2X communication interfaces but to the ethernet interface of the vehicleCAPTAIN hardware. Hence, results do not include specific parameters, such as Received Signal Strength Indication (RSSI) values. The analysis is carried out for End-to-End (E2E) packets between both platforms.

3.4 VehicleCAPTAIN Toolbox

The vehicleCAPTAIN toolbox is integral to this work. Hence, it will be discussed in more detail in Chapter 4. With its open design, the one component allows a deeper analysis of the V2X behavior. The vehicleCAPTAIN toolbox is described in detail in Pilz et al. [6]. It is a collection of hardware and software components that allow easy access to V2X communication. Details of its features and the setup can be found in the respective FOSS repositories on GitHub [4], with an extensive description of its origin, purpose, and implementation in Karner et al. [3].

This work uses a Raspberry Pi 4 8GB computing platform and a Unex SOM301-E as a V2X communication module. The routing core for managing communication modules is running on the Raspberry Pi. The delay performance of the vehicleCAPTAIN hardware is discussed in Pilz et al. [5] and Karner et al. [3]. Figure 3.3 shows the interaction between vehicleCAPTAIN software components. A V2X message is received by a Unex SOM301-E, processed with the Unex V2XCast, and put into a ZeroMQ stream by the routing core. The ZeroMQ message is relayed via Ethernet to the V2X Gateway, which converts the ZeroMQ-packed V2X payload into ROS2 Autoware messages. The sending of messages works precisely in the opposite direction.

Figure 3.3: The processing flow for receiving messages in the vehicleCAPTAIN stack, as shown in Pilz et al. [6]. An ITS-G5 message is received and processed by the Unex hardware and software. The routing core handles the relaying to the vehicle stack via Ethernet. The V2X gateway processes the respective incoming message for the Autoware environment. Sending works exactly in the opposite direction.

3.5 Y-Ghost Platform

Y-GHOST is a V2X simulation and emulation platform provided by YoGoKo² which is used to load the V2X channel for performance analysis. It is based on a Nexcom VTC-6210BK embedded computer running under Debian 10 and equipped with an Atom E3845 processor at 1.91GHz, 2GB of Random Access Memory (RAM), and a Compex WLE200NX Wireless Fidelity (WIFI) module configured for ITS-G5. The channel loading analysis introduced in Pilz et al. [10] was used to replay pre-recorded CAMs to emulate a desired number of cars. This allows a controlled channel loading, from 0 to 1300 Hz worth of CAMs in 10 Hz increments. Note that for all tests performed with Y-GHOST, the signature of the messages at the Geo-Networking layer was not activated.

3.6 Important Implementation Details

For the validity of the performance results discussed in later chapters, the papers related to this thesis [5,6,10] provide details highlighted in the sections below. Section 3.6.1 provides the precision of sensors, Section 3.6.2 provides details of the localization algorithm, as well as its precision, and Section 3.6.3 provides details on the time synchronization for QoS measurements.

3.6.1 Lidar Precision

Both ADDs use the Ouster OS2-128 for localization and object detection. Hence, the accuracy of localization and object detection is defined by the accuracy of the lidar sensor. The datasheet [28] specifies a resolution of 0.3 cm and an accuracy of 2.5 – 8 cm depending on the distance. The angular accuracy is 0.01° vertically and horizontally.

3.6.2 Localization

Both ADDs use a lidar HD map of the Graz University of Technology Inffeldgasse campus for localization. This allows each vehicle to localize with around 2.5 cm precision, according to the lidar precision mentioned in Section 3.6.1. The localization uses the NDT-MCL algorithm provided by Saarinen et al. [17]. This algorithm allows highly accurate yet fast localization.

The lidar HD map has a GNSS pose as a reference. As the same lidar HD map is used in both vehicles, the GNSS reference point is the same; hence, we can mitigate the inaccuracy of GNSS.

3.6.3 Reference Time

The QoS measurements necessitate high-precision clock synchronization between measurement components. The expected transmission delays are within a few milliseconds. These low transmission delays require the clock synchronization accuracy to be substantially below

²<https://www.yogoko.com/>

one millisecond throughout the measurements. Network Time Protocol (NTP) cannot reach sufficient synchronization accuracy. Typically, the obtained accuracy of NTP is about a millisecond at best. Precision Time Protocol (PTP) allows reaching our needs. However, PTP needs wired synchronization channels to reach this accuracy, which is impossible to realize in mobile measurement scenarios. Thus, we base our approach for clock synchronization on the one Pulse Per Second (1PPS) signal obtained from a GNSS. Using 1PPS enabled us to reach below $100\ \mu\text{s}$ synchronicity with the following setup: we use `gpsd`, a GNSS service daemon, in combination with `chrony`, an NTP implementation supporting GNSS reference sources. The 1PPS source provided by the ublox GNSS module allows synchronization of the host device's clock without being directly connected.

We verified the synchronicity of the setup, as shown in Figure 3.4: the Universal Asynchronous Receiver Transmitter (UART) interface connects two vehicleCAPTAINs. One vehicleCAPTAIN triggers the verification measurement by sending data from its Tx pin. Both vehicleCAPTAINs receive the same data simultaneously on the Rx pin. Both devices store the current timestamp when receiving the trigger signal, synchronized via 1PPS.

Figure 3.4: Setup to determine the time offset between two vehicleCAPTAINs, as shown in Pilz et al. [5].

Comparing these timestamps results in the offset between the devices, as shown in Figure 3.5. The data shows that the synchronicity is below $10\ \mu\text{s}$ for most samples, with spikes below $100\ \mu\text{s}$. Outliers of more than $100\ \mu\text{s}$ might result from the software overhead of the evaluation method. However, `chrony` deals with such spikes, and as seen from the analysis in Table 3.2, the synchronicity is higher than the expected transmission times and, therefore, suitable for highly accurate measurements.

3.7 Final Measurement Setup

The measurement setup was similar in all publications involved in the creation of this thesis [5,6,10]. Figure 3.6 shows the setup from a field operational perspective. The lab setup is the

Figure 3.5: Box plot of the offset between two vehicleCAPTAINs during time synchronization evaluation, as shown in Pilz et al. [5].

Table 3.2: Significant metrics of the time offset between two vehicleCAPTAINs, with 1PPS synchronization, as shown in Pilz et al. [5].

Metric	Value [μs]
minimum offset	0.0
maximum offset	115.871
average offset	6.967
median	4.768
interquartile range	5.722

same, but without vehicles, i.e., communication only. From a field perspective, two street-legal ADDs are equipped with Autoware, discussed in Section 3.2. Qosium is used to conduct and evaluate measurements for the QoS analysis.

The Qosium measurement setups are always E2E between two vehicleCAPTAINs, as shown in Figure 3.6. The Qosium measurement agent, Qosium Probe, is installed on the vehicleCAPTAIN platforms, and the measurement is carried out on their respective Ethernet interface instead of the V2X communications modules. The most emphasis in our analysis is put on one-way delay, jitter, message loss ratio, and message loss bursts, also considering the measured traffic statistics. The radio interface statistics, such as RSSI, were not collected in the experiments.

For channel loading, we used two different methods. We used the Y-Ghost system to control channel loading from a single ITS-S. And we used an array of vehicleCAPTAIN development kits for channel loading with multiple ITS-Ss. Section 3.6 provides a few details necessary for reference towards the validity of results.

Figure 3.6: Basic test setup from field perspective (clockwise), as shown in Pilz et al. [10]. The Autoware system provides CA/CP data. The V2X gateway prepares and sends the data via Ethernet to the vehicleCAPTAIN routing core, which arranges transmission via ITS-G5. The Qosium probe detects the packet when passing through the Ethernet interface. The receiving process is mirrored.

CHAPTER 4

The vehicleCAPTAIN Toolbox

This thesis's most important core component is the vehicleCAPTAIN toolbox. It is the basis for the research conducted in this thesis. The vehicleCAPTAIN toolbox also received positive feedback from the V2X community, and other research teams actively use several parts.

This chapter will introduce the toolbox's purpose, components, and development history. This is done by formally introducing the vehicleCAPTAIN toolbox in Section 4.1, continued by the underlying problem that created the need for such a toolbox in Section 4.2. Section 4.3 then introduces the developed solution and core element, the vehicleCAPTAIN toolbox. The validation of this toolbox is then discussed in Section 4.4 with a summary of key performance indicators presented in Section 4.5. Finally, Section 4.6 concludes the introduction of the vehicleCAPTAIN toolbox as the fundamental core of the work presented in this thesis and the work surrounding this thesis.

4.1 Introduction

Automotive research started the standardization of the wireless standard 802.11p for V2V communication in the early 2000s. Nowadays, the standard includes, among others, V2I and V2N, the latter meaning communication via web-service backends. The family of vehicle communications with everything else is called V2X communication. From the technology perspective, the 802.11p standard was released in 2010 by the Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers (IEEE) [29]. This is derived from the commonly known WiFi standard. Then, in 2017, the 3GPP [30] released the C-V2X standard based on the PC5 side channel in LTE. It is important to note that the standards 802.11p and C-V2X(LTE) are from different wireless standard families and incompatible. The IEEE and the 3GPP also announced successors 802.11bd and C-V2X (5G-based), respectively. Before the hardware supply chain problems started in 2020, the four soon-available technologies competed for a central standard. To date, the battle is still ongoing.

Communication for ITS also needed a software protocol. The SAE and ETSI started specification in parallel with their respective protocols, Wireless Access in Vehicular Environments (WAVE) and ITS-G5. The network protocols slightly differ in their approach. Hence, they are not fully compatible. However, the messages found a common baseline. The ETSI consortia

defines the messages using parts of the messages defined in the DSRC protocol, which is part of WAVE. Nowadays, following the combined effort, all technologies mentioned above, i.e., 802.11p/bd and C-V2X (LTE/5G), are designed to use the message standards defined by ETSI, with messages such as CAMs and Decentralized Environmental Notification Messages (DENMs).

V2X development now has an easy and complicated side. The easy side is that there is a standard message protocol. The complex side is the multitude of (soon) available hardware technologies. Before 2020, manufacturers of V2X solutions provided mainly 802.11p systems but quickly adopted the released C-V2X (LTE) standard. Among others, Cohda¹, Commsignia², Yogoko³, and Yunex⁴ are providing On-Board Units (OBUs) and Roadside Units (RSUs), each with its own Application Programming Interface (API). Adding multiple APIs now increases the effort in research and development for implementing application software if there is a need to stay independent of the underlying V2X technology. Each company mentioned above aims to provide a single API. However, independent of the used technology, there is still the issue of adapting to multiple APIs and using other prototypes, such as V2N.

In our work, we aim to provide a solution for the interface problem. We created a platform that can host multiple V2X interfaces and route the messages from the interfaces to the user and from the user to the respective interfaces. This way, the user only has to implement one interface. The platform handles the actual hardware interfaces as a hardware abstraction layer. In addition, we also provide a FOSS message library for the ETSI-defined messages to get started, as well as a ROS 2 interface.

In the following Section 4.2, we provide more detail on the underlying issue with interfaces. In Section 4.3, we present the vehicleCAPTAIN as the solution. The functionality of the vehicleCAPTAIN is then validated in Section 4.4. In Section 4.5, we discuss the applications and benefits of the vehicleCAPTAIN before concluding in Section 4.6.

4.2 Problem Statement

V2X has several communication standards. The most common are 802.11p and C-V2X (LTE), with their successors 802.11bd and C-V2X (5G). The 802.11 family is compatible with each other on the lower Open Systems Interconnection (OSI) levels but incompatible with C-V2X on the physical layer. The C-V2X family is not compatible with each other. V2N extends the range of available technologies with various web-based interfaces, with Ethernet, WIFI, 4G, and 5G as underlying technologies [31]. However, V2N needs a management system that relays messages to specific users, similar to the Geo-Networking protocol, with middleware, such as Message Queuing Telemetry Transport (MQTT) [32]. Going a step further, there are also mmWave protocols [33][34][35] currently under development that may be included in the V2X communication domain.

¹<https://www.cohdawireless.com/>

²<https://www.commsignia.com/>

³<https://www.yogoko.com/>

⁴<https://www.yunextraffic.com/de/>

The complexity of this multi-interface structure should not hinder research and development of the application of V2X. Hence, there is a need for a platform that takes away the implementation effort for interfaces from the user. In other words, there is the need for a platform that is open enough to integrate new hardware interfaces with their respective APIs and have the option to configure the Routing of messages, depending on the message type, payload, and connectivity; yet also provide one user interface for straightforward integration.

4.3 vehicleCAPTAIN - a V2X platform for research and development

The vehicleCAPTAIN toolbox is a set of FOSS components, paired with a hardware development kit, designed for research and development in the V2X domain, developed by Pilz et al. [4]. It is designed to lower the entry barrier for V2X development by providing various software repositories with sample code and libraries.

The components, shown in Figure 4.1, are available as FOSS by Pilz et al. [4]. Essential details of the components are discussed in the following sections. Section 4.3.1 introduces the routing platform and the core concept of how it eases development with V2X as a developing standard. Section 4.3.2 continues by introducing the C/C++ message library, followed by Section 4.3.3 introducing the ROS 2 support.

Figure 4.1: The vehicleCAPTAIN toolbox is split into four major groups. These four major groups currently provide seven public GitHub repositories, shown in Pilz et al. [4].

4.3.1 The Platform

The core elements of the vehicleCAPTAIN consist of a hardware configuration and the software routing core. The hardware is required to host at least one V2X capable transmission interface. The software needs interface drivers for each of the used interfaces.

One can look at the High Level Architecture (HLA) of the vehicleCAPTAIN, shown in Figure 4.2, to understand how the platform works. Stepping through the sending process from a user's perspective, the user provides some V2X message in the bottom right. This message is encoded and relayed to the V2X routing middleware via a Zero Message Queuing (ZMQ) interface. The routing middleware processes and relays the message to the V2X Input/Output (IO) control. The V2X IO control again processes the message and distributes it to the connected V2X interfaces. The respective V2X interface implementation then handles the transmission via the physical interfaces and its API. Receiving messages works in the opposite direction.

Each of the discussed components can be extended with custom functionality. The V2X routing control may be extended to handle the Geographical Networking (GN) protocol or prioritize specific messages. The V2X IO control may use receiver information, such as RSSI or geo-location, to decide which interfaces should be used for future transmissions. The V2X interfaces may be extended to other technologies, such as mmWave, UART communication, or Morse code. In its simplest form, the vehicleCAPTAIN routing core is a hardware abstraction layer for V2X messages.

Figure 4.2: The HLA of the vehicleCAPTAIN routing core, as shown in Pilz et al. [4]. The left side shows V2X hardware interfaces. The bottom right connects the user application via ZMQ.

Last but not least, the vehicleCAPTAIN needs hardware. Currently, ITS-G5 communication

via the Unex SOM301-E and MQTT via Ethernet or plugged-in mobile network connections, such as 4G/5G, are supported. The Virtual Vehicle Research GmbH can provide schematics or assembled hardware, as shown in Figure 4.3. We currently use this setup with three modules. The Unex SOM301-E for ITS-G5 communication, the Simcom sim8202g for 4G and V2N, and the Ublox F9P for highly accurate time-synchronization via 1PPS.

Figure 4.3: The vehicleCAPTAIN development kit in Quad Expander configuration, with a Raspberry Pi 4 as the computing platform (underneath the circuit board). The Quad Expander configuration can host up to four mPCI-E or M.2 modules. The configuration is from left to right: (i) Ublox F9P with 1PPS, (ii) empty, (iii) Unex SOM301-E, and (iv) Simcom sim8202g.

4.3.2 Message Library

The ETSI provides the message exchange protocol for all V2X-related standards as ASN.1 encoding specifications in a public git repository [25]. Descriptions of each message element and the usage of each message are distributed across various public standardization documents. The ETSI repository contains scattered instructions on generating a C and C++ library from the specifications. However, it takes a few days of effort to set up everything.

A library can ease this entry barrier. Similar to Protocol Buffer [36] and ROS messages [37], a generator script was designed, which creates a ready-to-use library, as shown in Pilz et al. [4]. The creation process is shown in Figure 4.4. As one can see, everything is run in a Docker environment to provide a clean environment. A clean environment is needed for the ASN.1 compiler to be installed correctly so that the generated library contains clean user paths, which are included as generated comments in the header. Within the setup environment, the script handles the generation. At startup, the script automatically loads the newest ASN.1 specification files for ETSI specifications, its dependencies, and additional defined experimental messages from ETSI provided sources. After loading, the script provides a simple menu where the messages to generate can be selected. The options are (i) to generate

specific messages, (ii) to only generate standardized messages, or (iii) to generate all messages that are available to the script. Each selection triggers the generation of multiple C-Header and C-Source files dumped in a folder containing the respective message. One may already use this dump or the CMake option in the menu. The CMake option will rearrange the generated files to fit a library structure and automatically generate the required CMake files. The final library is ready to use in CMake projects. However, depending on the CMake version and CMake environment, it may be necessary to adapt the CMake syntax, as usual.

Figure 4.4: The *vcitslib* creation process, within its Docker environment, as shown in Pilz et al. [4]. On the left side is the setup of the environment. In the middle is the file creation process. On the right are the final files, which have been rearranged into a library.

One must say that vendors of complete OBU and RSU hardware platforms already provide such libraries. However, they are not free and also not open source. The latter may be necessary for research of novel message standards. The script provided in the repository allows the addition of ASN.1 specifications outside existing standards. The generated library then includes those new messages without any extra effort.

The *vcitslib* is a core component of the vehicleCAPTAIN toolbox and, therefore, already integrated into all necessary parts to allow rapid development. However, one may use a commercial ITS message library at any time. Within InSecTT, we use this library to exchange CPMs in the airport use case. One robot can detect debris and share this information via V2X with other robots.

4.3.3 ROS 2 Support

Research and development teams often use ROS 2 for rapid prototyping. ROS 2 also provides much debugging functionality. Hence, part of the vehicleCAPTAIN toolbox is the ROS 2

interface. This interface can be used specifically for V2X messages.

Part of the ROS 2 interfaces is the ROS 2 type messages as a complement to the ETSI messages discussed in Section 4.3.2. The ROS 2 type messages are generated from the ASN.1 specifications. To achieve this, the ASN.1 code generator [38], recommended by ETSI, is forked to include functionalities to generate ROS 2 type messages from ASN.1 specifications. The ASN.1 specifications are complex; hence, minor adaptations are necessary after the generation. For example, the ASN.1 specifications allow circular dependencies of messages, which is not supported by ROS 2 messages. However, the provided generator script handles those fixes and generates ROS 2 type messages from provided ASN.1 files and outputs a ready-to-use ROS 2 message library as source code and an installable package.

The other part is the ROS 2 V2X gateway, a translator between ETSI V2X messages and ROS 2 V2X messages, shown as HLA in Figure 4.5. The gateway is designed to use the vehicleCAPTAIN routing core to input and output ETSI V2X messages. Still, the internal abstractions allow straightforward changes with a different hardware and software environment for ETSI V2X message transmission. Furthermore, the gateway has handlers for every V2X message to account for the different requirements of the message itself. For example, the gateway may be used to buffer messages to control the 1 – 10 Hz sending frequency limit, or it might be used to pre-filter specific message types for applicability. In the provided form, the handlers translate V2X messages between ETSI format and ROS 2 format. The logic for handling V2X messages is implemented behind the gateway in dedicated message-handling nodes. Specifically, the gateway translates an incoming message, such as a CPM into ROS 2 format. A node behind the gateway takes the perception information and includes it into the AD stack. The other way around, a node may use ROS 2 messages, such as the odom-localization to create a ROS 2 CAM. The gateway then translates this message to ETSI ASN.1 format. The advantage is that one can use the input and output of the gateway on the ROS 2 side to debug V2X messages beyond the capability provided by network analyzing tools, such as Wireshark. Additionally, the abstraction allows for the decoupling of message translation from the actual implementation, i.e., one can focus on generating and interpreting messages without dealing with translation and validation.

4.4 Validation

The functionality of the vehicleCAPTAIN is regularly tested in the lab environment, and its performance is validated with the aid of Qosium⁵, provided by the InSecTT partner Kaitotek. This section will discuss the validity of transmission, i.e., if messages are passed through correctly in the transmission process. In parallel, the journal paper by Pilz et al. [5] has focused on highly time-accurate delay measurements and packet loss caused by the wireless connectivity, including the overhead of the vehicleCAPTAIN platform, thereby proving its overall functionality.

This section will analyze the system and how the payload transmission can be proven. Section 4.4.1 will briefly discuss the input/output relation of the vehicleCAPTAIN before

⁵<https://www.kaitotek.com>

Figure 4.5: The vehicleCAPTAIN gateway for ROS 2 is a translator between ASN.1 encoded V2X messages and ROS 2 encoded V2X messages. The gateway is compatible with the vehicleCAPTAIN routing core but can be easily adapted to support other specific interfaces, as shown in Pilz et al. [4].

explaining the test setups. Section 4.4.2 will then show the found statistics before Section 4.4.3 reviews the outcome.

4.4.1 Test Methodology

If one has two vehicleCAPTAINs, one sender and one receiver, the messages' payload on both ends must be the same, as discussed in Section 4.3.1. Three separate tests validate this expected behavior: (i) the input/output validation with simple senders and receivers, (ii) the input/output validation with the ROS 2 gateway, and (iii) the packet loss test within a field application.

In the first two cases, the two vehicleCAPTAINs stand side-by-side in the lab, as shown in Figure 4.6. In those two cases, the aim is zero packet loss, as the goal is to validate the correctness of the transmission. The third test is a comparison of field applications with likely packet loss.

The first case is simple input/output testing to validate that the message content stays the same and that the code has no information loss. The data is sent out via vehicleCAPTAIN A with a set frequency. The data is then received with vehicleCAPTAIN B and compared for integrity. The used message test set consists of the following ten ASN.1 encoded bitstreams:

- header only
- header with maximum payload
- CAM with mandatory default payload

Figure 4.6: Two vehicleCAPTAIN development kits stand on each other for continuous integration tests, as shown in Karner et al. [3].

- CPM with mandatory default payload
- DENM with mandatory default payload
- IVIM with mandatory default payload
- CAM with pre-recorded payload
- CPM with pre-recorded payload
- DENM with pre-recorded payload
- IVIM with pre-recorded payload

The second test is similar. Here, we additionally use the ROS 2 gateway to validate that the transmission and encoder are working correctly. Hence, the ROS 2 gateway generates CAM data with our ADDs simulation environment and sends them via vehicleCAPTAIN A. The data is then received with vehicleCAPTAIN B, respectively, the second gateway, and we compare the received and sent messages again for integrity.

The third case aims to test the packet loss in a field scenario. This time, Qosium probes are installed on the vehicleCAPTAIN hardware and check the incoming and outgoing ZMQ Transmission Control Protocol (TCP)/IP packets for integrity. The vehicleCAPTAINs are mounted into two streets legal ADDs of the Virtual Vehicle Research GmbH. During the tests, the ADDs drive around a building block of 100×250 m with specific distances.

4.4.2 Results

The results are provided in three tables. Table 4.1 shows the simple sending and receiving results. The packet loss is minimal, as expected in a side-by-side laboratory setup. Also, the distribution of lost messages was as expected. Messages with bigger payloads are more likely to be dropped than messages with smaller payloads.

The results shown in Table 4.2 show that the ROS 2 gateway is working correctly, as the messages sent out equal the messages coming in on the other end. Again, there is a slight packet loss, which is to be expected in wireless transmission scenarios.

Finally, shown in Table 4.3 is an excerpt of the measurements conducted with Qosium. Here, one can see a different metric for counting packets. Qosium averages the quality of service results over a definable period, in our case, 1000 ms. Hence, Table 4.3 shows the sum of averaging periods with the direct result of overall packet loss.

4.4.3 Discussion

The results presented in Section 4.4.2 show the platform's fundamental capability to relay messages reliably. Results shown in Table 4.1 and Table 4.2 show that messages can be transmitted reliably, with packet loss as can be expected in wireless communication scenarios. Table 4.3 then includes packet loss results from test drives where the line of sight between sender and receiver was obstructed. The packet loss in those scenarios is as expected. The

Table 4.1: Simple Sender Receiver Tests, as shown in Karner et al. [3].

Sending Frequency [Hz]	$\sum sent$ [#]	$\sum received$ [#]	Packet Loss [%] ^a
1 Hz	1000	999	0.10
10 Hz	10000	9971	0.29
20 Hz	10000	9963	0.37

^a Each message in the set is transmitted at least once correctly.

Table 4.2: ROS 2 Gateway Sender Receiver Tests, as shown in Karner et al. [3]

Sending Frequency [Hz]	$\sum sent$ [#]	$\sum received$ [#]	Packet Loss [%]
1 Hz	1021	1019	0.20
10 Hz	10113	10085	0.28
20 Hz	10125	10084	0.41

Table 4.3: Qosium Packet Loss Test, as shown in Karner et al. [3]. Driving around a building complex (100×250 m) with different distances at the Graz University of Technology campus. Averaging interval (T) = 1000 ms. CAM frequency = 10 Hz.

Distances	$\sum T$	Packet Loss [%]
Campus Standstill (10m)	173	0.12
Campus Round (50m)	259	13.69
Campus Round (150m)	266	55.74
Campus Round (250m)	278	57.78

output of the vehicleCAPTAIN platform is also continuously tested with the aid of Wireshark as a reference decoder. Known issues are tracked within the respective GitHub repositories [4].

Overall, one must validate the other components, such as the C/C++ encoder called *vcitslib* and the ROS 2 message library. The conducted sending and receiving tests implicitly prove their functionality, as messages can be encoded and decoded. However, we currently only test messages we implement in use cases. In other words, both libraries are constantly under development because the V2X message standard is extremely nested and complex and, therefore, not yet implemented and tested in every aspect.

4.5 Key Performance Indicators

As discussed, the vehicleCAPTAIN toolbox consists of four major elements: (i) the platform itself, providing V2X transmission hardware and a software routing core; (ii) the ITS message libraries, currently supporting C and C++ development, (iii) the ROS 2 support, which consists of a ROS 2 type ITS message library and a supporting message translation gateway, as well as (iv) the additional tools, which currently support the generation of ITS messages for ROS 2.

Each component lowers the entry barrier for V2X development. The components are not designed to provide a complete implementation but to provide a basis for research and development. The toolboxes for ready-to-use OBUs, as discussed in Section 4.1, may be enough. But as soon as specific requirements have to be fulfilled, the vehicleCAPTAIN toolbox can help. Requirements could be the parallel support of different V2X radio standards, testing new yet unsupported message types, or using ROS 2 components.

4.5.1 Use Cases within the InSecTT Project

The vehicleCAPTAIN demonstrates its capability in two demonstrators. One demonstrator shows V2X management from the infrastructure side with a complex simulation and an actual intersection in Istanbul, Turkey. Here, the vehicleCAPTAIN is used to communicate various V2X status messages.

The other demonstrator showcases the sharing of perception information between robots and vehicles. This demonstration uses the *vcits* library to generate an encoder for pre-standardized CPMs. All of the systems in the demonstrator run ROS. Hence, the ROS 2 interface is also used to translate messages.

4.5.2 Use Cases within the Virtual Vehicle Research GmbH

The use cases are plentiful, as designed by the approach of V2X. To get a better understanding, this section provides an overview of scenarios in which the vehicleCAPTAIN toolbox is already of high value for the Virtual Vehicle Research GmbH.

The *vcitslib* is the most used component of the vehicleCAPTAIN toolbox. We use this library across various projects and in multiple scenarios. We use it extensively to share positional information for sensor fusion, i.e., CAMs for ego information and CPMs for second-person

information. We also use other messages, such as DENMs to react to active tramway crossings, IVIMs to react to speed limit changes, automated driving levels, and open bus lanes, as well as RTCMEMs, to receive GNSS correction data.

The vehicleCAPTAIN hardware and routing core are valuable because of their versatility. At first, we used the Unex SOM301-E for ITSG5 communication, which could have also been done with a complete OBU from another vendor. However, we soon needed highly accurate time synchronization between sender and receiver for testing and validation. The vehicleCAPTAIN hardware allowed us to adapt quickly by including 1PPSs synchronization via a Ublox F9P. The next challenge was to provide better connectivity over farther distances in city environments. The simple solution was to integrate a 4G module and implement V2Ns. As we are using the vehicleCAPTAIN toolbox, it was as simple as integrating a new interface into the vehicleCAPTAIN routing core. This way, we did not have to change any other parts, and all other use cases were immediately able to use the same way of communication.

The vehicleCAPTAIN routing core and its connectivity are used for major projects. Additionally, as mentioned in Section 4.3.3, we see high potential in using ROS 2 in our use cases. ROS 2 allows the reusing of components, enabling rapid prototyping and focusing on separate integration elements. In other words, at the Virtual Vehicle Research GmbH, we have street-legal ADDs running Autoware based on ROS 2. The ROS 2 gateway allows for a simple vehicle extension with V2X capability.

4.6 Conclusion

In this chapter, we discussed the vehicleCAPTAIN toolbox. The toolbox is designed (i) to ease entry into the V2X development domain, (ii) to provide a platform for cross-development with existing and upcoming V2X interfaces, and (iii) to provide development interfaces for rapid prototyping with ROS 2.

We found the toolbox to fulfill all these needs by (i) the discussion validating its design and by providing FOSS releases for its components, (ii) the validation of sending capability and performance in lab and field environments of the vehicleCAPTAIN development kit and routing core, and (iii) the discussion of use cases already implemented within and beyond InSecTT.

Development is currently focusing on switching to a more sophisticated implementation of ASN.1 generator, improving the out-of-the-box message support and providing quickstart tutorials for every component. Aside from those crucial steps, future development will focus on upgrading the provided V2X interfaces with the latest releases and integrating upcoming technologies.

Finally, we encourage V2X researchers and developers to use the vehicleCAPTAIN toolbox for inspiration and implementation, as it combines the know-how necessary for basic V2X implementations.

CHAPTER 5

V2X-as-a-Sensor-Components

Previous chapters discussed the Background of AD and V2X from a high level before discussing hardware and software components available for integration, analysis, and evaluation of this work. This chapter focuses on RQ1, which aims to analyze the components involved in V2XaaS to provide a basis for the overall system already introduced, as published in Pilz et al. [2,5]. The separation will lead to a discussion on the cross-dependencies of identified components and a suggestion for implementation architectures.

From the receiver perspective, V2X communication is an additional sensor for the vehicle, as discussed in Chapter 1. The difference to onboard sensors is the added need for data transmission via V2X. The transmitted data also has to be integrated with the onboard perception. Hence, V2XaaS consists of three components: (i) the retrieval of information, (ii) the transmission of information, and (iii) the integration of information by the receiver. To be specific, Figure 5.1 shows the components: (i) sensing, (ii) communication, and (iii) fusion. The diagram maps those components to the use case of CP, the currently most complex V2XaaS application. CP involves (i) the complex retrieval of information from the surroundings by a vehicle via its sensors, (ii) the transmission of that information via V2X communication, and (iii) the fusion of that information into the perception system of the receiving ego vehicle. The same principle applies to other V2X information, such as warnings about traffic jams, speed limits, and similar. The difference is the effort necessary for each of the three steps. Specifically, speed limits may be ground truth available to the infrastructure, while CP information is sensor information. Hence, there are differences in all three steps due to the differences in the complexity of the data.

Figure 5.1: The components of Cooperative Perception are (i) Sensing, (ii) Communication, and (iii) Fusion, as shown in Pilz et al. [2].

This chapter will continue by summarizing and highlighting my early research, published in Pilz et al. [2,5]. The discussion will target challenges that revolve around (i) the data involved, i.e., the format of detection and transmission in Section 5.1, (ii) the data delay, i.e., the processing time involved, in Section 5.2, and (iii) the accuracy, i.e., the reliability of the information, in Section 5.3. Finally, there is an essential discussion about cross-dependencies in Section 5.4, which leads to the proposed software stack, discussed in Section 5.5.

5.1 Sensing

Ground truth data is the best per definition, but ground truth is mostly only available for static information, such as speed limits and traffic signs. However, especially CA and CP scenarios usually involve dynamic objects. This means that ground truth is most likely unavailable, and sensors must be used to detect objects and their pose. Hence, V2XaaS knows two object types: (i) static objects, such as houses, trees, and traffic signs, and (ii) dynamic objects, such as vehicles, pedestrians, and animals. Static objects are usually received using map information and are relatively straightforward to integrate into the planner of an AV, as the confidence of existence is high and constant. Dynamic objects are more complex. They have to be detected by some sensor. If a dynamic object is occluded or not within the FoV of the onboard sensors, there is simply no direct way of correctly detecting its position. There is only the possibility of predicting such objects' positions with prior information, but such methods are inferior to the original sensor data. In the end, there are three possibilities to detect an object with sensors as shown in Figure 5.2: (i) the object is detected with onboard sensors, (ii) the object itself tells where it is (i.e., another vehicle sends GNSS sensor information via CAMs), or (iii) the object is within the FoV of a sensor of another traffic participant or infrastructure that can determine and share the position via CP.

Figure 5.2: The three possibilities on how to be aware of objects, as shown in Pilz et al. [2]: (i) onboard sensing (blue vehicle), (ii) sending GNSS position via V2X (orange vehicle), and (iii) sending sensor data via V2X (green vehicle and RSU). Onboard sensing capability (blue circles). V2X transmission capability (orange wireless indicators).

This results in three significant challenges for sensing that are described below: (i) the required data format resulting from sensing and processing, (ii) the delay caused by the aggregation and processing, and (iii) the accuracy of the sensed and processed data.

5.1.1 Data Format

The data provided by sensors can be available in raw forms, such as 3D point clouds, image streams, or preprocessed object data. Raw data has two advantages: (i) it has unprocessed information, meaning it still contains detailed and unfiltered information, and (ii) it has not yet used much time for processing. On the other hand, processed data is more lightweight, saving bandwidth, transmission time, and post-processing time. SOTA systems for AD, such as Autoware [13], can use both raw data formats and object data formats as sensor input. However, they convert raw data to object data early for further processing.

5.1.2 Data Delay

The delay of sensed data is caused by the sensor and data processing. The sensor needs a specific time to provide the data. The data can then be further processed or directly shared via V2X communication. The sensing delay is the delay between detecting an event until the data is used in the V2X communication. The delay also causes the age of information. Specifically, sensor data typically has a timestamp. This timestamp specified when the data was recorded. The time that expires between the first and the timestamp when using the data is called the age of information. The sensing delay adds to this age of information. Details for SOTA AD systems are discussed in Chapter 6.

5.1.3 Data Accuracy

Accuracy is a measure of how closely information represents the ground truth. The accuracy of sensed data strongly depends on the sensor technology. For example, lidar sensors have more precision but less range than radar sensors. Additionally, sensors need calibration to be accurate. This is the determination of extrinsic calibration, meaning the exact mounting point on the vehicle to fit the reference frame, and the determination of intrinsic calibration, meaning calibration of sensor-specific properties. Zhang et al. [39] provide a broad entry point for such calibration techniques. Additionally, adverse weather conditions [40,41,42] challenge the accurate discoverability of objects overall. In CP's context, inaccuracies must be accounted for during fusion and planning.

5.2 Communication

To spread information, data has to be transmitted from one ITS-S to another. Wired interfaces are, of course, no practical option for individual traffic. Hence, V2X communication is based on wireless interfaces. SOTA V2X interfaces operate in Centimeter Wave (cmWave) bands around 6 GHz and use messages defined by ETSI, as discussed in Section 2.2. There are also

V2X technologies under development in the mmWave band above 30 GHz that provide a much higher data rate. However, they are highly directional and not yet market-ready.

The following paragraphs discuss (i) the data rate, possible with different technologies, (ii) the data delay caused by the transmission, and (iii) the data accuracy in terms of reliability of transmission.

5.2.1 Data Rate

The data rate is the amount of data transmitted via an interface. SOTA V2X communication is based in the cmWave band, as discussed in Section 2.2. A review of specifications suggests similar performance for all four technologies, around 3 – 27 Mbps [43,44], depending on the used technology and transmission protocol. However, data throughput also strongly depends on the message format, as V2X messages need headers for communication, which take away payload [45].

Alternative technologies in the mmWave band above 30 GHz provide much higher data rates between 2 – 6 Gbps [46]. However, mmWave is a highly directional form of communication. Besides the effort still necessary for development and specification, mmWave technologies should be seen as a single connection towards one ITS-S due to the limitation of directional beams. The premise of falling back to a single connection style means the communication will suffer performance due to the necessary multi-hop communication. Even more, mmWave is strongly limited by shadowing effects. Shadowing means an object blocking the direct transmission between sender and receiver.

5.2.2 Data Delay

The communication delay is the overall time needed for transmission, i.e., the sum of all involved steps, such as packing and airtime, as discussed in detail in Section 6.2. For now, it is essential to highlight that transmission times can, in general, be expected to be around 3 – 22 ms depending on the payload, according to Rauch et al. [47]. However, the delay may be drastically higher with high communication channel loads, up to a point where delivery can not be guaranteed due to channel starvation, i.e., ITS-Ss not being able to transmit data, as discussed in Pilz et al. [5].

The delay and the data rate also strongly depend on the data selection. The CPM specifications [48] define parameters to decide which data is relevant for sending. This reduces redundancy and, as a consequence, increases throughput. However, if data is deemed less relevant, the buffering of said data will also increase the delay in communication and the overall age of information.

5.2.3 Data Accuracy

The accuracy of communication is seen from the reliability perspective. V2X communication is designed to be highly reliable [49,50]. However, as the performance evaluation in Section 6.2 will show, distance and occlusion must be considered. Additionally, cmWave V2X is prone to channel loading by other ITS-Ss, as well as to wireless attacks by adversaries in the form of

spamming or spoofing, as discussed in Chapter 9. And mmWave V2X is prone to shadowing and loss of connections in dynamic traffic situations, i.e., when the directional communication beam is lost.

5.3 Fusion

AD systems typically get information from several sensors, such as camera, lidar, and radar. Each sensor may provide information ranging from raw sensor data [51], such as 3D point clouds or image streams, up to ready-to-use object data [52] with speed, position, and orientation.

Sensors are also inherently imprecise, specifically imprecision within distance and bearing, timestamp accuracy, and the probability of detection. These issues with imprecision mean that data from different sensors can not be used immediately. They have to be fused to increase the accuracy of the state estimation, which in turn improves the accuracy of the data available for the planner.

In the context of CP, there are two major types of sensors: (i) onboard sensors, mounted directly to the ego vehicle, and (ii) shared sensors, which is sensor data shared from other ITS-Ss. For CP, there are two basic approaches for the sensor fusion. Either fuse onboard sensor data first and then fuse it with shared sensor data or fuse everything at once. Both methods have their advantages and drawbacks.

5.3.1 Data Format

The data format of the fusion, such as point clouds or object lists, results from three different fusion levels within CP, as shown by Shi et al. [53]. The fusion levels are (i) low-level fusion [51], (ii) high-level fusion [52], and (iii) feature-level fusion [54], as shown in Figure 5.3. Arnold et al. [55] use the terms early and late fusion, which maps to low-level fusion and feature-/high-level fusion, respectively.

Figure 5.3: The three different levels of sensor data for fusion, as and shown in Pilz et al. [2]: (i) raw sensor data, (ii) feature-based sensor data, and (iii) object data.

Low-level fusion, meaning the fusion of raw sensor data, gives the best results for fusion, as few information is lost in processing steps, such as object detection and fusing those objects [56]. However, the amount of information in the data is rich and rapidly exceeds bandwidth

limits, as well as computational power [57]. Sensor data is, therefore, preprocessed to avoid bottlenecks. Preprocessing is either done by the sensor itself or via the preprocessing steps of the AD system. The processing of data can be based on features [58], which leads to occupancy grids [59,60], tracks of vehicles [61], bounding boxes [55], or similar. However, fusion of fully processed object data with basic positional information [62] is most reasonable for applications with limited bandwidth for data transmission, rapid fusion on limited hardware [63], or even centralized traffic maps [64,65]. Also, the fusion of object data is SOTA for systems, such as Autoware [13].

5.3.2 Data Delay

The fusion *data delay* goes hand in hand with (i) the input format of the data to fuse, (ii) the fusion method used, (iii) the output format, and (iv) the accompanying method for object detection and tracking. Pollach et al. [66] point out that integrating tracking mechanisms into fusion can speed up object detection and improve fusion, as object detection is focused on areas where objects are expected. But slow down the fusion process overall as the workload increases.

5.3.3 Data Accuracy

The accuracy of the final perception represents the perception of the environment to the planner. The imperfections of sensors, processing, and communication do not allow direct data matching due to spatial and temporal deviations or false positives/negatives in the sensor data, a general problem in robotic sensor fusion. Techniques such as track-to-track fusion [67] and Kalman filter [68] are used to mitigate such problems. However, errors may persist, and depending on the fusion method and the input data, the resulting perception might be less reliable than the onboard perception. One concern is the general problem of malfunctioning sensors, a traditional perception topic. Another concern is security and trustworthiness in ITS-Ss, which provide the data, as discussed in Section 5.4.1.

5.4 Cross Dependencies and Challenges

The discussions around sensing, communication, and fusion show that all three have interdependencies. Saving time for data preprocessing in the sensing step provides raw data, which is hard to transmit during communication. Yet, this data may be perfect for the final fusion. In other words, changing the data type in specific steps affects the delay and accuracy in other steps. Which overall is an optimization problem.

Optimization is most reasonable when approached with physical limitations. Specifically the physical limitation in transmission interfaces. The V2X domain provides cmWave and mmWave technologies, but there are also more traditional consumer interfaces, like mobile networks, that have their advantages and disadvantages for V2XaaS applications. Among others, the bandwidth fits between cmWave and mmWave technologies and the overall better

availability. Disadvantages include the need for a backend to scale the exchange of data and the increased delay due to the need for bidirectional communication.

In turn, the constraints set by selecting the physical interface sets constraints towards the sensing and fusion. The components analysis above clearly demonstrates these cross-dependencies and challenges. However, other, more complex challenges can also cause cross-dependencies, as highlighted in the following sections.

5.4.1 Processing Security and Trust

One additional factor for dependencies is the processing of security and trust. Messages with malicious intent can cause accidents, for example, in virtual towing or infrastructure-controlled scenarios. To prevent accidents and possibly fatalities, messages have to be secured. In general, data security can be ensured with encryption and signatures. However, encryption is only possible for end-to-end communication, which is not supported by the design of direct V2X communication. Signatures, however, can ensure message integrity during transportation, which is why SOTA V2X standards support this principle in their security header [69].

Digging deeper, wrong data may be caused by malicious intent of ITS-Ss, but it may also be a simple malfunction or poor calibration. Therefore, the research aims to open the field through mutual trust networks. Hurl et al. [70] and Yan et al. [71] provide a good overview of the topic and related research.

Finally, the malicious intent may also be a third party not directly involved in the CP but a target of the sensors. For example, Xu et al. [72] found that specific patterns avoid object detection.

5.4.2 Complexity of Processing

V2XaaS depends on many factors, such as the sensor data format or the transmission delay, as shown by the analysis of the components of CP by Pilz et al. [2]. Nevertheless, two issues impact the complexity of V2XaaS more than others. (i) How do we fuse the available onboard and shared perception data? (ii) How do we select which data to send?

Fusing of onboard and shared perception data can either be done separately, (i) by fusing onboard data first and then adding shared data to extend or improve the FoV, where the shared data is fused with the onboard data [47], or (ii) by fusing onboard and shared data in one step [55]. The advantage of separate steps may be that (i) onboard data is more accurate, as no additional spatial or temporal drifts are added through communication; (ii) onboard data is fresher, as no communication overhead is needed; (iii) onboard data is more reliable, as communication bandwidth may prevent a regular stream of shared sensor data, and (iv) onboard data is more trustworthy, as tampering can only happen onboard. However, the advantage of fusing everything at once is that there is just one step. This is especially useful if there is equal trust in the sensors or if preprocessing steps would lose information, such as with 3D point clouds.

Selecting the data to be sent is not trivial. Current ETSI specifications for CPMs [48] suggest that only onboard perception data is used, as fusing shared sensor data first and then

sending it as a new CPM might compromise perception over time, for example, untrustworthy data may be integrated and sent out with a new signature. However, the more critical question, especially regarding communication bandwidth and latency, is: how do we update information? Specifically, how often do we update the status of an object we are perceiving? Several papers propose improvements on how to decrease channel load [45,73,74]. Some go even further and use network-based decisions [75], or Reinforcement Learning (RL) [76,77] to predict which information is important. All in all, optimization is not trivial. For example, there is truly redundant information, such as the notification frequency of standstill vehicles in parking lots, and information that is redundant but important for safety, such as standstill vehicles at the intersection. If traffic comes to a stop at the intersection, the vehicle position is redundant, but avoiding sending those messages is a safety hazard.

5.4.3 V2XaaS in Automated Driving Demonstrators

V2XaaS is a new topic for AD but has already been partly discussed in other fields, such as robotics [78] and unmanned aerial vehicles [79]. There are open libraries for AVs to integrate, for example, CP functionality, such as CarSpeak [80], AutoC2X [81], and the vehicleCAPTAIN toolbox [4]. For research purposes, accessibility and modifiability are key features. Pereira et al. [82] propose to release a CP platform that promises straightforward integration. However, even though CP is a rather complex task, research teams such as Shan et al. [83] try to showcase working demos. This also results in accidental discoveries, such as Augmented Virtual Reality (AVR) applications [84,85,86,87]: merging 3D point clouds to have a global CP-assisted point cloud creates data that can also be used to generate an AVR for the driver.

5.5 State of the Art V2X-as-a-Sensor System

Previous sections revolved around the features and dependencies of V2XaaS, as discussed in Pilz et al. [2]. This section moves onward to the discoveries in Pilz et al. [5]. This later publication highlighted that the current standardization by ETSI focuses on cmWave technologies for the exchange of data. Other technologies for mmWave are still under development.

The selection of cmWave technologies is also favored by related research. Rauch et al. [47] were among the first to discuss the V2XaaS network setup, which was separated and extended by Pilz et al. [2] as discussed above. At the same time, Schiegg et al. [88] showed the performance of CP communication in a V2X simulation environment with a similar setup. Volk et al. [89] combined this research and provided details of the CP processing chain from a communication perspective extracted from a simulation. Cui et al. [90] provides an overview of other existing research. However, the authors above do not discuss details of the complete CP processing chain.

The alignment and timing of components of V2XaaS are best described with the use case of CP, as shown in Figure 5.4. From a general stance, an event is happening, i.e., the first possibility to detect a Vulnerable Road User (VRU). First, detection is possible through a sensor. The sensor needs a specific time to process and input the physical environment into sensor

data. This can, for example, be the shutter time of a camera or the scanning of a lidar. The data is then typically limited to certain frequencies to have a continuous flow of information. This means there could be a frequency of 10 Hz, and the data is new with each set. However, the delta between physical sensor time and frequency to meet is the cycle time that has to be accounted for.

SOTA perception systems follow processes, as shown in Figure 5.4. This can be done directly on the sensor hardware or dedicated computing platforms. In any case, SOTA systems prefer object detection before the sensor fusion, as this eases the fusion of different sensor types, as discussed in Section 5.3. The fusion of object data has two primary steps. The first is the data fusion, i.e., the combination of lists of detected objects and the matching and tracking. Matching is done to find the same objects, and tracking is done to fuse two or more matched objects into one final object.

Next is communication, which includes all of its elements. First, the data is collected, then packed, and then sent. The other ITS-S unpacks and redistributes the data. Details on the implementation will be discussed in Chapter 6. For this first introduction, it is important to note that the V2X data requires a second fusion step in the other system with the local data. However, details will follow in Section 6.2.

Figure 5.4: CPM timing, as shown in Pilz et al. [5]. From an event happening until collective awareness. Involved are (i) the other vehicle (top) and communication partner that senses its environment and sends the information via V2X and (ii) the ego vehicle (bottom) that runs its local perception and puts the received global perception on top. The CP fusion is run asynchronously to the received CP information.

5.6 Conclusion

In this chapter, we discussed the components of V2XaaS and identified them as (i) sensing, (ii) communication, and (iii) fusion. We also identified three parameters for each component that specify performance. The elements are (i) an indicator of how data is treated, i.e., the pre-processing of sensor data resulting in the data format, or the data rate of the communication interface, (ii) an indicator for the delay, i.e., the time from data to send being available, until

it is received by the communication partner, or the time needed for the fusion, and (iii) an indicator for the accuracy, i.e., the degradation of the data caused by the processing in the component.

The components were then analyzed for their cross-dependencies and challenges. The analysis found (i) the element of security and trust, i.e., the injection of malicious data by adversaries, which has to be prevented, (ii) the complexity of the processing chain itself, and (iii) the integration of V2XaaS in SOTA AD stacks.

Finally, existing standards and related research were analyzed to discuss the integration of V2XaaS into a SOTA AD stack. The discussion was driven by the availability of cmWave technology as the most viable automotive solution. In turn, the data provided by the perception fell into place, with object data being needed. The fusion was proposed as a two-step process, i.e., doing sensor fusion first, followed by the global/CP/V2XaaS fusion.

The implementation of this stack uses the technologies discussed in Chapters 3 and 4. Next is the analysis of the performance in Chapter 6, focusing on accuracy, delay, and FoV extension.

CHAPTER 6

V2X-as-a-Sensor-Performance

The previous chapter discussed the components involved in V2XaaS to provide a basis for an implementation. The work in this chapter focuses on RQ2, aiming to analyze the performance of V2XaaS. The focus is on my primary work, focused on accuracy [6], and focused on delay [5,10], with validating demonstrations, published in Reckenzaun et al. [7], and Lesjak et al. [8].

The data format for exchange and integration was discussed and defined in Chapter 5. This chapter now focuses first on the accuracy that can be provided by shared data in Section 6.1 before discussing the delay behavior in detail using a systematic approach in Section 6.2. After analyzing these two core indicators, the benefit of V2XaaS is discussed by analyzing the extension of the FoV of onboard sensors in Section 6.3. Next, the results obtained are discussed using the perspective of applicability in Section 6.4. Finally, this chapter is concluded in Section 6.5, providing a concentrated set of highlights.

6.1 Focus: Accuracy

CA and CP deal with the exchange of perception data using V2X. The analysis in this section follows our work in Pilz et al. [6]. The current baseline for accuracy within related research is the data from simulations, recommendations provided by standards, and various perception datasets with an unclear relationship between localization accuracy and perception accuracy. To improve this baseline, we extended a SOTA AD platform with CA/CP functionality and deployed it on two street-legal ADDs for extensive field tests to acquire data. With the data, we show the achievable accuracy of SOTA systems and discuss the requirements for future implementations.

6.1.1 Introduction

V2X is the communication link within an ITS, which allows an AV to get information without detecting it with classical onboard sensors, such as a camera, lidar, or radar, as discussed in Chapter 2. The information can be as simple as active speed limits or traffic jam warnings. It can also be more complex information, such as CA data, sent directly from an ITS-S to inform

everyone about its location. Most recent standards define CP information [48], meaning sharing onboard perception information.

The accuracy of integrated CA and CP information depends on the received information's accuracy. The accuracy of the original data can be encoded into the confidence parameters of the respective messages CAMs [91] and CPMs [48]. The car2car Communication Consortium (C2C-CC) specifies basic system profile requirements [92] that regulate the minimum accuracy, such as *RS_BSP_209*, which states 5 – 15 m positional accuracy, depending on driving conditions. However, specifications do not acknowledge the accuracy needed by AD systems. Related Research, such as Miller et al. [57], provides an analysis of the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) for a system that shares the GNSS data to incorporate the time delay of the transmission into the system. Others, such as Li et al. [93], developed an algorithm that selects the objects to send via CPMs, depending on if the information improves the CP. Finally, several system implementations are worth mentioning, as they show how CP works in field environments [94,83,31] and simulations [63,95,96].

However, the abovementioned implementations do not discuss the achieved and possible accuracy of the shared localization and perception data. Specifically, there is a lack of comparing the accuracy provided by components of V2X concerning the onboard perception in a fully implemented AD stack. Comparing CA/CP information with the onboard perception will provide a baseline for discussions of needed accuracy. Furthermore, this allows for discussing accuracy requirements on transmission delay compensation and global fusion implementation in future contributions. Hence, in our work, we equipped two street-legal ADDs with V2X to share CA and CP information. We compare the positional information provided by the onboard perception of the ego vehicle with the CA/CP data from the second vehicle. This analysis provides insight into the accuracy of single elements of CA/CP.

This work will describe the problem domain in Section 6.1.2 and describe testing scenarios in Section 6.1.3. Next, the measurement setup is presented in Section 6.1.4, followed by the actual measurements and their results in Section 6.1.5 and 6.1.6. Findings on the accuracy of CA/CP will then be discussed in Section 6.1.7, followed by a discussion on related research in Section 6.1.8. Finally, this work concludes the findings in Section 6.1.9.

6.1.2 Problem Statement

Within CP, object data is transmitted between ITS-Ss. The accuracy of the object data depends on three factors: (i) the accuracy of the localization, which is the reference position of the sensor data of the sending ITS-S, but also the reference position of the receiving ITS-S, (ii) the accuracy of the sensor itself, its intrinsic and extrinsic calibration, as well as the used object detection model, and (iii) the time accuracy, which is influenced by the time delay of sensor data.

This work discusses the accuracy of perception data for V2XaaS. For this, we compare the CA and CP information from one vehicle with the onboard perception of a second vehicle within three consecutive scenarios, as described in Section 6.1.3. We use the perception of the first vehicle as a reference, as the AD stack is calibrated to the onboard perception. In other words, an AV is designed to deal with minor accuracy deviations of onboard perception, as

will be discussed in Section 6.1.7.

The accuracy of the V2XaaS perception can be visualized with three specific questions. These questions will be discussed in Section 6.1.7 to provide a basis for future implementations and standardization:

1. How accurate is SOTA CA/CP?
2. How accurate does it have to be?
3. How do the standardized requirements compare to SOTA system requirements?

6.1.3 Method

We defined three scenarios for this work, shown in Figure 6.1. Each scenario includes parameters causing a deviation in accuracy, as described below. We performed each scenario twice. Once at a standstill and once with moving vehicles. On top of that, we performed each test in a different location to mitigate the potential for biases and errors caused by testing in a single location.

Figure 6.1: Scenario 1 (left): the ego vehicle (red) detects the other vehicle (gray) with its onboard sensors. The other vehicle broadcasts its location via CAM. – Scenario 2 (middle): the ego vehicle (red) receives its position from the other vehicle (gray). – Scenario 3 (right): the ego vehicle (red) detects a pedestrian and receives the position of the pedestrian from the other vehicle (gray) via CPM. As shown in Pilz et al. [6].

Scenario I investigates details of the accuracy of the localization of vehicles, i.e., the reference position for CAMs and CPMs. Hence, Scenario 1, shown in Figure 6.1 (left), includes two vehicles. One vehicle is broadcasting its position via CAM. The ego vehicle detects this other vehicle with its onboard sensors. The positional difference between onboard sensors and CAMs is the accuracy of CA.

Scenario II investigates the accuracy of CP. The simplest form is the inverse of scenario 1, as shown in Figure 6.1 (middle). The scenario includes a car that sends out CPMs, containing the position of the ego vehicle. The ego vehicle knows its position. The positional difference between the localization of the ego vehicle and the position received via CPM defines the accuracy of CP.

Scenario III investigates the accuracy of a full CP scenario. The scenario shown in Figure 6.1 (right) has two vehicles detecting a pedestrian. The ego vehicle uses its perception to detect the pedestrian and receives an additional CPM from the other vehicle. By comparing the positional difference between the local perception and the CPM, we estimate the overall accuracy CP.

Locations

The scenarios are carried out at three locations, shown in Figure 6.2 to mitigate potential biases toward localization with lidar HD maps. Additionally, the distances between vehicles at these locations are selected to fit the accuracy limits for specific distances, as defined by the lidar precision discussed in Section 3.6.1.

Figure 6.2: Measurement locations 10 m, 30 m, and 60 m (l.t.r.), as shown in Pilz et al. [6]. Satellite perspective (top) with vehicle and pedestrian positions. Third-person perspective (bottom) with highlighted vehicles (arrow) and pedestrian positions (circle).

The scenario with < 10 m distance is a parking space on the Graz University of Technology campus, as shown in Figure 6.2 (left). The vehicles were parked facing the same center point and ~ 7.5 m apart, with $\sim 83.5^\circ$ angle, to allow optimal detection by the object detection algorithm. This setup is below 30 m and, therefore, the best setup for the accuracy of the lidar. It is also the best setup for the highest amount of possible lidar points to ensure optimal detection of the size of the other vehicle.

The scenario with 30 – 60 m distance is an intersection on the Graz University of Technology campus, as shown in Figure 6.2 (middle). Compared to the previous scenario, one vehicle was turned $\sim 180^\circ$ to extend the tested parameters. The vehicles were parked 36 m apart, with $\sim 94.5^\circ$ angle. This setup is in the medium accuracy range of the lidar.

The scenario with > 60 m distance is a side street on the Graz University of Technology campus, as shown in Figure 6.2 (right). Compared to previous scenarios, the vehicles were parked directly facing each other, with only a slight angular offset allowing correct vehicle detection. The vehicles were parked ~ 62 m apart, with $\sim 189.0^\circ$ angle. This setup is in the upper accuracy range of the lidar.

The distances and angles were determined with a Bosch Professional GLM-100 by measuring the distance from one top lidar to the other top lidar. The angle was determined by taking additional measurements from the side mirrors. Those measurements by hand should indicate the validity of the results.

Dynamic Scenarios

Dynamic scenarios start like static scenarios, as described above and as shown in Figure 6.2. One of the vehicles starts driving in a straight line over the crossing center. The other vehicle follows as soon as the center point is crossed. The first vehicle stops when it reaches the same distance to the center point. The other vehicle does the same. Hence, there is always one vehicle driving, overlapping both of them. Also, the setup of the scenarios does not allow for the dynamic movement of the pedestrian, as the driving paths of the vehicles block a controlled route for the pedestrian.

6.1.4 Additions to the Evaluation Setup

The measurement setup consists of two street-legal ADDs of the Virtual Vehicle Research GmbH¹, as presented in Chapter 3. The following sections will provide additional details relevant to the V2XaaS perception accuracy test setup.

Details: Localization

For the validity of results, we add two discussion points: (i) the localization via HD maps is SOTA in many implementations, as it allows much better localization in urban environments, where big buildings blocks limit access to GNSS sources, and (ii) the inaccuracy added by GNSS can easily be added, as discussed in Section 6.1.7.

Details: Reference Time

For the dynamic scenarios discussed in Section 6.1.3, we synchronized the clocks of our ADDs via chrony and local NTP servers. This results in time variations of up to 5 – 6 ms. The delay will always be part of the CP accuracy. However, this is below 10% compared to the perception's 10 Hz cycle time, as will be discussed in Section 6.2.

6.1.5 Data Recording

The measurements are conducted for three static and dynamic scenarios at three locations. This aims to validate the V2XaaS system at different distances and locations, as discussed in Section 6.1.3. In Section 3.6.2, we showed that the vehicles use the same HD map for localization, hence having the same GNSS reference frame for localization.

We recorded measurement data for around 5 minutes for the static scenarios to create a statistically significant baseline. The dynamic measurements were recorded in one go.

¹<https://www.v2c2.at/automated-driving/>

Specifically, as long as it takes to complete the proposed dynamic movement with ~ 5 km/h. Which is around 1 – 2 minutes, depending on the distance. The CAM/CPM sending frequency is 10 Hz each.

The results are represented as RMSEs. The RMSE of the distance d_{RMSE} is calculated as shown in Equation 6.1. The input parameters are the Cartesian coordinates of the locally perceived (lp) object and the Cartesian coordinates of an object perceived via V2X.

$$d_{RMSE} = \sqrt{(x_{lp} - x_{v2x})^2 + (y_{lp} - y_{v2x})^2} \quad (6.1)$$

The RMSE of the orientation yaw Ψ_{RMSE} is calculated as shown in Equation 6.2. With the input parameter yaw (ψ) of the lp object and the V2X object, respectively.

$$\Psi_{RMSE} = \sqrt{(\psi_{lp} - \psi_{v2x})^2} \quad (6.2)$$

Finally, one must also compare the perception data in the same time frame. Hence, we used the *ApproximateTimeSynchronizer*² to match an object received via V2X with the same object in the local perception. This tool allows matching messages depending on timestamps. For this work, the offset is 100 ms maximum to compare the objects at their respective creation time without interpolation.

6.1.6 Results

The first data set comprises the bounding boxes of the perceived vehicle and the pedestrian, as shown in Figure 6.3. Specifically, we analyzed scenarios I and III and compared the perceived object size in meters with the ground truth. We obtained the ground truth of vehicle sizes from the respective datasheets. The ground truth of the pedestrian is estimated as 0.3/0.5 m width/height.

The second data set comprises the RMSE of the distances between the two measurement points in meters and the orientation in radians. The graphs in Figure 6.4 are ordered row-wise to scenarios I-III. In each case, we used time stamp matching, as discussed in Section 6.1.5, and allowed $+/- 100$ ms of time deviation in the filter, which allows 10 Hz cycle compensation of the maximum CPM frequency.

As one can see, the evaluations do not contain results for dynamic measurements with pedestrians in Figure 6.3 and Figure 6.4. The setup of the scenarios did not allow us to also dynamically move the pedestrian, as discussed in Section 6.1.3.

6.1.7 Discussion

We put the vehicles side by side to visualize why accuracy matters, as shown in Figure 6.5. The detected object size directly influences the center point of the bounding box and, hence, the deviation in distance. This section will discuss the issues with estimated sizes of the detected objects and the actual RMSEs before discussing the initially stated questions from Section 6.1.2.

²https://github.com/ros2/message_filters/blob/rolling/index.rst

Figure 6.3: Results of detected sizes $[m]$ by the ADDs Ford Mondeo/Fusion, in scenario I (top) for vehicles and scenario III (bottom) for a pedestrian. The x-axis shows static measurements (A, C, E) and dynamic measurements (B, D, F), each with distances (10 m, 30 m, 60 m), as shown in Pilz et al. [6].

Figure 6.4: Results of the RMSEs, as shown in Pilz et al. [6]. For distances $[m]$ and orientation $[rad]$, of objects detected by the ADDs Ford Fusion/Mondeo in scenarios I-III (t.b.). The x-axis shows static measurements (A, C, E) and dynamic measurements (B, D, F), each with distances (10 m, 30 m, 60 m).

Figure 6.5: The local and global perception, when vehicles are put side by side, as shown in Pilz et al. [6]. The ego vehicle (slightly opaque vehicle) has a local perception (blue), which is overlaid with CAMs (orange) and CPMs (green).

Estimated Sizes of Detected Objects

One can see in Figure 6.3 that distance is, of course, a factor for the sensor accuracy. The more lidar detection points available, the more accurate the bounding boxes are. However, compared to the scenarios shown in Figure 6.1, one can also see that the object's orientation is important to determine its depth/length. The Ford Fusion and Ford Mondeo had issues determining the exact length of the other vehicle when there was a too-straight angle, as seen in locations *E* and *F*.

Regarding pedestrians, one can see the issues with bounding boxes in general. Pedestrians are overestimated because crossed arms in front of the body or a relaxed posture influence how many lidar rays hit the target pedestrian. Pedestrians farther away result in fewer lidar points, so they appear slimmer. This can also be seen in the mid-range transition scenarios, where the pedestrian size has a much higher standard deviation.

In conclusion, the bounding box is suitable for general approximations of an AD system to determine whether an object is present. However, underestimating the bounding box generates an offset for the center of the bounding box, which is a major part of the inaccuracy within CP, as discussed next.

RMSE Evaluation

The most critical parameter is the RMSE of the estimated distances. It defines the general positional accuracy for our system. As discussed in Section 3.6.2, the localization only depends on the lidar accuracy, as the same HD map is used for localization. This results in around 2.5 cm localization accuracy, as discussed in Section 3.6.2. If GNSS is used for localization, one can add GNSS localization inaccuracy to the RMSE.

With the setup given in this work, scenario I, shown in Figure 6.4, compares the onboard perception with the localization of the other vehicle. Hence, the results show inaccuracies caused by the local perception, two times the localization, and time delay, which leads to two effects. First, static measurements are more accurate than their dynamic counterparts, partly caused by the time offset < 100 ms, as the object was at two different positions at two different times caused by movement. And partly by the tracking algorithm of the object detection reacting to movement, i.e., the tracking estimating positions and movements from the sensor data input. Second, the RMSE is higher if the distance increases. This issue relates to the bounding box size issue discussed above.

Scenario II compares the onboard localization with CPMs describing the ego position. As with scenario I, the accuracy decreases again because of the combination of the perception inaccuracies, two times localization, and the time delay. The similarity is shown by comparing the d_{RMSE} in Figure 6.4.

Regarding orientation, scenarios I and II also show similar system performance. As one can see, the absolute values are way off, but the standard deviation is slight. This is due to the abovementioned 180° orientation effect. In the 30 m location, we deliberately parked one vehicle with the back side towards the center, as shown in Figure 6.2. Yet, object detection decided it was the front.

In scenario III, the distance is less of a problem for pedestrians, as they are comparatively

small and nearly cylindric objects. Hence, bounding box errors create no significant offsets. However, the orientation is difficult to estimate if the person is not walking forward.

Accuracy of CA/CP

Using lidar localization, one can see that CA/CP systems with SOTA AD stacks do not compromise accuracy in static scenarios. The performance of CA/CP depends strongly on the distance. Errors are caused by the distance-dependent density of the lidar point cloud and the connected object detection algorithm that has to fit the bounding box depending on the point cloud data. In numbers, with a distance of 10 m and standstill, one can expect 0.2 to 0.3 m RMSE on average, with a standard deviation of 0.01 m. In dynamic scenarios with 60 m distances, the RMSE is between 0.88 and 1.73 m on average and a standard deviation between 0.49 to 1.04 m. The lower RMSE is achieved by the Ford Fusion, with the optimized perception discussed in Section 6.1.4.

For the orientation, one can expect an RMSE of 2.3 to 2.5° with a standard deviation of 0.07 to 0.7° when two sides of an object are visible. The quality of the orientation estimation strongly depends on how the vehicle's surface is perceived. Warped fronts of vehicles also influence the perceived orientation. Despite these issues, the orientation can be wrong by 180°, and the orientation of pedestrians is impossible to detect with the used CNN without movement.

The results show that the accuracy of CA/CP predominantly depends on the perception system and strongly on the localization accuracy. The AD stack of Autoware works best with < 0.1 m accuracy for lateral localization and, depending on the driving speed, between 0.1 – 10.0 m longitudinal localization. Object detection is in similar ranges, depending on the use case. A CA/CP system has to work in lower ranges if the data should be used as direct input, as the localization of the receiving vehicle is added to the accuracy. However, if the information is just used to inform other vehicles about the potential presence of objects, i.e., a vehicle approaching an intersection, the importance of accuracy may be discussed.

Finally, one can discuss the standardization specifications of V2X messages. As initially mentioned, the C2C-CC specifies 5 – 15 m localization accuracy, which is insufficient for exact positioning use cases when dealing with pedestrians in parking spaces at low speeds. However, the specifications may not yet include the newest CA/CP integration approaches, with the CPM standard planned to be released in 2023.

6.1.8 Additional Factors Influencing Accuracy – Beyond this Study

This work focuses on the current standard of CPMs. However, related research also deals with issues strongly connected to the applicability of CA/CP. Issues that influence accuracy, methods that can improve accuracy, and techniques that use CA/CP in other ways that need accuracy. The following paragraphs provide an overview.

The discussion about dynamic scenarios in Section 6.1.7 indicated that delay influences the accuracy of information if it is not compensated. The sending frequency is related to delay and, therefore, the mechanisms to prevent congestion [97,74,45,77,98,99]. The accuracy of a single message is the same, independent of congestion control. However, more messages allow the

AD stack to increase detection accuracy. The more information the fusion algorithms have, the more precise the result.

The validity of the data also influences the accuracy. In other words, when malicious data is received, it will corrupt the overall perception accuracy. Related research deals with cyber security threats [100,101,102,103], and methods to guarantee the trustworthiness of data [104, 70,105,106].

Technologies under development may increase the accuracy of CP. This work uses 802.11p for data exchange, a cmWave protocol. Related research deals with mmWave protocols [33,34, 35], which have a much broader bandwidth and allow sharing of raw data. Overall, as stated in previous research [2], the accuracy can be increased; however, with the results of this work, the necessary effort may be discussed.

This work discussed the mitigation of GNSS accuracy using lidar HD maps. If one aims to achieve similar results by using GNSS for localization, one has to improve the accuracy. This can be done with real-time kinematic (RTK) data or by cooperative methods [107,108].

6.1.9 Conclusion

The work presented in this section discussed the accuracy of a CA/CP system. The system is based on Autoware Universe, a SOTA AD stack that we extended with the V2X communication capability of the vehicleCAPTAIN toolbox [4]. The resulting CA/CP software stack was deployed on two street-legal ADDs to be tested for three scenarios at three locations. The result is a dataset describing the offset between local and global perception with RMSEs of the distance and orientation. We can show that the most significant errors are caused by bounding box errors in object detection. We also assume that the localization with GNSS instead of lidar localization will decrease accuracy. Finally, we discussed our results with the accuracy specifications demanded by AD stacks and accuracy demands provided by the C2C-CC.

In Section 6.2, we will discuss the delay of CA/CP systems. As discussed in Section 6.1.8, the delay and the overall accuracy are strongly connected. Integrating delayed CA/CP data into the active perception represents a significant challenge. Hence, in future works, we will fuse the global CA/CP data and aim to provide further insight into the applicability of CA/CP in street-legal AVs. Integrating the V2N data could be exciting because of the higher Packet Delivery Rate (PDR) advantage. Similarly, we aim to discuss data cleanliness and trustworthiness, which can corrupt the resulting fused perception system.

6.2 Focus: Delay

AVs and V2X communication open the window for sharing sensor data. In this section, we provide a systematic view of the delay chain in this work, following the methodology presented in Pilz et al. [5,10]. We integrated CP into two street legal ADDs to investigate the components' delay. The integration allowed us to gather highly accurate QoS measurements for V2X communication in practical field environments and to gather a set of delay measurements for a working CP system, accompanied by discussions about scalability. The results provide a basis for evaluating the impact of the delay of single components and the applicability of CP use

cases from the perspective of time advantage. Time advantage means how much sooner does V2X information have to arrive before the same information can be acquired with onboard sensors?

6.2.1 Introduction

CP is part of CCAM and ITS. CP deals with the sharing of sensor information. For example, an ITS-S provides sensor information obtained by, i.e., infrastructure sensor, vehicle, or similar. A CPM [48] is filled with this information and sent via V2X. Other ITS-Ss can then incorporate that perception information into their local perception system.

Detailed knowledge about the delays — from an observable event until another ITS-S becomes aware of it — is crucial if one aims to discuss the applicability of CPMs for the safety of VRUs. Rauch et al. [47] were among the first to discuss V2X network delays, which Pilz et al. [2] extended by structuring the delays into perception, communication, and fusion, as discussed in Chapter 5. At the same time, Schiegg et al. [88] showed the delay of CP communication in a V2X simulation environment. Volk et al. [89] combined this research and provided details of the CP delay chain from a communication perspective extracted from a simulation. Cui et al. [90] reviews existing CP system integration methodologies. However, details in the CP delay chain, such as communication cycle times, still need to be included and discussed.

The work presented in this section will revisit the analysis of the delay chain of CP, provided in Pilz et al. [5,10], to extend the baseline for discussions of CP use cases from a delay perspective. We aim to quantify CP delay parameters from a systematic point of view by analyzing the components of a live CP implementation. We aim to provide an overview of how much influence a CP delay element has on the overall delay. Discussion points are (i) the absolute amount of delay a CP element causes that can be determined from a working system, (ii) the amount of variable delay it causes, meaning the amount of delay that can be expected, and (iii) the maximum boundaries where CP becomes unfeasible. Expectations from the literature are compared to field-operational data collected from an AD system supporting CP. The implementation allows a QoS analysis of 802.11p with highly time-accurate measurements and a detailed analysis of perception and fusion components involved.

This focus section will introduce the delay problem in Section 6.2.2 and a method to resolve it in Section 6.2.3. Next follows a detailed description of the delay components of CP in Section 6.2.4. Afterward, the measurement setups are presented in Section 6.2.5, followed by the recorded results in Section 6.2.8. The measurements are then assembled to address the problem statement in Section 6.2.9. Section 6.2.10 digs a bit deeper to elaborate on the scalability issues of V2X before comparing the measured results to results from the literature in Section 6.2.11. Finally, concluding in Section 6.2.12.

6.2.2 Problem Statement

This section revisits the discussion on the end-to-end delay and the QoS between two ITS-Ss, presented in Pilz et al. [5,10]. The discussion of the applicability of V2XaaS is missing

quantitative data on the delay perspective, as outlined in Section 6.2.1. The core elements missing are (i) the delay from a detailed and systematic perspective, (ii) the details of the QoS for different field scenarios, and (iii) the limitations caused by specific components.

The delay can be addressed with three specific questions. These questions will be discussed in Section 6.2.11 to provide a basis for future implementations and standardization:

1. What is the baseline delay of a working CP implementation?
2. Which QoS performance can be expected in common field scenarios?
3. Which QoS performance can be expected from loaded channels and other edge cases?

6.2.3 Method

This section aims to provide a systematic view of the delay of a working CP implementation in an AV. A systematic view comprises three significant viewpoints: (i) the overall delay of information, meaning the time needed for information to be available in another ITS-S, via CP, after a triggered event, (ii) the QoS that can be expected across varying distances, and (iii) the limitations caused by components involved.

First, the delay components of the CP delay chain must be defined. This is done by extending the preceding work of Volk et al. [89], and others [47,2,88], as mentioned in Chapter 5. The core contribution is a systematic representation of the CP delay components, with expected results from the literature, as presented in Section 6.2.4.

Next, we analyze the QoS of V2X communication in low channel load scenarios. We thereby extend works, such as of Böhm et al. [109] and Altinel et al. [110], who studied the connectivity and link quality of ITS-G5, by a study on the E2E delay of an implemented system. The first set of measurements is executed in an environment with low V2X channel load, with highly time-synced platforms and software designed for QoS measurements, as will be described in Section 6.2.5.

Afterward, we present the implementation of a complete CP chain into our ADDs, which are street-legal vehicles controlled via a drive-by-wire system and a software stack that we present in Section 6.2.5. Here, we also discuss the performance of edge cases involving distance and wireless noise by other ITS-Ss. This analysis is then extended in the lab and the field by an analysis of the behavior of the system in loaded channels.

Finally, we aggregate the measurement results in Section 6.2.9 and discuss in Section 6.2.11 our findings in comparison to the expectations from the literature in Section 6.2.4.

6.2.4 Delay Components

Rauch et al. [47] were the first to show V2X-related delays in a diagram. Pilz et al. [2] then suggested extending those times and splitting them into three major components: (i) the sensing-related delay, (ii) the communication-related delay, and (iii) the fusion-related delay. The CPM delay time is the sum of delays of all components, as shown in Equation 6.3.

$$t_{cpm} = t_{sensing} + t_{communication} + t_{fusion} \quad (6.3)$$

The three components can be split into more detailed delay components, as shown by Volk et al. [89], focusing on V2X communication. Hence based on both Rauch et al. [47] and Volk et al. [89], Figure 6.6 shows the CP delay chain with four significant changes: (i) it takes into account sensor processing times, (ii) it adds a necessary buffer on the receiving end, (iii) it removes the reference of local perception of the receiver, as the receiver always has a local perception available, and (iv) it shifts the focus from the communication to perception and fusion. Shifting the focus to perception and fusion is done, as this work views communication as one complete transmission block. In other words, this communication is a complete message-passing system with QoS parameters.

Figure 6.6: CPM delay chain, as shown in Pilz et al. [5]. From an event happening until collective awareness. Involved are (i) the other vehicle and communication partner that senses its environment and sends the information via V2X and (ii) the ego vehicle that runs its local perception and puts the received global perception on top. The global fusion is run asynchronously to the received CP information.

The following sections will discuss the (sub)components of the delay chain. We back up this investigation by aggregating expected delays from related research in Table 6.1. In a later step, results from the live implementation are integrated into the same table, resulting in Table 6.5. Section 6.2.11 will then compare the expectation to the measurements obtained from a working implementation.

Sensing Delay

First, an *event* triggers the sensing phase of the CPM chain. Let this event be a pedestrian that walks into the field of view of a sensor, i.e., when it can be detected the first time. The sensor now adds (i) its data delay, (ii) its cycle delay, and (iii) its related object detection delay.

Sensing: Data Delay The data delay is dependent on the sensor type. For cameras, the data delay consists of the frame acquisition time and the frame read time [111], as shown in Equation 6.4. Similar principles apply to lidars and radars.

The data delay can be found in the sensors' datasheets. If it is included, the sensor data delay is usually close to the cycle time of the highest frequency. The reason is simple: the

Table 6.1: Components of delay with reference to Figure 6.6, as shown in Pilz et al. [5]. Listed here are estimates from the literature, as discussed in Section 6.2.4.

Delay Component	Delay Description	Estimate from literature [ms]
Sensing Delay	sensing delay	206-280
- Sensor Data Delay	from event to sensor image	camera: 25 lidar: 50
- Cycle Time	from sensor image to available data	camera: 25-100 lidar: 50-100
- Object Detection	from sensor data to object data	56-130
Communication Delay	from collecting to redistribution	11-254 + [100-∞]*
- Buffering	fastest (ETSI): 10Hz	2-100
- Packing	ROS2 and packing	2
- Transmission Delay QoS	C-ITS load low C-ITS load medium*** C-ITS load high***	3-50 100-500* 500-∞*
- Unpacking	unpacking and ROS2	2
- Distribution	sensor like: 10Hz	2-100
Fusion Delay	local sender and global receiver	4-6
- Sender (Local) Fusion Delay	local multi-sensor fusion	2
- Asynchronous Fusion Delay	local multi-sensor fusion	0-2
- Receiver (Global) Fusion Delay	global multi-sensor fusion	2
CP Delay Time	all in ***	221-540 + [100-∞]*

* Scalability (ITSG5): delay may be drastically increased by the Access Layer due to channel load. (Section 6.2.10).

vendor wants to provide sensor data with as high of a frequency as possible without giving redundant sensor images. So, the cycle time's lower bound is the data delay's upper bound.

We look at the sensor cycle time to calculate expectations for the data delay. For a SOTA lidar, sensor [112] this is 10 – 20 Hz. For a SOTA high-resolution camera [113], this is 10 – 40 Hz. In both cases, we expect the upper limit of the frequency to be close to the data delay itself. Higher frequencies are mostly not possible due to data acquisition limitations. Hence, in the worst case, the data delay is $1/f_{sensor,max}$, which results in 25 ms for a camera and 50 ms for a lidar.

$$t_{data} = t_{acquisition} + t_{readout} \quad (6.4)$$

Sensing: Cycle Time The cycle time of the sensors is calculated from the cycle frequency, as mentioned above. This leads to cycle delays of 25 – 100 ms and 50 – 100 ms for SOTA cameras and lidars, respectively. The best case is that the sensor completes its cycle before the interface sends the data. The worst case is having the sensor data ready but missing the cycle. Hence, in the worst case, one missed cycle has to be estimated. In summary, the sensor delay is the sum of the data delay and the cycle time, as shown in Equation 6.5.

$$t_{sensor} = t_{data} + t_{cycle} \quad (6.5)$$

Sensing: Object Detection Delay The object detection delay is created by extracting objects from the sensor data to be able to transmit them as CPMs. Starting with the raw sensor data, it is possible to (i) proceed directly with object detection or (ii) proceed with sensor data fusion first and then do object detection. Pilz et al. [2] point out that dependencies between elements of the CPM influence the approach. For example, fusing raw sensor data will generate better object detection results, but detecting objects first and fusing them later is faster. Also, Hackett et al. [114] show that the fusion of raw data of multi-sensor systems increases accuracy but requires a pre-processing step that introduces dependencies between sensors. These dependencies can be avoided by object detection first and fusing the detected objects later. On the receiver side, the fusion of sensor data from multiple onboard sensors, i.e., camera, lidar, and radar, is also up to the respective implementation. In this work, both the sender and receiver will follow the object detection first and fusion later approach. This approach means that object detection is done directly after pre-processing sensor data and before the fusion of objects. Back to the sole object detection, SOTA object detection algorithms can analyze around 7.7 – 17.8 Frames per Second (FPS), as discussed by Wen et al. [115], which is a 56 – 130 ms delay for object detection.

Σ Sensing Delay The overall time needed for sensing includes the above-stated sensor data delay, sensor cycle time, and object detection delay, as shown in Equation 6.6. Hence, given the information stated, this estimates a best/worst case of 81 – 280 ms for the sensing delay, as shown in Table 6.1.

$$t_{sensing} = t_{data} + t_{cycle} + (t_{class_fusion}) + t_{object_detection} \quad (6.6)$$

Communication Delay

The communication delay consists of several elements. For this work, we focus on three major categories: (i) the buffering and distribution, which are the most influential cycle times; (ii) the packing and unpacking, which represents the needed data conversion times; and (iii) the transmission of data as a whole, which can be defined using QoS parameters.

Communication: Buffering and Distribution By specification [48], the CPM frequency has to be between 1-10Hz. Sending CPMs immediately, i.e, as soon as data is available, would be better for the delay. However, related literature [73,45,74] shows that this will pollute the channel. The ETSI CPM standard suggests 10Hz sending for new objects and objects with a high dynamic, while 1 Hz is enough for static objects or objects with a straightforward prediction. In this work, we look at the fastest scenario with 10Hz. We expect, for example, an object to appear or to change its direction in a critical, unexpected way. This then results in a maximum time of 100 ms. The minimum cycle time is more complex: if the local fusion frequency is 10 Hz, the buffering could be coupled with the local fusion output, typically also 10 Hz. In that case, the buffering delay is only the time necessary for analyzing the object data. If one uses a simple comparison algorithm, this can be done in less than 1 ms. Including the Data Distribution Service (DDS) transport time of less than 1 ms, the overall buffering time is between 2 and 100 ms.

Before distribution, the CPMs must be buffered on the receiver side. As discussed above, typical sensor distribution frequencies are 10 Hz; hence, 10 Hz distribution frequency is also reasonable for V2X data. The best case is that we receive the data and can immediately distribute the data, which would again result in less than 1 ms processing time. For a systemic approach, we also include some internal transport time. In the case of ROS2, the internal transport time of DDS is less than 1 ms for a single transmission, provided by Kronauer et al. [116]. All in all, the distribution time is then 2 and 100 ms, depending on the implemented fusion strategy of the receiver, as discussed below.

Communication: Packing and Unpacking There is a delay in packing and unpacking objects. As V2X is a low-latency transmission technology, it is essential to consider delays, such as packing and unpacking, in the systematic approach. For our implementation, we expect that ROS2 objects are packed into transmittable ASN.1 bitstreams and vice-versa. This is again the internal transport time of DDS with less than 1ms [116] for a single transmission. The packing and unpacking of ASN.1 streams to C arrays and their conversion from and to ROS2 messages are estimated to take less than 1 ms. This results in 2 ms packing and unpacking time, respectively.

Communication: Transmission Delay Much research has already been done (i) for analyzing V2X to confirm the low latency transmission times [43,117,118] in perfect side-by-side scenarios, (ii) for analyzing V2X congestion control mechanisms [119,120] in heavy traffic scenarios, (iii) for providing simulation results for packet-loss [121,122,123], and (iv) for providing field measurements for connectivity [109,110]. However, the QoS of wireless

technologies, such as V2X, is complex. The following paragraphs aim to provide a basic estimate.

The physical layer transmission times of all four existing V2X standards have a comparable delay. Anwar et al. [43] specify the 802.11p physical layer transmission time from its standard as 0.344 ms for 100 bytes and 4.08 ms for 1500 bytes. Transmission delays of 802.11bd, C-V2X(LTE), and C-V2X(5G) are in a similar range with 0.336/3.98, 1/11, 0.75/8 all in ms for 100/1500 bytes. However, other communication layers add a delay. Campolo et al. [117] point out that a DENM requires around 3 ms E2E in an analysis of C-V2X(LTE) as the lower boundary.

To get an upper estimate for low channel load scenarios, Correia et al. [31] tested CPM sending with 10 – 75 vehicles as CPM payload and found message delays between 0 – 45 ms. The 0 ms is likely due to internal processing and time synchronization only via NTP. Considering measurement errors of up to 5 ms through NTP, an upper boundary of 50 ms seems fitting. For ITS-G5, it has to be stressed that the expected transmission delay of 3 – 50 ms for one message is only a frame for the minimum and the maximum expected transmission time in low channel load scenarios.

When at least one other transmitting ITS-S occupies the V2X channels, there are busy times and collisions in transmissions. The channel load influences the transmission delay, caused by necessary QoS functionality defined in the Medium Access Control (MAC) layer and its extensions [124]. The complexity and scalability of V2X transmission, focusing on ITS-G5, is outlined in Section 6.2.10. Here, we aim for a rough estimate. Shahen Shah et al. [125] show the relation between delay caused by the MAC layer and the number of vehicles, respectively, and their differential speed. Simulation results show a near-linear behavior for the delay of non-safety data. Depending on several parameters, the average packet delay is 100 ms for 25 vehicles. A similar delay is caused by a 35 km/h differential speed.

Zheng et al. [126] show results depending on the Enhanced Distributed Channel Access (EDCA) queue. Depending on the messages, their priority, their payload, their distribution frequency, and the overall number of ITS-Ss, a single message may suffer from delays much larger than 100 ms. This means that the delay of the CPM in loaded channels can not be specified in a trivial form. In the worst case, the message might never arrive. Either due to the MAC delay or packet loss caused by obstructions or out-of-range communication. Details are discussed in Section 6.2.10.

The transmission delay can be expected to be around 5 to 50 ms in low channel load scenarios. For medium load with 25 to 100 vehicles, one can take the simulation results of Shahen Shah et al. [125] with 100 to 500 ms. With a high channel load, the delay is unbounded without guaranteed delivery, hence one can expect 500 up to ∞ ms. One may argue about the definite delays for the channel load and differential speed combination. But for a rough estimate, the given frames should be fitting.

Σ Communication Delay The final communication delay is the sum of all five mentioned communication delay subcomponents, as shown in Equation 6.7. The final communication delay can be calculated between 11 and 254 ms for low channel load, as shown in Table 6.6. For medium and high channel loads, one can expect at least 100 ms of additional delay, depending

on the circumstances of transmission.

$$t_{comm} = t_{buffer} + t_{pack} + t_{transmit} + t_{unpack} + t_{distribute} \quad (6.7)$$

Fusion

Delays for data fusion can be separated into delays for data fusion and matching & tracking for the fusion of high-level object data, as shown in Equation 6.8. Data fusion fuses the object data from the object detection step in a multi-sensor setup with high-level object data. Matching is then needed to find the corresponding objects. Finally, the tracking step produces tracks of the matched objects.

$$t_{fusion_components} = t_{data_fusion} + t_{matching_tracking} \quad (6.8)$$

Fusion: Data Fusion, Matching and Tracking For a detailed analysis, it makes sense to analyze the fusion components as stated in Equation 6.8. However, SOTA systems, such as Autoware [13], provide an all-in-one solution for matching, tracking, and object data fusion using list and matrix operations, as well as Kalman filters. Hence, one has to compare the overall inference time of such solutions, as suggested by Jahromi et al. [127]. The authors analyzed SOTA algorithms for the complete detection and object data fusion pipeline and found inference times of 92 – 185 ms. The elements matching, tracking, and fusion are only parts of this time. As Jahromi et al. [127] provide the times for detection and fusion, we could subtract the time for object detection, see above Wen et al. [115], from that. However, this only gives a rough idea of around 30 ms of overhead when subtracting the minima and maxima without discussing different hardware and algorithm setups. A better estimate is to look at how matching, tracking, and object data fusion are processed. Matching and tracking are the nearest neighbor searches, which can be done in around 1 ms for a few objects, according to Gallego et al. [128], while object data fusion is a simple merging of lists, which is even faster. Hence, we will estimate a rough fusion time of 2 – 30 ms.

Fusion: local, global and async delay Next, as shown in Figure 6.3, two sections cause data fusion times. The first one is the local fusion for the sender. The second one is the global fusion of the receiver. Two main approaches can integrate CP data: fusing everything simultaneously, meaning fusing the local and global CP data directly every time. However, as elaborated by Pilz et al. [2], data freshness, cleanliness, and security issues will arise. Without external moderation, local data should be the reference. Otherwise, global data may corrupt the CP. Hence, the second approach is that the receiver does local fusion first and then global fusion. From the perspective of delay, it is best to use the most recent local fusion to integrate the global fusion, as is shown in Figure 6.6. This way, perception information is already here.

In conclusion, the fusion time consists of the local fusion time of the sender, the asynchronous delay of the global fusion cycle, and the global fusion time of the receiver, as shown in Equation 6.9 and Figure 6.6.

However, the global fusion itself has a catch. Figure 6.6 shows that the event starts the timeline. This means the currently active local perception of the Ego vehicle may be already more recent than the CP data received from the other vehicle. In this case, the global fusion has to consider the timing offset of the CP data to the newer local perception data. Generally, one can implement two strategies: alter the CP data and, for example, predict it into the future or alter the new local perception to fit the old CP data. The more accurate way is to do the latter; hence, we also estimate that global fusion will do one fusion step with older data and then add the new local perception if it is already available. In summary, there will be one global fusion step if the local perception fits but two fusion steps if the local perception is new.

$$t_{fusion} = t_{local_sender} + t_{async} + t_{global_receiver} \quad (6.9)$$

Σ Fusion Delay The delay results of Equation 6.9 will be most accurate when calculating local and global delays separately. A separate calculation is essential when two ITS-Ss highly differ in performance or deal with many objects. However, from the perspective of objects, related research, such as Correira et al., [31], estimate below 75 objects per intersection. This amount of objects is not yet computationally expensive, as shown by Gallego et al. [128]. Hence, we can simplify the calculations for scenarios with few objects as shown in Equation 6.10. This equation calculates the final fusion time of 4 – 6 ms as seen in Table 6.1.

$$t_{fusion} = 2 * t_{fusion_components} + (t_{fusion_components}) \quad (6.10)$$

6.2.5 Additions to the Evaluation Setup

The measurement setup consists of two street-legal ADDs of the Virtual Vehicle Research GmbH³, as presented in Chapter 3. The following sections will provide additional details relevant to the V2XaaS perception accuracy test setup.

Details Automated Driving Software Stack

For this work, only the perception part is relevant. Figure 6.7 adds the camera input to the setup presented in Chapter 3. Each colored box represents a separate ROS node. The sensor data nodes are drivers acquiring sensor data and providing the raw data to the ROS environment. The preprocessing reformats the data to be used by the Autoware object detection implementations. The lidar object detection uses a CNN, which outputs 3D clusters representing detected objects. The camera object detection uses YOLO3 to output labeled two-dimensional (2D) objects. The local fusion then does cluster association to fuse the 3D and 2D objects. The associated objects are then shape-fitted to the detected object class, resulting in bounding boxes. Afterward, the multi-object tracker matches the detected objects with previous detections using a Kalman-Filter-based approach and generates a track for each object. The planner will then predict future tracks and act accordingly. At the same time, the V2X gateway will process the data to be sent to another ITS-S.

³<https://www.v2c2.at/automated-driving/>

On the receiving end, the V2X gateway receives the object data. The receiving vehicle also ran the same processing as the sending vehicle. Hence, a local fusion is available. The CP fusion first does the time association of the incoming CP data. The time association checks the timestamp of the incoming message to associate it with the correct local fusion, which can either be the most recent fusion or the previous one. The previous one is used if the local sensor data is newer than the CP data and has already been fused. In this case, the time association first manages the fusion of the CP with the local fusion and then adds the most recent sensor data. The CP tracking finally does the same as the local tracking. It matches the objects with the already known objects and produces the track. The planner now receives tracks for local and CP objects. The separation allows decisions to be based on the source of information.

Figure 6.7: Perception part of the AD software stack, as shown in Pilz et al. [5]. The diagram shows the flow of information from sensor information to the planner and where the V2X communication is connected. The software is based on the architecture proposal of Autoware [13].

Details: Communication Platform

For this work, the vehicleCAPTAIN hardware, discussed in Chapter 3 and 4, is equipped with one Unex SOM-301E to guarantee the low latency of V2X. The Unex SOM-301E ships with V2XCast⁴. V2XCast handles the V2X stack during transmission and sending. The vehicleCAPTAIN is mainly an abstraction to exchange the underlying sending hardware and software without changing the implementation of the V2X communication interface in the ADDs and other demonstrators.

The vehicleCAPTAIN hardware distinguishes this work from similar approaches of delay measurements by synchronizing the hardware clocks with 1PPS. The hardware, listed in Table 6.2, allows the synchronization of sender and receiver to be good enough for the low latencies of V2X. Combined with Qosium, a QoS analyzer software, we can do a comprehensive and highly time-accurate analysis of V2X QoS in field-operational situations.

⁴<https://unex.com.tw/v2xcast/>

Table 6.2: Hardware setup – vehicleCAPTAIN, as shown in Pilz et al. [5].

Component	Type
Base Board	Raspberry Pi 4 8GB
V2X Module	Unex SOM301-E
GNSS Module	ublox ZED-F9P

Details: Delay Results

The minimum delay of V2X communications, especially the physical and MAC layers, can be calculated from specifications, as elaborated in Section 6.2.4. Other QoS parameters, such as packet loss, have been discussed and simulated in [117,129,130,118]. However, practice and theory come with a gap, especially in wireless communications. One is that simulation models need approximations and assumptions for many factors affecting wireless communications. There are no publicly available studies for highly accurate and comprehensive QoS measurements for V2X, which are essential when talking about performance and especially safety. For CP transmission in general and specialized CP use cases in specific, especially virtual towing [131], it is essential to have a constant flow of messages and a low delay for critical messages. With Qosium⁵, we can empirically measure an extensive amount of QoS statistics to extend the basis for discussing such parameters.

6.2.6 Measurement Setups

The work presented in this chapter targets the analysis of transmission delays using three general scenarios: (i) a set of laboratory tests with artificial channel load to show performance limits, (ii) a set of driving scenarios in unloaded channel environments to provide a baseline in the field, and (iii) a set of driving scenarios in high channel load environments.

Lab Tests

The laboratory tests are designed to provide a reference point in a controlled environment. The QoS tests are conducted in a single room in the laboratory to mitigate influences from the environment and the network of the AVs. The basic setup is shown in 6.8. A minimum of 1 m distance separates the sender, receiver, and adversary senders, while the adversary senders are centered in between. The adversary senders are ITS-Ss that deliberately fill the channel with valid messages. Listed in the following are the test scenarios in the laboratory:

- L1** Basic QoS: sender and receiver are active. The QoS is measured for the transmission. This provides the ground level of QoS that can be expected.

⁵<https://www.kaitotek.com>

- L2** Single ITS-S load: as Basic QoS, but an adversary sender loads the channel with small messages from 0 – 1300 Hz, the maximum channel capacity, and also the maximum frequency that can be produced by the Y-Ghost system, in 10 Hz increments. This provides insight into the QoS reduction that a single adversary sender can cause.
- L3** Multiple ITS-S load: as Basic QoS, but multiple adversary ITS-Ss send messages, each with 600 Hz, the maximum frequency that can be produced by a single used Unex module. Specifically, up to seven ITS-Ss are used iteratively, and each generates 600 Hz of V2X messages. This provides insight into the QoS of a low-loaded channel.

Figure 6.8: Laboratory setup of the V2X QoS tests channel load tests, as shown in Pilz et al. [10]. Two vehicleCAPTAINs (sender/receiver) exchange messages. Six vehicleCAPTAINs or the Y-Ghost system (adversaries) send messages to fill the channel depending on the scenario.

Field Tests

The field tests are set up around the Graz University of Technology campus, as shown in Figure 6.9. The sender and receiver are street-legal ADDs of the Virtual Vehicle Research GmbH. We chose four scenarios for driving-related tests and four for QoS-related tests. In all QoS scenarios, one vehicle sends, and the other receives. A third vehicle is centered between and carries the other ITS-Ss as adversary sender sources, as shown in Figure 6.10.

Driving-related scenario setups Field Driving (FD)x:

FD1 Standstill: ADDs are at a standstill to get reference data.

FD2 City Scenario: ADDs are driving around a TU Graz building block spanning around 100×250 m, with distances of 50 m, 150 m, and 250 m, allowing for good combinations of free line of sight, one corner, and two corners between the vehicles.

Figure 6.9: V2X measurement route (red) at the Graz University of Technology Inffeldcampus, exported from OpenStreetMaps [132].

FD3 Urban Area Scenario: from the Inffeld Campus to the highway, allowing for a good set of typically city/urban driving data.

FD4 Highway Scenario: the leading vehicle starts on the ramp, and the follower starts after the first one reaches the 2 km mark, with a differential speed of 40 km/h. This provides insight into the maximum range and differential speed.

Load-related scenario setups Field Load (FL)x:

FL1 Single ITS-S load: the ADDs are standing apart with distances of 10, 50, 100, 150, 250 meters. According to the standard, one ADD sends CAMs and CPMs, each with a frequency of 1 – 10 Hz. In between, a third vehicle with an ITS-S fills the V2X channel with CAMs from 0 – 1300 Hz, close to the maximum channel capacity, in 10 Hz intervals. This shows how much influence a single ITS-S can have on the channel.

FL2 Multiple ITS-S load: as single ITS-S load, but in between, there is a vehicle with six ITS-Ss, each filling the V2X channel with CAMs with a frequency of 600 Hz, the maximum frequency of a single used Unex module. This provides insight into the QoS of a channel fully loaded from a low number of ITS-Ss.

FL3 Follower Scenario: is based on all previous scenarios concerning adversarial senders. All three vehicles drive with a typical city distance of around a 150×250 m building block. The adversary in-between runs the single ITS-S test for 0, 500, 1000, 1300 Hz. The multiple ITS-S test is run with 2, 3, 4 ITS-Ss. This provides insight into city scenarios with a loaded V2X channel.

FL4 One Corner Scenario: as single/multiple ITS-S load, the second vehicle is standing across the corner, outside the FoV of the first vehicle. This demonstrates a city corner scenario.

Figure 6.10: Field setup of the V2X QoS tests, as shown in Pilz et al. [10]. Two vehicleCAPTAINs (sender/receiver) exchange messages. Six vehicleCAPTAINs or the Y-Ghost system (adversaries) send messages to fill the channel depending on the scenario.

6.2.7 Application Scenarios

The work presented here aims to quantify delay parameters to discuss how CP can contribute to VRU safety and passenger comfort from a timing perspective. We are, therefore, looking at three scenarios to visualize the need for the discussion on delay. Here, we assume high sensor accuracy and positional awareness of the automated vehicles to focus on the information delay.

We compare the time available for decision-making of the ego vehicle in two scenarios: (i) with CP data made available via V2X and fused with the onboard perception, and (ii) with data available via onboard perception only. The questions are: (i) How can CP generate a benefit for safety and comfort? (ii) how much time benefit can CP generate compared to onboard perception?

The City Side-by-Side Scenario

The city side-by-side scenario is shown in Figure 6.11 and describes our ego vehicle, shown in red, driving straight ahead. On the side of the road, there are parked vehicles. One of the parked vehicles is a bigger vehicle, such as a bus, that blocks the view of a VRU stepping onto the road. Without V2X, our ego vehicle can only detect the VRU when stepping on the drive path and into the sensor view. With V2X, an aware ITS-S could send out a CPM to tell our ego vehicle about the VRU. The aware ITS-S could be a standstill vehicle, another active vehicle shown in blue, or an RSU.

Figure 6.11: City side-by-side scenario, as shown in Pilz et al. [5]. VRU (red circle) walking out between vehicles. Ego vehicle (red) can not see VRU. Other ITS-S, such as standstill vehicles (gray), other active vehicles (blue), or RSUs (not in the picture), can warn about the pedestrian.

The Highway Scenario

The Highway Scenario is shown in Figure 6.12 and describes our ego vehicle, shown in red, driving on a highway around a corner. Around the corner is a broken-down vehicle, shown in gray, and a VRU standing on the road. Without V2X, the ego vehicle has to get far enough around the corner to detect the VRU with its sensors. With V2X, another ITS-S can tell the ego vehicle about the VRU. Other ITS-Ss could be the standstill vehicle, the other active vehicle shown in blue, or an RSU.

Figure 6.12: Highway scenario, as shown in Pilz et al. [5]. VRU (red circle) behind standstill vehicle (gray). Ego vehicle (red) can not see standstill vehicle. Other ITS-S are aware of VRU and can send warnings via CP. Other ITS-S could be other active vehicles (blue), standstill vehicles (gray), or RSUs (not in the picture).

The City Intersection Scenario

The city intersection scenario is shown in Figure 6.13 and describes an ego vehicle, shown in red, that takes a right turn at the intersection after stopping at the stop sign. At the same time, a VRU may cross the road. Two things can happen here: one possibility is that another ITS-S sends out free space via CP. The ego vehicle ignores the stop sign, improving performance. The second possibility is that another ITS-S sends out a message about the VRU crossing the road, and the ego vehicle slows down in advance to increase comfort.

Figure 6.13: City intersection scenario, as shown in Pilz et al. [5]. VRU (red circle) crossing street behind the corner. The ego vehicle (red) will be turning right at the intersection. Other active vehicles (blue) can warn about the situation.

6.2.8 Data Recording

This section overviews the QoS data recorded with Qosium and highlights core findings. The QoS statistics are provided using averaging periods ($T = 1000ms$). Specifically, samples for QoS statistics, such as delay, are averaged over a specific period T to provide discrete statistics into varying QoS parameters, such as packet loss. The provided QoS statistics include (i) the E2E delay of transmitted V2X packets, (ii) the standard deviation as jitter, (iii) the average lost packets as Packet Loss Ratio (PLR), and (iv) the average time without successfully delivered packets as connection break duration.

Lab Tests

The laboratory tests provide insight into the channel capacity and, in turn, message throughput performance, provided by the mechanisms Carrier Sense Multiple Access with Collision Avoidance (CSMA/CA), EDCA, and Decentralized Congestion Control (DCC) [133]. The following paragraphs will discuss the basic QoS of V2X between two ITS-Ss, the channel behavior with a single adversary ITS-S, and the channel behavior with multiple adversary ITS-Ss.

L1: Basic QoS Here, we aim at a robust baseline for the minimum delay of a V2X message. The data is extracted from a one-hour recording, with the V2X QoS measurement setup as

defined in Section 6.2.5. One can see from the data shown in Figure 6.14 that the delay is, on average, 4.99 ms, with distributed delay spikes of up to 19.46 ms, causing a jitter of 0.62 ms. We also measured the connection break duration and packet loss. For one lost packet, the connection break duration is 100 ms, i.e., one 10 Hz cycle. This is more visible in the other tests. Finally, after one hour, there was only one lost packet.

Figure 6.14: L1: Qosium QoS data averaged over 1000 ms for sending 10 Hz CAMs over one hour, as shown in Pilz et al. [10].

L2: Single ITS-S load The V2X channel capacity for ITS-G5 can be calculated from specifications via characteristics, such as timeslots, coding rate, and message size. For a V2X message around 40 to 50 bytes, the total channel is fully loaded with around 1400 messages. To show the effects of a loaded channel, we configured the Y-Ghost system to send with a maximum frequency of 1300 Hz in 10 Hz increments, as discussed in Chapters 6.2.3 and 6.2.5.

The overall time from 0 – 1300 Hz with 60 s for each 10 Hz iteration is *2h10min*. Hence, one can see the QoS in great detail, as shown in Figure 6.15.

One has to remember at this point that the Y-Ghost system is designed for basic sending, as discussed in Section 6.2.5. The CSMA/CA and EDCA mechanisms are kept simple and are designed for rapid sending. Hence, transmission from the vehicleCAPTAIN, with the fully activated CSMA/CA, EDCA, and DCC stack, struggles with lost packets. However, the packet loss is minimal, with an average of one lost packet in the 1000 ms averaging intervals.

One can see that the packet loss is starting after around 10% of the runtime. This is when the DCC mechanism starts to dictate channel behavior. However, the Y-Ghost system is designed to ignore the DCC mechanism. The Unex module must adapt to the adversary, hence the packet loss. At around 50% of the runtime, the Jitter starts to rise. This is the point where the channel gets slightly loaded. Soon later, the average delay also begins to rise.

One can see that the vehicleCAPTAIN can still find gaps to transmit because the payload and frequency are only 41 bytes and 10 Hz, respectively.

L3: Multiple ITS-S load The vehicleCAPTAIN utilizes the Unex SOM301-E modules for ITS-G5 communication, as stated in Section 6.2.5. These modules are standard-compliant.

Figure 6.15: L2: Qosium QoS data averaged over 1000 ms for sending 0 – 1300 Hz worth of CAMs, in 10 Hz iterations, increasing every 60 s, as shown in Pilz et al. [10].

Hence, one can evaluate the performance of the DCC algorithm with multiple senders. In general, the DCC mechanism [133] requires a local minimum $t_{off} = 25 \text{ ms}$, which is 40 Hz of maximum sending frequency. The total channel capacity is also limited to 160 Hz for messages without high-priority safety. This behavior is shown by the first test in Figure 6.16. Here, 0 – 7 vehicleCAPTAINs send as many messages as possible, and another vehicleCAPTAIN is receiving. One can see that each added sender adds close to 40 Hz more messages until the 160 Hz of similar messages is reached. It is essential to notice that the throughput will not increase as the DCC mechanism caps it. Hence, the sending vehicleCAPTAINs will suffer from substantially high channel occupancy, delaying transmission. The messages will not be lost, but the transmitting station waits for a silent channel for the back-off period counter and transmits the message.

The second test was done with a deactivated DCC mechanism, as shown on the right in Figure 6.16. Starting again with one vehicleCAPTAIN, one can see that the Unex SOM301-E tops out at a frequency of around 570 Hz. One can also see the linear rise in maximum frequency when more vehicleCAPTAINs are added as senders. This maximum tops out at around 1300 – 1400 Hz, similar to the previous Single ITS-S test. The maximum frequency is not as stable as with the Y-Ghost system because more senders are involved, and the CSMA/CA and EDCA mechanisms regulate the channel. The channel regulation leads to the receiver's average throughput of 900 – 1000 Hz. The average and median seem to climb slowly with more senders, which is expected, as the random-based channel management allows better throughput for the receiver. However, we can not confirm this within the lab, as we would require more sender hardware.

The critical fact is that while the receiver may have a constant flow of information, the messages are significantly delayed due to restricted channel access. The maximum throughput of the channel is reached, but the messages are stuck at the sender. However, this is only true for the involved adversary senders. If another ITS-S is added, the channel will still not be full due to CSMA/CA and EDCA. Proof can be given by the QoS measurements shown in Figure 6.17. Like the basic QoS test, one vehicleCAPTAIN sent CAMs with 10 Hz. Via a

Figure 6.16: L3: DCC visualized. The x-axis shows the number of sending vehicleCAPTAINS. The y-axis shows the throughput as the frequency of messages received by another vehicleCAPTAIN. The left graph shows the throughput with DCC=on. The right graph shows the frequency throughput with DCC=off. The V2X interface (Unex SOM301-E) configuration manages the DCC state. As shown in Pilz et al. [10].

script, every 60 s, another vehicleCAPTAIN was started, trying to transmit 600 Hz worth of CAMs. The data in Figure 6.17 show that this is not noticeable for the two communicating vehicleCAPTAINS. However, this behavior can only be guaranteed with working CSMA/CA and EDCA mechanisms and the low amount of involved ITS-Ss.

Figure 6.17: L3: Qosium QoS data averaged over 1000 ms for 10 Hz CAMs, with 0-7 ITS-S adversaries added in 60 s intervals to the channel, as shown in Pilz et al. [10].

Literature dealing with simulations, such as Shahan et al. [125], suggest that 10 – 20 ITS-Ss will start to create a noticeable delay. One hundred ITS-Ss will create around half a second delay due to limited channel access. Confirming those numbers with more ITS-Ss would be interesting. However, our data shows that it seems plausible if one takes the possible throughput of 900 – 1000 Hz.

Field Tests FD1-FD4

The data provided by Qosium allow for deep analysis of empirical QoS for the V2X application and system. The primary data for the FD setups is split into two sections, discussing delay and connectivity.

Delay Data The delay data is shown in Table 6.3. Right away, one can see three scenarios with high packet loss. The FD2 Campus scenarios with 150 m and 250 m have obstructions, such as trees and buildings, which lead to lost packets. The FD4 highway scenario has out-of-range distances, which also hinders the reception of packets. The delay data is within the expected range, as shown in Figure 6.18. One highlight is that jitter, delay standard deviation, and maximum delay statistics values are about double higher in the FD3 city follower scenario than in the other scenarios. This is caused by differential speed, i.e., collisions caused by the Doppler effect. But also by noise on the wireless channel, from reflections and other wireless systems on channels with proximity. Both factors produced lag spikes, as shown in Figure 6.19.

Table 6.3: Qosium Delay data, for one sending ITS-S, as shown in Pilz et al. [5]. Averaging interval (T) = 1000 ms. Packet E2E delay (τ), for one sending ITS-S.

Type (Distance)	$\sum T$	packetloss $\sqrt{}$ [%]	$\tau_{min,\sqrt{}}$ [ms]	$\tau_{max,\sqrt{}}$ [ms]	$\bar{\tau}_T$ [ms]	$\tilde{\tau}_T$ [ms]	$\hat{\sigma}_{\tau_T}^2$ [ms]	\overline{jitter}_T [ms]
FD1: Campus Standstill (10m)	173	0.12	3.735	13.611	4.477	4.304	0.473	1.656
FD2: Campus Round (50m)	259	13.69	3.731	16.612	4.547	4.311	0.582	1.619
FD2: Campus Round (150m)	266	55.74	3.823	67.258	4.619	4.391	0.703	2.118
FD2: Campus Round (250m)	278	57.78	3.792	59.842	4.641	4.378	0.765	2.444
FD3: City Follower (50 – 100m)	877	3.71	3.694	141.655	4.791	4.285	1.684	4.711
FD4: highway Overtaking (max. 3000m)	800	79.94	3.649	14.649	4.494	4.280	0.547	1.604

Connectivity data The connectivity data is shown in Table 6.4. These data include the PLB lengths and their durations in time. A PLB spans from one lost packet until another is successfully received.

With the standstill vehicles, we measured only one of the 1719 packets lost during FD1. However, we observe long PLBs when considering vehicle mobility. The FD2 Campus Round scenario with a 50 m distance and the FD3 city follower example give important data for close city distances. The data shows a 3 to 14% PLR, accompanied by 29 to 86 ms average connection loss, at worst 0.8 to 1.2 s. Even more, it is essential to note that obstructions impact packet loss substantially, as shown by the 150 and 250 m FD3 city scenarios. In such scenarios, packet loss causes longer delays for the information itself. Also, the potential for lost messages gets more concrete with longer distances, as seen in the FD4 highway scenario, where the overtaking scenario leads to a high packet loss and long PLBs when going out of range.

Figure 6.18: V2X QoS data for the FD2 Campus Round 50m scenario, with one sending ITS-S, as shown in Pilz et al. [5]. The overall E2E transmission delay is between 4 – 8 ms. Most data is between 4 – 6 ms, confirmed by the jitter, which is between 0 – 2.5 ms. Both diagrams show a strong baseline, confirmed by the standard deviation of 0.58 from the averaging data shown in Table 6.3.

Figure 6.19: V2X QoS data for the FD3 City Follower Scenario, with one sending ITS-S, as shown in Pilz et al. [5]. The E2E transmission delay is between 4 – 23 ms in the averaging intervals. Most delays are between 4 – 10 ms, confirmed by the jitter of 0 – 37 ms, with most data between 0 – 5 ms.

Table 6.4: Qosium connectivity data, for one sending ITS-S, as shown in Pilz et al. [5]. PLB Length (ℓ). PLB Time (t).

Type (Distance)	$\sum \text{packets}$	$\sum \text{PLB}$	ℓ_{\max}	$\bar{\ell}$	$\hat{\sigma}_{\ell}^2$	$t_{\text{PLB},\max}[\text{s}]$	$\bar{t}_{\text{PLB}}[\text{ms}]$	$\hat{\sigma}_{t_{\text{PLB}}}^2[\text{ms}]$
FD1: Campus Standstill (10m)	1719	1	1	1	0	0.1	101	0
FD2: Campus Round (50m)	2574	175	12	1.88	1.88	1.2	86	160
FD2: Campus Round (150m)	2644	179	547	10.77	57.07	55.0	411	3539
FD2: Campus Round (250m)	2763	106	370	13.01	58.18	37.2	318	2908
FD3: City Follower (50 – 100m)	8719	140	8	1.76	1.30	0.8	29	85
FD4: highway Overtaking (max. 3000m)	7954	65	2420	67.87	391.95	243.4	554	11226

Field Tests with Artificial Channel Load

All test setups are designed to cover edge cases of the QoS in more fine-grained detail compared to previous approaches [5]. The focus is to extend the laboratory tests to edge cases involving distance and blocked lines of sight, as discussed in Section 6.2.3. Another difference is that for the field tests, live data is used for CAMs and CPMs, with standard conform generation frequencies, as discussed in Section 6.2.5.

FL1: Standstill Single ITS-S load The reference QoS measurements were taken at distances between sender and receiver of 50 m, 100 m, 150 m, and 250 m. The Y-Ghost loaded the channel with CAMs from 0 – 1300 Hz in 10 Hz increments every 10s. The antennas are mounted on the roof of the ADDs and are not blocked by any other equipment in their line of sight. However, vehicles and people passed the line of sight within the 22 min duration, causing delay and packet loss spikes.

The diagrams in Figure 6.20 show data of the 100 m distance setup. The PLR is 6.3%, with an average delay of 15.2 ms and a standard deviation of 8.3 ms. One can also see that the effect of the channel loading is not as drastically visible as within the lab environment. However, the raw sending mode of the Y-Ghost system drastically causes a higher average delay and more packet loss, especially with delivery trucks moving in and out of the line of sight, which also causes more dynamic wireless reflections overall. It is also noteworthy that the delay goes down in the first 5% due to the moderation of the channel by the adversary as an active sender.

The data for the distances of 0 m and 50 m were better than the 100 m scenario and were closer to the data from the laboratory tests. Conversely, when the distance is increased to 150 m and 250 m, the channel is increasingly disrupted by the raw sending mode of the Y-Ghost system. The increased number of messages decreases the channel quality, decreasing the maximum transmission distance compared to previous research [5]. Specifically, while a distance of 150 m is only slightly worse with 23.7% PLR, 250 m already shows 82.6% PLR.

FL2: Standstill Multiple ITS-S load The major difference to the laboratory test is the configuration of the payload. In this scenario, we use standard compliant generation of CAMs and CPMs. Specifically, CAMs are generated with 1 Hz during standstill, and CPMs are generated with 1 – 10 Hz depending on the movement of vehicles and pedestrians. The campus road was busy, so the average CPM sending rate was 6 – 8 Hz. However, CPMs are much bigger than CAMs. While the CAM in our vehicle has a payload of 64 bytes, the CPM has around 350 bytes. This is also visible in the tests. The 41 byte CAMs in the laboratory setting could be easily transmitted. With nearly ten times larger messages, the CPMs in the field scenario suffers from increased transmission delays.

In our field test, the two vehicleCAPTAINs in the ADDs were configured to use a standard compliant transmission with DCC=on, as within the lab. Six additional vehicleCAPTAINs were configured with DCC=off to support the maximum amount of sending frequency. A script was timed to start those, ramping from 0 – 6 adversary senders, with a step every two minutes. The result is an artificially loaded channel. While only having six ITS-Ss, the message load starves the transmission between the communicating ADDs, as shown in Figure 6.21. The

Figure 6.20: Qosium QoS field data averaged over 1000 ms for 0-1300 Hz adversary CAMs from the Y-Ghost system with 10 Hz iterations every 10 s. Distance 100 m. As shown in Pilz et al. [10].

delay and packet loss are low for 0 – 1 adversary senders. The delay jumps to around 50 ms, beginning with the second adversary sender, as the channel is full, as discussed in Section 6.2.8. Increasing the number of adversary senders increases the delay and the PLR.

Figure 6.21: Qosium QoS field data averaged over 1000 ms for the full CA/CP stack with 0 m distance and 0-6 ITS-S adversaries added to the channel in 120 s intervals, as shown in Pilz et al. [10].

We repeated these tests with increased distances, which showed data similar to those of the single ITS-S adversary. Specifically, the channel is loaded, which causes the maximum transmission distance to decrease rapidly.

FL3: Follower Scenario The movement of vehicles with added adversary senders did not create any different result than adding adversary senders at a standstill or changing the distance. The distance between vehicles was less than 100 m for all three vehicles in the follower scenario, which is a typical city scenario of three vehicles. The result is a straightforward overlap of varying distances and interference, as shown in previous research [5].

FL4: One Corner Scenario For the one-corner scenario, the explanation is the same as for the follower scenario. The corner is a simple obstruction of the line of sight for wireless communication. This obstruction decreases the QoS, similar to increased transmission distances.

6.2.9 CP Delay Chain Analysis

This work discussed the expected delay for CP from the literature perspective in Section 6.2.4 and provided the results in Table 6.1. This section extends this table to include a field perspective from the implementation analyzed above, in Table 6.5.

In Section 6.2.5, we mentioned that our ADD runs Autoware, simplified as shown in Figure 6.7. The runtime of the nodes, shown in Table 6.7, is the time difference between the availability of an input message and the availability of the corresponding output messages. The runtime was acquired by adding simple time stamp logging to the original code. Finally,

remember that also ROS2 communication is between the components with up to 1 ms delay for each communication step as discussed by Kronauer et al. [116]. Aside from these results, one must remember that some nodes' runtime depends on the number of detected objects.

Table 6.5: Components of delay with reference to Figure 6.6, as shown in Pilz et al. [5]. The delay components are derived in Section 6.2.4, with estimates from the literature. Measurements are provided by the results in Section 6.2.9.

Delay Component	Delay Description	Estimate from literature [ms]	Measured [ms]
Sensing Delay	sensing delay	206-280	207.7
- Sensor Data Delay	from event to sensor image	camera: 25 lidar: 50	camera: 24.1 lidar: 34.3
- Cycle Time	from sensor image to available data	camera: 25-100 lidar: 50-100	camera: 62.5 lidar: 100
- Object Detection	from sensor data to object data	56-130	camera: 69.0 lidar: 73.4
Communication Delay	from collecting to redistribution	11-254 + [100-∞]*	19.1/119.1/419.1 + [100-∞]**
- Buffering	fastest (ETSI): 10Hz	2-100	1
- Packing	ROS2 and packing	2	1.1
- Transmission Delay QoS	C-ITS load low C-ITS load medium**** C-ITS load high****	3-50 100-500* 500-∞*	5/105/405 exp. + [100-500]** exp. + [500-∞]**
- Unpacking	unpacking and ROS2	2	11
- Distribution	sensor like: 10Hz	2-100	1
Fusion Delay	local sender and global receiver	4-6	104.8
- Sender (Local) Fusion Delay	local multi-sensor fusion	2	2.4
- Asynchronous Fusion Delay	local multi-sensor fusion	0-2	100 (w.c.)
- Receiver (Global) Fusion Delay	global multi-sensor fusion	2	2.4
CP Delay Time	all in****	221-540 + [100-∞]*	331.6/431.6/731.6 + [100-∞]**

* Scalability (ITSG5): delay may be drastically increased by the Access Layer due to channel load. (Section 6.2.10).

** Scalability (ITSG5): be aware of the Access Layer delays. (Section 6.2.10).

Sensor Data Delay The sensor data delay is calculated as shown in Equation 6.4. The acquisition time can be taken from the datasheet, if available. For the Ouster OS1 Lidar [112], it is less than 10 ms. For the FLIR BFS-PGE-27S5C-C [113] camera, we have to estimate 23.3 ms for 43 FPS as upper data latency per frame as no concrete values are mentioned. To get a more accurate reading, one would have to set up a measurement setup where movement is created, and the output is measured on the other end. The second value for the data delay is the readout delay. The respective ROS2 nodes in our system need around 0.8 ms for camera data and around 24.3 ms for lidar data, as shown in Table 6.7. The resulting data delay is now 24.1 ms for camera data and 34.3 ms for lidar data.

Sensor Cycle Time The sensor drivers only read data when new data is available. Hence, the frequency of the respective ROS2 nodes gives the sensor cycle time, with $16 \text{ Hz} \Rightarrow 62.5 \text{ ms}$ for the camera and $10 \text{ Hz} \Rightarrow 100 \text{ ms}$ for lidar, as shown in Table 6.6.

Object Detection Delay The object detection delay consists of the pre-processing and object detection steps. Pre-processing is necessary to rectify the camera image and decrease

Table 6.6: ROS topic frequencies - separate test runs in Ford Fusion (*) and Ford Mondeo (+). The analysis shows ROS node frequency stability, as shown in Pilz et al. [5].

ROS Topic	f	Δf_{min}	Δf_{max}	$\hat{\sigma}_f^2$	samples
camera A (*)	15.95	0.02	0.38	0.02	2803
camera B (*)	15.94	0.03	0.39	0.03	2803
lidar (*)	10.0	0.07	0.25	0.01	2878
CPM-send (*)	10.1	0.09	0.13	0.03	2878
CPM-recv (+)	10.0	0.05	0.07	0.01	3512

Table 6.7: Delay test results for each CP component from the ADD Ford Fusion. Summary of three test rounds around the Inffeld Campus of the Graz University of Technology, as shown in Pilz et al. [5].

CP Component	Σ samples	$\tau_{min}[ms]$	$\tau_{max}[ms]$	$\bar{\tau}[ms]$	$\tilde{\tau}[ms]$	$\hat{\sigma}_\tau^2[ms]$
Data Latency						
- Camera A	9743	0.480	11.163	0.807	0.734	0.256
- Camera B	8543	0.303	4.167	0.555	0.481	0.217
- Lidar	9746	15.983	99.148	24.255	20.283	7.734
Object Detection						
- Camera	5696	3.241	72.250	69.018	69.261	3.179
- Lidar	5688	56.966	282.586	73.416	71.319	11.897
Fusion	5582	0.007	11.132	0.266	0.242	0.213
Tracking	5582	0.004	0.424	0.074	0.062	0.045
Packing	10006	0.000	0.250	0.103	0.117	0.038
Unpacking	10006	0.000	0.102	0.030	0.034	0.012

the point cloud's level of detail. In our case, the camera images are analyzed with the YOLO3 network, which results in 2D labeled object lists. For the lidar, we get unlabeled 3D bounding boxes from a CNN. Overall, the pre-processing and object detection takes around 69.0 ms for camera data and 73.4 ms for lidar data, as shown in Table 6.7. Finally, as discussed in Section 6.2.4, one should know that data of similar sensors are fused before the object detection and pre-processing step. For example, our ADD Ford Fusion can fuse the point clouds of four separate Ouster lidars. However, for simplicity, we only use one Ouster lidar for the tests conducted in this work. Hence, we get the final sensing delays as 159.8 ms for camera data and 207.7 ms for lidar data with Equation 6.6. We use the higher delay for Table 6.7 as both sensors are used, and the higher delay is the significant factor.

Data Fusion (Local) The local fusion is done at the object level when the camera and lidar object lists are ready. The fusion is done in image space. Therefore, 3D objects are first projected to the image space and compared with the object list of the YOLO3. The objects are then merged based on the intersection of the unions. In an additional step, 3D shape fitting is done based on the classification. This fusion takes around 0.3 ms to process object data from the camera and lidar in our system. However, it may be higher if many new objects are detected, as the maximum of 11.12 ms shows. As data fusion is a single processing node, the ROS2 DDS delay of < 1 ms [116] is added, resulting in 1.3 ms data fusion time.

Matching & Tracking (Local) Matching, also called data association, is done right before the tracking stage. The tracked objects from the previous round are matched with the new objects of the fusion step with a global nearest neighbor approach. Tracking is the final step in the local perception pipeline. The matched objects are now used to update the tracked objects from the previous round or, if no match was found, to initialize new objects for tracking. Matching and tracking take around 0.1 ms. Both are done in a single ROS2 node. Hence, one has to add once the ROS2 DDS delay of less than 1 ms [116], which results in 1.1 ms for the matching and tracking and 2.2 ms for the overall fusion.

Beyond the Perception Pipeline After the tracking, the local perception is complete. Next, our system will predict the object's movement from the existing track. The planner then uses the local perception and the predict-ahead, which then acts upon the data.

Buffering The local perception can be buffered with a sensor-like frequency of 10 Hz. In our implementation, this frequency is already provided as our local fusion output, which is stable 10 Hz, as shown in Table 6.7. In future implementations, we will add filters to prevent congestion, as suggested by ETSI specifications [48]. For now, there is only the ROS2 DDS delay that routes the data through an empty ROS2 node. Hence < 1 ms ROS2 DDS delay [116].

Packing The packing is done in our V2X gateway. As soon as the CPM node sends out the ROS2 CPM message, the V2X gateway converts the ROS2 message into an ETSI conform ASN.1 message and sends it to the vehicleCAPTAIN. This process takes around 0.103 ms for

a CAM. CAMs are used for reference, as CPMs are not yet fully standardized and can not easily be compared. Afterward, as discussed during QoS measurements, the vehicleCAPTAIN transmits the ASN.1 payload. For such small times, we add the ROS2 DDS delay with less than 1 ms [116], resulting in 1.103 ms.

Unpacking The unpacking is similar to packing. The V2X gateway polls the vehicleCAPTAIN with a maximum sleep time of 10 ms if messages are not received in between. The data is collected from the vehicleCAPTAIN and converted from the ASN.1 bitstream to a ROS2 CPM. The conversion takes around 0.030 ms for a CAM. CAMs are used for comparison, as stated above, for packing. Including the less than 1 ms ROS2 DDS delay [116], this is up to 11.030 ms of unpacking time.

Distribution The CPM node of the receiver distributes CPMs as sensor messages. In our implementation, we directly feed the incoming data into the global fusion pipeline, which results in a less than 1 ms ROS2 DDS delay [116]. In a future implementation, we aim to pre-process V2X data to decrease the computational load of multiple V2X messages on the global fusion.

Asynchronous Fusion Delay If one distributes V2X messages with a specific frequency, the global fusion could be run directly afterward. In our implementation, we directly relay V2X messages to ROS2 so that other systems can immediately use them. As one fusion step takes around 2.4 ms, the fusion could run at 100 Hz, adding 10 ms of worst-case delay. However, this high frequency will not be possible with multiple CPM sources, as discussed in Section 6.2.11. As the local perception pipeline runs with 10 Hz, we limit the global fusion to 10 Hz. This adds a worst-case delay of 100 ms if the fusion cycle is missed.

Fusion, Matching, Tracking (Global) Depending on the fusion strategy, global fusion components will differ from local fusion components. The problem is how to fuse multiple CP sources. In our measurement, with only one CP source, the fusion delay is the same as in the local fusion, i.e., 2.4 ms for two ROS2 nodes and their processing time. However, fusing each CP source as a separate sensor will lead to scaling problems. Five or ten CP sources will not be a problem, as the situation is similar to a multi-sensor setup in automated vehicles. However, especially when V2N sources are integrated, there has to be a fusion strategy, which increases the overall fusion time.

6.2.10 Theory of Transmission Delay with ITS-G5

This section goes into more technical detail on ITS-G5-based V2X communications to better understand where most communications delay comes from. As discussed in Chapters 6.2.4 and 6.2.9, loaded channels can result in high delays. Depending on several factors — such as the type of messages (priority) and transmission (unicast and broadcast), message size, signal strength, channel load and interference, antenna setups, signal propagation factors, and the

number of actively transmitting ITS-Ss — a message may experience increased delay, affecting the buffered messages sent next, or a failed transmission.

One major challenge with ITS-G5 is multiuser scenarios, which affect delays and reliability. Only one station can send at a time over a single channel while the others need to wait for their turn. The MAC layer in ITS-G5 is based on EDCA which, similarly to Distributed Coordination Function (DCF), gives every station the power to compete for radio resources [124]. EDCA brings additional capabilities over DCF to prioritize different types of traffic by introducing data traffic-specific queues and different listening periods called Arbitration Interframe Space (AIFS). The AIFS length depends on the access category; where AIFS is shorter, the higher the priority. This results in a situation where channel access for low-priority traffic can be substantially delayed; the lowest-priority traffic can even experience starvation with much high-priority traffic [134,126,135,136]. Traffic with short AIFS can proceed to direct transmission with a much higher probability than low-priority packets.

ITS-G5 employs CSMA/CA. The station goes to a backoff state if the channel is busy upon transmission attempt. The key to avoiding different transmitting stations sending simultaneously is the random duration of the backoff period, selected from the range $[0, CW]$. Thus, the Contention Window (CW), with defined CW_{min} and CW_{max} values for different access categories, plays an essential role in the backoff duration. The back-off counter is decremented only when the channel is idle. On busy channel moments, the stations in backoff listen to the AIFS period, specific to the access category, until the channel becomes free again to continue decreasing the backoff counter. Thus, the CW size and the AIFS duration impact the time to wait for transmission turns. Upon collision or otherwise unsuccessful transmission, the CW is increased until CW_{max} and retransmission limit is reached, potentially extending the next backoff period for the retransmission. This is to spread transmissions from multiple stations in time, but it potentially introduces additional delays, especially for background and best-effort traffic categories. The retransmission applies only to the unicast mode, while in broadcast, there is only one backoff period, after which the packet is sent, successfully or not, to ITS-S receivers in range. Broadcast traffic does not suffer from increased delays caused by retransmissions, but, on the other hand, there is no information on whether all stations benefitting from the message got it. One challenge of the EDCA and DCF, also impacting the V2X scenarios, is the hidden node problem. If two transmitting stations cannot hear each other, they can initiate transmission simultaneously, resulting in a collision.

ITS-G5 is based on a random-access MAC. The number of competing stations, traffic access category, packet sizes, retransmissions, and packet buffer lengths impact the delay in ITS-G5 systems on the MAC level, being spiced up by the Physical Layer (PHY) and applications. Our results empirically evaluate the V2X delays without ITS-Ss competing for the same radio resources. The CPM is of the highest priority, with only ten packets per second per ITS-S, and when broadcast, the delays, in theory, do not grow high. Comparing our results with related work based on simulations for accurately determining the practical delay behavior in congested channels is not straightforward. As no study that empirically evaluates the V2X communications delay in controlled channel loading scenarios with traffic of different access categories and multiple transmitting ITS-S exists, this is an interesting future work item, also to discover how the estimations from the literature of this work match the practice.

6.2.11 Discussion

The overall time needed for all CP components – from an event happening until reaching the awareness of it within another ITS-S – can be derived as discussed in Section 6.2.4. Table 6.5 shows the estimations from literature and includes the field operational performance metrics provided in Section 6.2.9. The discussion below will first analyze the influence of QoS parameters on the transmission, followed by analyzing essential parts of the CP chain, and finally conclude by looking at the applicability of CP in the scenarios specified in Section 6.2.5.

Influence of QoS

The V2X QoS measurements confirmed the low transmission times of V2X messages in side-by-side scenarios, as shown in Section 6.2.9. The low latency times of around 5 ms are applicable for specialized time-critical scenarios, such as virtual towing [131], where the packet loss should be close to zero. However, if a vehicle's sensors are working correctly, the nearby surroundings of a vehicle will always be covered with onboard sensors. Hence, the following form of CP scenarios applies to city scenarios, where distances are between 50 – 100 m. In these cases, we expect only to receive every other V2X message, as one message can be lost. Thus, 105 ms is a reasonable estimation for a missed message and the delay of the next one. Finally, there are scenarios with farther distances of 150 – 250 m. The PLR is high in these scenarios, primarily due to occlusion. However, those scenarios are edge scenarios for CP. They mean that two vehicles are, e.g., occluded by a long corner on a highway or by buildings in a city. Other scenarios are already city scenarios with close distances and occlusions or a scenario with a line of sight, where V2X is working again. Hence, 405 ms is estimated for those ranges. For such scenarios, it is also essential to mention that fast V2N scenarios may be in similar ranges. Correira et al. [31] shows a 200 – 6000 ms delay with LTE via a single MQTT server. However, their setup is straightforward, and delays with traffic management software would be more applicable. In general, the V2N messages of vehicles have to be managed to be only relayed in specific regions, or else the mobile network is also congested.

However, beyond our field evaluation, one has to be aware of scalability issues resulting from loaded channels and differential speed. As stated in Section 6.2.10 and compared to literature in Section 6.2.4, the back-off algorithm and EDCA system can cause a delay much greater than 100 ms. Specifically, simulations by Shahen Shah et al. [125] suggest an additional delay of 100 – 500 ms for medium channel load and differential speed, depending on the definition of medium load and differential speed. For high channel load, the delay is unbounded. In other words, a message may never arrive, depending on multiple factors, such as priority and involved ITS-Ss. Hence, we suggest a discussion on including the V2X channel load into the global fusion algorithm. To be specific, if, e.g., a free space message is sent, its validity should depend on the channel load, as the negation of the free space may not arrive in time or at all.

One big remaining issue is the scheduling of V2X messages. If the CP algorithm [48] does not consider the CP object as critical, the sending frequency is only 1 Hz, which increases the

expected delay by a factor of 10. This delay will also defeat the purpose of thinking about lost consecutive messages, as four lost messages from the expectation above would lead to 4 s of delay; this, in turn, raises the question of how the situation evolved four seconds later. One could argue that the object is not critical in this case, else another 10 Hz burst would have been sent, which in turn throws overboard all estimations on the frequency and expected lost messages. In conclusion, for the discussion in this work, we expect the object to be critical.

CP Delay Chain

It is essential to be aware of the entire CP delay chain to discuss the implications of changes in specific components. This work overviews the CP delay components in Figure 6.6. To understand the delay overhead of CP, one can subtract the local perception delay from the overall delay. Table 6.8 shows the expectations from the literature compared to an empirical analysis of the implementation in this work. The delta time is the delta between local perception and total CP delay. If local sensing and fusion are similar for both vehicles, the difference in time is primarily the added communication delay and the global fusion delay. However, as seen in Table 6.5, there is also a delay for asynchronicity. Literature shows this delay within the communication part. But as our implementation showed, this asynchronous delay can also be in global fusion.

For the discussion, there are two critical delays. The first one is the age of information. This is the delta, which is caused by transmission and global fusion. We show that CP information takes at least 1.5 times longer to be available than local perception, as shown in Table 6.5. The other critical delay concerns the first information about an event. This delay takes packet loss into account. The QoS analysis of ITS-G5 confirmed that one should expect one missed package in city scenarios, which means that global perception is twice as slow as local perception. Larger distances lead to weaker connectivity and more packet loss. Hence, there is a higher information delay, meaning the global perception delay is larger than 2.5 times the local perception.

If the channel is loaded or the differential speed is high, the information delay increases drastically, as discussed in Section 6.2.4. The tests in this work are limited by not having the capability for controlled channel loading and differential speed. Hence, Table 6.8 shows expected delays for medium and high channel load, respectively differential speed, with added estimations from simulations by Shahan Shah et al. [125].

Impact on Application Scenarios

With the complete CP delay chain, one can now discuss the applicability of CP concerning safety and comfort. At this point, one must emphasize that SOTA automated vehicles always have to carry the consequences for their actions, similar to a human driver. Thus, an AV has to drive in a way such that no critical situations arise. In general, a human driver learns in Austria/Germany that a child may walk out between vehicles, and one has to be able to stop in advance. By current standards, this is also true for an automated vehicle. The AV has to be able to stop in advance. In other words, CP may not be used to prevent such situations, as the

Table 6.8: Local perception compared to expected extra delay caused by CP, as shown in Pilz et al. [5]. Comparison of literature (lit) to field operational (real) by scenario. Premise: local perception can detect the object. Difference between CP and local perception Δt . All delays in [ms].

Scenario	$local_{lit}$	$local_{real}$	$\Delta t_{lit,low}$	$\Delta t_{lit,med}^*$	$\Delta t_{lit,high}^*$	$\Delta t_{real,low}$	$\Delta t_{real,mid}^*$	$\Delta t_{real,high}^*$
Side-by-Side	208 – 282	207.7	15 – 47	115 – 547	515 – ∞	123.9	223.9 – 623.9	623.9 – ∞
City	208 – 282	207.7	115 – 147	215 – 647	615 – ∞	223.9	323.9 – 723.9	723.9 – ∞
Highway	208 – 282	207.7	N/A	N/A	N/A	523.9	623.9 – 1023.9	1023.9 – ∞

* Scalability: additional delays for medium/high channel load and differential speed, as discussed in Chapters 6.2.4 and 6.2.9.

AV has to guarantee that. However, evaluating the delay contributes to discussing whether the general approach could change.

In general, CP may be used to improve traffic flow and comfort. If the ego vehicle knows that objects (VRUs, other vehicles, debris, or similar obstacles) do not occupy a particular area, it may increase its speed. In these cases, it is crucial if the situation changes. In other words, if an RSU sends out free-space messages via CP and the situation changes, countermeasures must be fast. There are three types of countermeasures: (i) the warning via V2X, which is the fastest if there is no direct knowledge about a situation; (ii) the onboard detection, which is the standard for an AV; and (iii) the human intervention, which is comparatively slower to the onboard detection, as elaborated in the following.

Table 6.8 shows that CP data is 123.9 – 523.9 ms slower than onboard sensor data within low channel load scenarios. Thus, if the ego vehicle can not detect the dangerous object within this time difference, V2X is faster. However, C-ITS will suffer from loaded channels, with a higher density of ITS-Ss. In city scenarios, this will likely cause 100 – 500 ms of additional delay. Depending on the circumstances, the delay may be drastically higher, up to a point where the message can not successfully be sent. Beyond transmission delays, the implementation of the tested CP chain does not include signed data or any other form of verification. Thus, the data may not be trusted, which is terrible for safety-relevant situations, as counter-actions may lead to worse situations. Therefore, verification and trust management delays have to be considered but have yet to be measured. Security delays aside, if CP information extends the FoV, the scenarios discussed in Section 6.2.5 are applicable.

Last but not least, there is human intervention. The human reaction time for objects moving into the drive path is roughly 1.5 seconds, according to Green [137]. As Table 6.5 shows, the sensing time is up to 280 ms as suggested by literature and 207.7 ms tested with our vehicle. Thus, an AV will react faster and more precisely to date. In contrast, a human may be better in their decision if it is a trained driver or in uncertain situations. However, an AV can be more aware of its surroundings, which may be even better with V2X.

The following paragraphs will discuss the three reaction methods to understand better how V2X can contribute to safety and comfort. All scenarios present lower expectations without channel load. The transmission delay is unbounded, but at least much greater than 100 ms for loaded channels, as discussed in Section 6.2.4.

City Side-by-Side Scenario The city scenario, shown in Figure 6.11, has a VRU that will come out between vehicles. As discussed above, an AV has to be aware of the possibility of such a situation. In that sense, the speed has to be according to the situation. Thus, safety should be no problem. However, it can increase comfort and performance. If the oncoming ego vehicle is aware of a declared free space or a VRU between the vehicles, it can act accordingly. With free space declared, the ego vehicle can increase its speed. The sensors of the free space declaring ITS-S will send out a CP warning of the pedestrian, which will be taken into account by the ego vehicle 123.9 ms later, due to the close distance, without channel load. If a VRU approaches the free space, the situation changes again, triggering a CP. Hence, there will not be the possibility of a sudden pedestrian appearance. Therefore, the ego vehicle has to adapt its speed according to the available free space that can cover predict-ahead estimations of VRUs, including the expected CP delay. The scenario is similar if there is already a VRU between the vehicles. In conclusion, if the CP data of the VRU can be integrated before the data of the onboard sensors, the ego vehicle will have a time advantage due to the CP data.

Highway Scenario The highway scenario shown in Figure 6.12 has a broken-down vehicle with a VRU walking around. As discussed above, such a situation should be no safety issue. However, the ego vehicle can increase speed if an ITS-S declares free space. In this case, the ego vehicle has to consider the delay caused by lost packages at long distances. In other words, if the situation changes for a particular area, at least 405 ms has to be added for the transmission time. This factor is especially true when there is no RSU but oncoming vehicles that declare the free space. In this case, there might always be a situation where oncoming vehicles have sensor range to the location of the scenario, but the ego vehicle is on maximum communication range. However, one must consider the arrival of early information that can neither be known by the ego vehicle nor by an active human driver. In that case, at least 523.9 ms of extra delay is better than having no information until getting into the sensor range. Looking further, if there is no free space but an obstacle, as shown in Figure 6.12, the ego vehicle can ensure the comfort of its passengers and slow down in advance, i.e., avoiding driving on the limit.

City Intersection Scenario The intersection scenario shown in Figure 6.13 has an intersection scenario where a VRU crosses the road behind the corner. Again, safety should not be an issue here, as the ego vehicle has to drive in a way where onboard sensors can avoid a collision. Overall, the scenario is similar to the city scenario; however, messages could be lost due to corners. In this case, we consider that an ITS-S may send out free space around the corner, but the situation changes. As the situation changes, the ITS-S detecting it immediately (10 Hz) sends out the position of a VRU crossing the street. Nevertheless, as it is a city scenario, one message may be lost. This results in at least 223.9 ms additional delay, compared to the onboard perception. Depending on the slow speeds at the intersection, this may be fast enough, depending on the channel load.

6.2.12 Conclusion

This work aims to provide a systematic view of the delays of CP. We started by defining a set of scenarios where CP can provide benefits. We then defined the delay elements of CP and collected expectations from the literature for all elements. We then set up two measurement campaigns: (i) to deepen the knowledge of V2X QoS performance with highly time-accurate measurements in low channel load scenarios and (ii) to complete the delay dataset of the CP delay chain with field operational performance measurements, of a V2X enhanced AD stack.

The update of the CP delay chain allowed us to collect delay expectations from the literature. We then used a SOTA Autoware implementation in our street-legal ADDs to collect delay results in field operational tests. We first confirmed that low latency can be fulfilled for CP with field operational QoS parameters of ITS-G5 with around 5 ms transmission time at close distances in sparse traffic scenarios. We then argued that packet loss should be counted as an additional 10 Hz cycle delay for high-priority CPMs, leading to an expected information delay of 105 ms for intersection scenarios in cities and 405 ms for highway scenarios.

The results are limited by not specifically testing loaded or congested communication. Hence, we highlight the risk in scalability, with transmission delays much greater 100 ms due to necessary MAC mechanisms. Specifically, we derived an additional 100 – 500 ms delay overhead for channels with medium load and differential speed. We highlighted that highly loaded channels have unbounded delays. Consequently, we discussed that loaded channels should be considered in the trustworthiness of CP data. In other words, if the channel is loaded, CP data will have higher delays, which results in risks, e.g., CP updates negating free space messages may never arrive.

The discussion of delays of the full CP chain also showed that a basic high delay originates in the asynchronous reception cycle. Either the CP data is received and distributed with a specific frequency before feeding it into the global fusion, or the global fusion cycle creates an asynchronous delay with its cycle. This results in a 100 ms cycle delay caused by the 10 Hz global fusion for SOTA AD software, as demonstrated in this work. Loaded channels will produce different results, making the transmission delay more prominent. However, the provided delay expectations from the literature and a SOTA system provide a basis for the optimization discussion.

Finally, the expected local perception delay – for sparse traffic scenarios, defined in Section 6.2.5 – is 207.7 ms. We argue that close-distance scenarios are a minority of use cases, as the onboard sensors should be able to cover the driving path. Hence, while the expected additional global perception delay is 123.9 ms, the expected additional information delay is at least 223.9 ms due to packet loss. In other words, in low-traffic scenarios, CP information should be expected to have at least twice the delay of local perception. However, the delay may increase drastically in higher V2X channel load cases.

As a follow-up for this work, we see (i) the integration of V2N for CP and (ii) the extension of tests for multiple global fusion sources. The usage of V2N with 5G benefits from the low latency of 5G systems, as shown by Castiglione et al. [138]. However, integrating V2N will increase the overhead with a backend system, as demonstrated by Correia et al. [31]. It will also need a management system for data exchange dedicated to geo-location. The advantage is the higher reliability for guaranteed data delivery. The disadvantage is the much higher

delay with two-way connection and backend management. The V2N connection will also create challenges for global fusion. As discussed in this work, our global fusion approach can handle limited CP sources. More than a dozen CP sources will be problematic, as the global fusion strategy has to manage the fusion of multiple input sources with various time delays. However, we see much potential in applying existing fusion strategies for onboard sensors in robotics. However, we also see difficulties with the additional time delay caused by loaded channels, which might considerably negate the need to optimize the global fusion approach.

Beyond this work, one should consider the implications of CP for safety purposes. Three immediate issues are: (i) First, lifting safety guards for higher performance can lead to dangerous situations. Not only when the CP chain is broken at some point, i.e., packet loss or unbound MAC delay, but mainly when unsecured towards adversaries and faults. Parameters on when to allow the lifting of safety guards have to be precise; (ii) second, increasing comfort by braking in advance to prevent emergency braking for VRUs can lead to psychological issues with legacy vehicles. Specifically, there needs to be explainability for passengers, and much more importantly, future VRUs will learn that vehicles brake even though they can not see them, so they are safe. If the oncoming vehicle is now a legacy vehicle, without CP functionality, fatal accidents may happen; and (iii) third, ignoring hard rules, such as stopping at red traffic lights, stopping at stop signs, ignoring speed limits, and many more, may create uncertainty in hybrid environments.

Finally, CP can increase safety and comfort by extending the FoV as long as onboard safety can be guaranteed. Beyond that, other factors, such as reliability and accuracy, play an essential role.

6.3 Focus: Field of View

This section will overview the core benefit of extending the FoV with V2XaaS. In general, every factual information is useful. V2X communication allows to share such information between ITS-Ss. This section will take a straightforward approach to confirm the possibility of extending the FoV using a small measurement campaign published in Pilz et al. [10].

6.3.1 Introduction

V2X communication allows sharing of information between ITS-Ss, which we defined as V2XaaS, as discussed in Chapter 2. Section 6.1 already showed that sharing of object information via CA and CP is possible. This was demonstrated as the same object can be detected with two different ITS-Ss.

One can now imply that if the same object can be detected with two ITS-Ss, those two ITS-Ss will also extend their respective FoV if one ITS-S does not see an object that is shared by the other ITS-S. The measurement campaign presented in this section aims to prove this premise by demonstrating the extension of the FoV of a single ITS-S with the data from another ITS-S.

6.3.2 Method

The FoV field scenarios are tested at the Graz University of Technology Inffeld campus. Selected are three basic CA/CP scenarios for AVs, which are listed in the following:

1. **Follower Scenario:** a classic follower example, where the leading vehicle extends the FoV of the follower.
2. **One Corner Scenario:** two vehicles can extend the FoV of each other, with an overlap at the intersection.
3. **No FoV overlap:** the FoV of both vehicles do not overlap; hence, there is an extension of the FoV, in proportion to the FoV of the other vehicle. Additional CP-capable vehicles can extend the FoV even further.

The scenarios are executed with the software stack discussed in Chapter 3, with all specifics as discussed in 6.1.4 and 6.2.5. Specifically, the system provides high accuracy and low delay for the data exchange. This also allows the global fusion to work. In turn, we can use the matching part of the global fusion algorithm to identify similar objects, as discussed for the accuracy performance in Section 6.1.

The measurements will allow us to compare the local perception, the global perception provided by V2X, and the fused perception, combining local and global objects.

6.3.3 Additions to the Evaluation Setup

The additions to the evaluation setup, discussed in Chapter 3, are the same as those discussed in Section 6.1.4.

6.3.4 Measurements

The big advantage of V2XaaS is the extension of the FoV. One can know about a situation without being able to detect it with onboard sensors. This can be best visualized by the three scenarios of the FoV field tests, as shown in Figure 6.22. From top to bottom, there is, at first, the side-by-side scenario. Two vehicles are roughly in the same position, standing beside each other. The FoV is just blocked by the other vehicle. In our tests, the ego vehicle (ADD: Ford Mondeo) detects, on average, 11 objects during the 5 min recording. The other vehicle (ADD: Ford Fusion) detects, on average, 13 objects. The number of objects detected by both vehicles is 8, whereas 3 objects were only detected by the ego vehicle, and 5 objects were only detected by the other vehicle. From the perspective of the number of detected objects, this leads to an average increase of 45% for the ego vehicle.

The scenario in the middle is the one-corner scenario. The FoV overlaps at the intersection. Because of the shape of the intersection, the overlapping FoV also extends towards the bottom left corner of the image. During the 5 min data recording period, the ego vehicle detected, on average, 8 objects and the other vehicle 6 objects. On average, 2 objects were detected by both vehicles, whereas 3 objects were only detected by the ego vehicle, and 5 objects were

only detected by the other vehicle. From the perspective of the number of detected objects, this leads to an average increase of 62% for the ego vehicle.

The scenario on the bottom is the no-overlap scenario, where a row of bushes separates the ego and the other vehicle. The FoV is extended close to 100% by one vehicle, as the overlap of sensor ranges is minimal. During the 5 min data recording period, the ego vehicle detected 8 objects and the other 12 objects. On average, there was 1 object detected by both vehicles. From the perspective of the number of detected objects, this leads to an average increase of 137% on the ego vehicle side.

6.3.5 Results

The recorded data showed how many objects each ADD could detect within a period of 5 min for each of the three scenarios. The AD system within each vehicle compared the locally perceived objects with the objects received via V2X. The decision on whether the same object was detected was made using the matching algorithm from the global sensor fusion algorithm. To complete the picture, the debug view of the global sensor fusion is shown in Figure 6.23. Here, the ego vehicle detects another vehicle and receives a CPM for that other vehicle. The global fusion combines the local perception and the CPM to provide a single object. In this case, we put a CPM by hand, as the detection is often too good, to highlight the fusion effect.

6.3.6 Discussion

The results show how sharing sensor information extends the FoV. Together with the accuracy and delay analysis presented in Sections 6.1 and 6.2, one can see that extending the FoV with the sensor data of one vehicle works as expected. In turn, if one would put more than one ITS-S with CPM capability, the FoV and, thus, the number of detected objects could be extended even further.

More vehicles have the advantage of increasing and detailing the FoV. However, two core problems will arise. The first one is the already elaborated problem with channel load, discussed in Section 6.2. The other issue is the eventual performance decrease of the global fusion algorithm. As discussed in Chapter 5 and 6.2, the fusion algorithm strongly depends on the objects to fuse. A high amount of objects may result in problems with the fusion algorithm. However, as also pointed out in Section 6.2, redundancy of objects may cause vast delays.

6.3.7 Conclusion

This section briefly analyzed the extension of the FoV through V2XaaS. The analysis demonstrated the extension of the FoV within a field test environment. The results show that already the side-by-side scenario has advantages, as blind spots can be covered by V2XaaS. Even more, without overlapping FoVs, the ego FoV can be increased beyond 100%.

However, it is also pointed out that an increased number of ITS-Ss may increase the number of objects drastically. This can lead to a rapid performance decrease for the global fusion algorithm of the ego vehicle.

Figure 6.22: FoV scenarios are side-by-side following (top), separated by one building corner (middle), and split by a row of bushes (bottom). The ego (grey) vehicle uses the lidar to detect object bounding boxes (green). A second vehicle sends a CAM (orange) as its position and its detected object bounding boxes via CPMs (blue), as shown in Pilz et al. [10].

Figure 6.23: The ego vehicle (faintly visible) detects another vehicle with its onboard perception (blue). Another ITS-S provides a CPM via V2X (green). The fusion algorithm combines those perceptions into a fused object (red).

6.4 Focus: Validating Applications

The results presented in this thesis are applied across three different projects. The first two applications are published in Reckenzaun et al. [7]. The application in the third one is published in Lesjak et al. [8]. This section will provide insight into the performance increase that can be gained using V2X. The following two sections refer to those publications to keep an overview.

6.4.1 CCAM Application Scenarios

Our results were applied to a transnational testing application published in Reckenzaun et al. [7]. The two EUREKA projects, *TestEPS* and *Central System*, focus on AD and V2X communication in major parts of their research. *TestEPS* addresses the certification of AD systems, while *Central System* focuses on infrastructure solutions for CCAM. Both integrate the same four technological fields: (i) simulation and virtual testing, (ii) real-world testing, (iii) HD mapping, and (iv) communication to realize their vision and achieve their individual goals. Here, we present application use cases for each field in the respective projects. Furthermore, collaboration between these two projects and respective technologies is highlighted in advancing the SOTA in CCAM technologies.

Both projects are complex in functionality, and the contributions presented in this thesis were focused on V2X specific implementations. The overall testing goals were targeted at higher-level use cases. Hence, the following paragraphs will provide summaries of the achievements.

Teleoperation

Reckenzaun et al. [139] show the full concept of the Central System project. Several experiments were conducted to test capabilities such as CP, teleoperation, and cloud-based autonomy. One of the aims was to realize a CP-aided teleoperation function through the proposed central system. A vehicle at the ZalaZONE proving ground was teleoperated from Los Angeles to demonstrate the communication capabilities during the ITS world conference 2022. It is worth mentioning here that the available bandwidth to perform the teleoperation task was limited to 1.5 kB/s.

Figure 6.24 shows the setup: the teleoperated vehicle comprised a GNSS module, three cameras, a rotating lidar sensor, and a driving robot. The sensory data was processed by a low-level camera-lidar fusion-based object detector running in the vehicle. The detection results, together with the position and heading of the test vehicle, are forwarded to the central system, where based on these data and the HD map of the area, the digital twin of the scenario is generated in real-time, as shown in Figure 6.25. During the tests, the pedestrian was represented by a pedestrian dummy. The given “traffic” situation is evaluated based on the digital twin.

While the situation is safe, the vehicle can be operated via teleoperation; thus, the actuation signals generated by the remote driving wheel and pedals are sent to the vehicle through the central system. In critical situations, the vehicle performs emergency braking, which is also

Figure 6.24: Setup for the teleoperated vehicle in the Central System project, as shown in Reckenzaun et al. [7]. The teleoperator (t.l.) accesses a cloud system from Los Angeles. The AV connects to the cloud system via V2N, provides sensor data and receives steering commands.

Figure 6.25: Central Systems teleoperation control: digital twin on the left screen, real camera image on the right screen, as shown in Reckenzaun et al. [7]. The AV is controlled from here. The data is exchanged via V2N.

realized through the central system. Similar to the demonstrated teleoperation, more complex scenarios, including several types of participants, can also be evaluated on a central system basis.

The works presented in this thesis profited from insights into the delay behavior of teleoperated vehicles. The limited bandwidth made it necessary to only transmit the own position and detected objects, similar to CAM and CPM.

C-V2X Based Collective Perception Service

A V2N CP service prototype was developed and tested within Central Systems. The developed V2N service allows sharing CP information between multiple traffic participants over a cloud service. Cloud deployment solutions were tested for real-time CP sharing. The client was integrated into ROS and running on embedded hardware for easy integration into the research vehicle.

The implemented CP service differs from the primary implementations discussed in Chapter 3. Primarily, the perception pipeline for sensing has different hardware and software components, and the message exchange was not yet standard compliant but used ROS type message exchange. However, the architecture and steps were comparable to the approach, as proposed in Chapter 5.

The delay results are limited in their comparability to the performance results in Section 6.2. However, the application and test of V2N directly showed the need for a backend management system of data to resemble the GN layer in V2X communication. Specifically, we were able to have multiple nodes communicating in the system, but the implementation is not scalable for countrywide use.

In other words, while 5G mobile networks can perform with low latency, the backend management causes extra delay. This issue is not trivial to solve and is a network scalability problem, which is out of the scope of this thesis. However, Chapter 9 will provide related research focusing on this topic, as discovered in Pilz et al. [5].

6.4.2 GNSS and RTCMEM Application Scenario

Centimeter-level GNSS Positioning Using C-ITS for Correction Data Delivery: An Experimental Study is a paper by Lesjak et al. [8] about the integration of GNSS correctional data received via RTCMEMs. The work contributed to this paper was more prominent than in the previous examples. The vehicleCAPTAIN toolbox was used in this study to analyze C-ITS as a novel way of transmitting GNSS correction data into common vehicles and AVs to achieve centimeter-level GNSS positioning accuracy. The results of using V2X and the vehicleCAPTAIN toolbox are compared to traditional 4G mobile internet connection methods.

Introduction

RTK GNSS can provide position information with an accuracy at the cm-level [140]. However, RTK positioning requires an AV to use different types of measurements and information as

correctional data from a positioning service provider, and typically, this data is sent via 4G. This implies that RTK is not available in regions and areas where 4G is not well deployed.

The AV of the future may have an increased demand for infrastructure support. As V2XaaS eases specific tasks of being informed as a hive mind. The advantage of then existing communication systems may be used to also provide GNSS RTK data not only via 4G, but also via V2X. In the works within Esrium and the above-mentioned publication, we evaluated the performance of V2X communication in the distribution of RTK data via RTCMEMs.

Method

This study compares using two sources of RTK data. The first one is data provided by 4G, and the second one is data supplied by V2X base stations of the ASFiNAG. The goal is to compare the delay of the 4G data to the delay of the V2X data.

Setup

The vehicleCAPTAIN toolbox, discussed in Chapter 4, was extended to support the distribution of RTCMEMs. Next, the vehicleCAPTAIN toolbox was connected to the computing unit of the AV. The following steps involved setting up a test system, as shown in Figure 6.26. Towards the left, the RTK service provider distributed data via 4G directly to the 4G router in the vehicle. In parallel, the data was provided to the infrastructure of the road operator ASFiNAG, which relayed the data to the vehicleCAPTAIN OBU in the AV. Towards the right, the AV used two GNSS receivers and fed them with the two input data sources. The resulting accuracy of the pose estimation was compared again within the computing unit of the AV.

Figure 6.26: Schematic representation of the GNSS correction data information flow in the RTCMEM application, as shown in Lesjak et al. [8]. The provider for correctional data (left) sends RTCMEMs in two ways. Once via mobile network directly to the AV, and once via the internet to the road operator, who relays the data via V2X.

Results

The results relevant to this thesis consist of the connectivity and delay insights. The results are as expected and as discussed in Section 6.2. The higher transmission power of RSUs provided a good network coverage, and the delay is low, as there is no channel load with only a small set of RSUs transmitting. In contrast, the 4G system provided better network coverage. However, the delay was much higher. The communication overhead for 4G was higher. Hence, the transmission was slower than the V2X connection with the small processing overhead and the fiber connection of the road operator to the service provider.

The performance of the GNSS system itself was exceptional in both cases. The error is, in both cases, smaller than 99%. The difference in the systems was only visible via the delay and, therefore, marginally better accuracy for the V2X system. However, due to the intermediate connectivity losses, the 4G system slightly beat the system's overall performance.

Discussion

Within the system presented in Lesjak et al. [8], we demonstrated the capability of V2XaaS to carry out other tasks than CA/CP as discussed in previous sections. We also were able to showcase the advantage of V2X as a low delay solution with the potential to support areas without a mobile network connection, where infrastructure or other vehicles could redistribute information, such as RTK data.

6.5 Conclusion

This Chapter summarizes the setup, measurements, and results of Section 6.1 – 6.4 to highlight the most important findings for the fast reader. Section 6.5.1 dealt with the performance in accuracy, Section 6.5.2 dealt with the performance in delay, Section 6.5.3 dealt with the FoV, and Section 6.5.4 dealt with the summary of applications.

6.5.1 Accuracy

The localization and detection of objects have to follow certain accuracy requirements. Reid et al. [141] state localization requirements of 0.2 – 1.4 m and 0.1 – 0.29 m for highways and cities, respectively. Similar values apply to the detection of objects if an AV has to navigate through traffic.

Section 3.6.2 points out that SOTA AD stacks use lidar for localization. This results in below 10 cm localization accuracy, as required by Reid et al. [141]. The lidar is also used for object detection. As Section 3.6.1 points out, the accuracy of SOTA lidar sensors is 2.5 – 8 cm depending on the distance. However, as shown in Figure 6.27, the most accurate detection only applies to the side facing the lidar. Depending on the object's shape, one cannot always accurately define the depth of information.

The localization and the detected objects are used to send out CAMs and CPMs, respectively. This means that the inaccuracy gets included in the data. The integration of both message types into the Autoware AD stack [13] of the used ADDs is discussed by Steinberger [12]. The

Figure 6.27: Simulation: ego vehicle (faintly visible) detects another vehicle (blue) with lidar points (white). A CPM indicates the position of this other vehicle (green), leading to the expected final fused object (red).

message integration is done on top of the V2X integration discussed in related publications, highlighted in Chapter 3. The final system evaluation, discussed by Pilz et al. [6], shows that the accuracy requirements stated by Reid et al. [141] can be fulfilled. The following sections highlight details on the setup and results.

Setup

For the setup, we used two ADDs with specifications as discussed in Chapter 3. Both AVs use the same lidar HD map, with the same GNSS reference point. This mitigates inaccuracies from GNSS and different maps for the localization. In other words, the localization error is the pure lidar localization error.

The object detection was compared with two different approaches. The first approach compares the perception of the other AV with the ego localization. The second approach compares the perception of the other AV to the ego's onboard perception. In all scenarios, the vehicles are time synchronized via NTP to guarantee synchronicity of around 5 – 6 ms. Time synchronicity is not important for standstill objects but is an important factor for moving objects.

Measurements

The evaluation results are best summarized in Figure 6.28. One can see the ego vehicle faintly highlighted. The other vehicle sends its position via CAM, and one can compare the onboard perception with the perception shared via CPM. One can see three different comparisons,

starting from the bottom right and going counter-clockwise. There are (i) the comparison of the localization of the ego vehicle and the CPM from the other AV. One can see that both ADDs are directly facing each other, which results in an inaccurate length of the ego vehicle. Also, a mismatch is visible, with either the ego vehicle being too far to the bottom or the other vehicle too far to the top of the image. This results from either inaccurate localization or detection; (ii) the localization of the other AV and the ego's onboard perception. Here, the angle is better, and the entire length of the other AV can be detected. However, one can again see a slight mismatch in perception; and finally, (iii) the comparison of a CPM and the ego's onboard perception in the top row. One can see that the perception of the other AV is most compromised as the close position of the lidar does not allow an accurate detection of the length of the other vehicles.

Figure 6.28: The local and global perception, as shown in Pilz et al. [6]. The ego vehicle (slightly opaque vehicle) has a local perception (blue), which is overlaid with CAMs (orange) and CPMs (green).

Results

The visualization of the perception, shown in Figure 6.28, indicates that there is not much difference when comparing different combinations of message types for their accuracy. The mismatch of detected object size and orientation is much more prominent, which also causes wrong center points when sharing that data via CPMs.

The object sizes are compared to the ground truth in the first step to highlight the issue. The next step compares the RMSE for position and orientation. Both steps have been done for a pedestrian and the two ADDs. The results indicate three core findings, as shown in Figures 6.29 and 6.30. The first finding is that the object size is detected incorrectly, which highly influences the accuracy of the RMSE of the final position due to the design of the CPM, which requires sharing the center point and the length and width of the object. The second finding is that the object's orientation can be off 180° for vehicles and cannot be determined for pedestrians with SOTA detection algorithms, which may cause high inaccuracies in the fusion process. The final finding is that the 10 Hz fusion cycle does not cause significant issues for the accuracy, other than the object having moved, which can be compensated with classic motion compensation.

Figure 6.29: Results of detected vehicle sizes [m] in scenario I (top) and pedestrian sizes in scenario III (bottom). The x-axis shows static measurements (A, C, E) and dynamic measurements (B, D, F), each with distances (10m, 30m, 60m), as shown in Pilz et al. [6].

6.5.2 Delay

The previous section discussed the accuracy that can be provided by SOTA CA and CP systems and compared this accuracy to functional safety requirements. The section also highlighted that information delay, specifically the age of information, is a problem that can partly be solved by motion compensation. Typically, SOTA AD systems have 10 Hz sensor cycles, which require a maximum of 100 ms of motion compensation. However, V2X may need more than this cycle time for detection, transmission, and fusion. The actual delay is higher, as the systematic approach in Pilz et al. [5] shows. Even more, the delay can be unbounded, meaning there is the lowest possible delay, which can be expected in uncrowded use cases, but the upper possible delay can be infinite.

Figure 6.30: Results of the RMSEs for distances [m] and orientation [rad] in scenarios I-III (t.b.). The x-axis shows static measurements (A, C, E) and dynamic measurements (B, D, F), each with distances (10 m, 30 m, 60 m), as shown in Pilz et al. [6].

Setup

For the setup, we used two ADDs with specifications as discussed in Chapter 3. Both AVs use the same V2X configuration, building upon the vehicleCAPTAIN toolbox that is integrated into the Autoware AD stack [13]. Additionally, we used a laboratory setup, where the vehicles are simulated, with the V2X hardware in the loop. In all scenarios, the QoS analysis is provided by Qosium with a 1PPS synchronized time reference, as discussed in Chapter 3.

The laboratory and field tests have been published in two papers. Pilz et al. [5] uses a systematic approach to analyze the entire delay loop, from a detectable event happening until realization is possible in the receiver. The delay behavior in distance and occlusion-dependent scenarios is also highlighted. Pilz et al. [10] follow this work with details on loaded channels.

Measurements

One of the core findings is the CPM delay chain, shown in Figure 6.31. The delay chain is an extension of the CPM chain defined by Rauch et al. [47] and discussed in Chapter 5. One significant difference is the arrangement of the V2X delay. Rauch et al. [47] put this delay into the V2X domain, however, from implementation perspective it is part of the global fusion. Specifically, the global fusion has to integrate several V2X sources into the local perception, which can be done with different strategies, causing different delays.

Another core finding is the overall delay that can be expected. The entire delay chain is analyzed from the occurrence of an event, including the sensor delay, the transmission delay, and the fusion delays. The results are put into perspective with estimations from literature, as shown in Table 6.9. This information delay is also compared to the overall possible information

Figure 6.31: CPM delay chain, from an event happening until collective awareness, as shown in Pilz et al. [5]. Involved are (i) the other vehicle and communication partner that senses its environment and sends the information via V2X and (ii) the ego vehicle that runs its local perception and puts the received global perception on top. The global fusion is run asynchronously to the received CP information.

age.

Table 6.9: Local perception compared to expected extra delay caused by CP in field operational scenarios, as shown in Pilz et al. [5,10]. Premise: local perception can detect the object. Difference between CP and local perception Δt . All delays in [ms].

Scenario	local	Δt_{low}	Δt_{mid}^*	Δt_{high}^*
Side-by-Side	207.7	123.9	223.9 – 623.9	623.9 – ∞
City	207.7	223.9	323.9 – 723.9	723.9 – ∞
Highway	207.7	523.9	623.9 – 1023.9	1023.9 – ∞

* Scalability: includes expected delays for channel load.

One final core finding is the delay behavior in loaded channels. The discovery of this was made possible by artificially loading the V2X channel with messages and measuring the transmission delay of CAMs and CPMs. The results published in Pilz et al. [10] confirm field expectations from earlier work and literature on channel starvation with high individual delay. However, it is also highlighted that the standardized specifications should allow for the smooth operation of use cases.

Results

For the discussion of results, one has to differentiate the delay of the information from the age of information. The delay typically specifies from sensing over transmission to integration in one go. The age of the information can be higher, as the information may be there, but if the packet is lost, the information has to be retransmitted.

To be specific, the involved publications [5,10] were able to confirm the low latency transmission times in V2X scenarios with good connectivity, but they also highlighted the very likely cases of lost messages and starved channels. Lost messages are dangerous in occluded scenarios or scenarios with interference, where single messages cannot be received. In channel-loaded scenarios, there is the risk of a full channel, meaning that a single sender may not be able to send the messages in the sending queue because the channel is full. In these cases, the buffer may be filled by even more messages, delaying future messages indefinitely.

One must consider the actual V2X applications in all cases. In many scenarios, it is already beneficial if an AV can receive information before it can be detected with onboard sensors. If onboard sensors can cover specific areas and information is sent redundantly via V2X, the usefulness of V2X can be questioned. In between, there are other use cases in traffic jam scenarios, where the standard has to guarantee that the channel is not too loaded to prevent channel congestion. In other cases, with high safety risk, the standard has to ensure that V2X information is reliably transmitted if needed. In other words, AVs should not rely on receiving highly important V2X messages from around the block in city environments. They should also not rely on V2X messages sent over long distances with sparse traffic that could compromise the channel by increasing the likelihood of lost messages.

6.5.3 Field of View

In general, information that can not be acquired with onboard sensors, V2XaaS, can be an advantage, as discussed in multiple examples within the publications on which this thesis is based. Explicitly highlighted in Pilz et al. [10] is the fact of the extension of the FoV. While this work mainly highlights the detection of objects, CPMs can carry much more information. Even more, other ETSI-standardized V2X messages can provide much more information about the surroundings of an AV. In question is the applicability of V2X information, which is discussed in Chapter 7.

6.5.4 Validated Applications

The work in this thesis was applied to a transnational testing application at the ZalaZONE⁶ proving ground in Hungary. The focus was, among other scenarios, the implementation of low latency ITS-G5 communication, to be compared to server backend-based 5G communication in V2I scenarios. Results showed the synergy between both technologies to support low latency communication in critical situations and high bandwidth communication and network coverage for teleoperation and digital twins.

Another low latency and accuracy application, where the work of this thesis was used, is the integration of GNSS correctional data via RTCMEMs, which is published in Lesjak et al. [8]. The focus was to provide active GNSS correctional data via V2X and integrate it into the GNSS localization system of an AV. The accuracy of the setup was compared to correctional data received via 4G. The results show that a localization accuracy below 10 cm could be provided 99% of the time, which is a perfect result for localization at highway speeds. The use

⁶<https://zalazone.hu/>

case also shows that GNSS correctional data is perfectly viable in V2X scenarios, as it decreases the overall mobile network load.

CHAPTER 7

V2X-as-a-Sensor-Rating

Previous chapters defined the components and analyzed the performance of V2XaaS. This chapter will look at how to rate the QoS of the surrounding V2X field, focusing on RQ3. The rating scheme is based on the performance indicators highlighted in Chapter 6. The chapter will discuss eight identified influencing factors clustered into four groups. Each factor and group is accompanied by a weight to allow tuning towards use cases. The focus is on our latest investigations, focused on rating the V2X field [10] and Mörtl et al. [9], discussing the importance of the V2X field quality for AD in general and user acceptance in specific.

Having information about the surroundings is good for an AV. However, the components of V2XaaS discussed in Chapter 5 indicate that the formatting, the delay, and the accuracy of the data involved diminish the quality of available information. Chapter 6 highlights these shortcomings in detail, which allows a rating algorithm to be put on top. This rating algorithm is intended to provide AD systems with an indicator of the quality of the surrounding V2X field. With this, the AD system can reason about the confidence of the integration of V2X data in the planning step of the SPA cycle. This chapter will introduce the rating metric in Section 7.1 before applying it to three scenarios in Section 7.2. Finally, Section 7.3 will discuss the importance of knowing about the quality of the surrounding V2X field for AD in general and user acceptance in specific.

7.1 The Rating Metric

The designed rating metric includes eight identified factors, which can be clustered into four groups, as shown in Figure 7.1. Each component rates the data's quality in relation to a specific area. It is important to note that the components are focused on the cmWave technologies, specific to ITS-G5. Other forms of V2X communication, such as mmWave or mobile networks with server backends, need different metrics and, in part, different rating parameters.

The scope and influence of the identified factors are discussed in the following sections. In general, the rating is based on a 0 – 5 rating scheme $R \in \mathbb{N}[0, 5]$, with a denotation as shown in Table 7.1.

The rating also includes influence weights ω . Those influence weights are implementation-specific and situation-specific. Implementation-specific means fitting the AD stack and its

Figure 7.1: The components used by the algorithm for the rating of the V2X field, as shown in Pilz et al. [10].

Table 7.1: Rating Levels of the V2X Field, as shown in Pilz et al. [10].

Rating	Denotation	Explanation
0	N/A	not available, or not considered
1	bad	there is useful information from time to time
2	sparse	there is useful information, but not always
3	okay	the FOV can be extended
4	good	information as useful as onboard information
5	excellent	information better than onboard information

inherent planning process. Situation-specific means that different use cases require different quality features.

The final V2X field rating is the sum of all those components, as defined in Equation 7.1. However, as the discussion in Section 7.2 will show, different driving situations and implementations require different importance of the elements included in the rating. Hence, the equation uses weights ω_{CL} , ω_{QI} , ω_{RI} , ω_{TI} to provide means of parameter tuning. The weights are normalized with the sum of all weights.

$$R = \frac{\omega_{CL}R_{CL} + \omega_{QI}R_{QI} + \omega_{RI}R_{RI} + \omega_{TI}R_{TI}}{\omega_{CL} + \omega_{QI} + \omega_{RI} + \omega_{TI}} \quad (7.1)$$

7.1.1 Channel Load

The channel load rating R_{CL} involves two components: the capacity of single ITS-Ss $R_{CL_{msgs,its}}$ and the overall channel capacity $R_{CL_{msgs,ch}}$, both as modeled in Figure 7.2. The overall R_{CL} , defined in Equation 7.2, is the weighted sum of the N_{its} individual channel loads and the overall channel load. The weights ω_{its} and ω_{ch} depend on the AD system and the driving situation. The following sections will describe their features in more depth.

$$R_{CL} = \frac{(N_{its}^{-1} * \sum R_{CL_{msg,its}}) \omega_{CL_{its}} + R_{CL_{msgs,ch}} \omega_{CL_{ch}}}{\omega_{CL_{its}} + \omega_{CL_{ch}}} \quad (7.2)$$

Figure 7.2: Channel Load metrics for the V2X field rating algorithm. Messages per incoming ITS-S (left). Load of messages on the channel (right). As shown in Pilz et al. [10].

Number of Incoming Messages (ITS-S)

Section 6.2 showed that individual ITS-Ss suffer starvation if the message frequency is too high. Specifically, the DCC manages the limit via the Channel Busy Ratio (CBR). Depending on the already available amount of messages on the channel, the DCC dictates the t_{off} and, therefore, the maximum frequency for sending. This results in 0 – 40 Hz for a single ITS-S and 160 Hz for multiple ITS-Ss, as shown by Pilz et al. [10].

The rating of the capacity of a single ITS-S can be represented by a parabolic function, as modeled in Figure 7.2. The best setup is exactly in the middle. There are enough messages from one station to have a consistent flow of information, but there is still room for additional messages. The components for this parabolic rating are defined in Equation 7.3. The range for x is from $0 - DCC_{max}$, with DCC_{max} being dictated by the CBR in the DCC mechanism. The value r is the number of rating steps.

$$R_{CL_{msg,its}} = \frac{\left(\frac{DCC_{max}}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{DCC_{max}}{2} - x\right)^2}{\frac{1}{r}\left(\frac{DCC_{max}}{2}\right)^2} \quad (7.3)$$

Number of Incoming Messages (Channel)

The channel capacity dictates the upper limit when reaching beyond the DCC. For small CAMs, and therefore small emergency DENMs, this is around 1300 Hz for single ITS-Ss and, on average, around 1000 Hz for multiple ITS-Ss. However, the latter is very uncertain, as discussed by Pilz et al. [10].

From a channel perspective, it is better to have fewer messages, as an unloaded channel allows individuals to send information at will. Hence, the more messages there are, the worse the channel quality, as modeled in Figure 7.2. The rating $R_{CL_{msgs,ch}}$, defined in Equation 7.4, can be calculated for x in the range from $0 - N$, with N being the maximum number of messages expected in the channel, and σ being a tuning parameter. For reference, Pilz et al. [10] selected $N = 1300$ for the channel capacity and $\sigma = 2$ to reflect the uncertainty shown in the multi-sender approach. Both numbers can be adapted to expected message sizes and channel capacity.

$$R_{CL_{msgs,ch}} = r * e^{-\frac{\sigma}{N} * x} \quad (7.4)$$

7.1.2 Quality of Information

The quality of information rating R_{QI} can be calculated as defined in Equation 7.5. Its elements, the accuracy, and age of information, modeled in Figure 7.3, have been discussed in much detail in previous research [5,6]. Accuracy and age can be checked already by the V2X message system if the respective fields are filled in the message. If the fields have not been filled or there is doubt about the data, this has to be analyzed in the trustworthiness rating. The weights $\omega_{QI_{acc}}$ and $\omega_{QI_{age}}$ are again dependent on the AD implementation and driving situation.

$$R_{QI} = \frac{\omega_{QI_{acc}} R_{QI_{acc}} + \omega_{QI_{age}} R_{QI_{age}}}{\omega_{QI_{acc}} + \omega_{QI_{age}}} \quad (7.5)$$

Accuracy of Information

Ground truth is the best and can be provided for speed limits, intersections, and construction sites. However, localization of vehicles is already off due to sensor accuracy. Pilz et al. [5] expect an accuracy of 2.5 cm for the localization. Reid et al. [141] state localization

Figure 7.3: Quality of Information metrics for the V2X field rating algorithm. Accuracy of information (left). Age of information (right). As shown in Pilz et al. [10].

requirements of 0.2 to 1.4 m and 0.1 to 0.29 m for highways and cities, respectively. However, while the input for CAMs is localization, this differs from other events detected with sensors, such as for CPMs or DENMs. Pilz et al. [6] expect an accuracy of 2.5 to 8 cm for the distance accuracy of a lidar sensor. Including point cloud filtering and object detection, the accuracy can be expected to be around 10 cm for the side facing the ego vehicle. Depending on the objects' shape, uncertainty can be much higher than 1 m in the depth information. For CPMs in general, one can expect an accuracy of around 0.3 to 1.9 m for standstill and low speeds. Hence, the accuracy of information $R_{Q_{acc}}$, defined in Equation 7.6, is highest below 0.1 m. After that, it will rapidly decrease to a minimum of around 10 m, as shown in Figure 7.3.

$$R_{Q_{acc}} = 2 - \ln\left(\frac{x}{5}\right) \quad (7.6)$$

Age of Information

The rating for the age of information $R_{Q_{age}}$ is based on the time from an event happening until the knowledge has arrived, as discussed by Yates et al. [142]. For V2X, this has been shown in previous research [5]. This is particularly important when dealing with CPMs. CPMs may be sent out immediately for critical data. However, the frequency may be lower than the 10 Hz cycle for load protection and less important data. Yet, a loaded channel already means a bad rating on R_{CL} , so penalizing both satisfies the algorithm.

All information with an age below 100 ms is considered excellent for the algorithm. This equals information, such as the localization in a CAM, or permanent information like construction sites within a 10 Hz cycle. 1 s old information is okay because it fits into 1 Hz cycles. Finally, everything older than 10 s should be considered aged and probably irrelevant.

The calculation of $R_{Q_{age}}$ is defined in Equation 7.7. It is modeled after calculating half-life time in physics, as modeled in Figure 7.3.

$$R_{Q_{age}} = 10 - \ln(x) \quad (7.7)$$

7.1.3 Relevance of Information

The rating for the relevance of information R_{RI} is distance and novelty dependent, as defined in Equation 7.8. The components are modeled in Figure 7.4 and discussed further in the paragraphs below.

$$R_{RI} = \frac{\omega_{RI_{dist}} R_{RI_{dist}} + \omega_{RI_{novel}} R_{RI_{novel}}}{\omega_{RI_{dist}} + \omega_{RI_{novel}}} \quad (7.8)$$

Figure 7.4: Relevance of Information metrics for the V2X field rating algorithm. Distance of Information (left). Novelty of information (right). As shown in Pilz et al. [10].

Distance of Information

There are two approaches for rating the distance of information $R_{RI_{dist}}$. The first approach is rating the maximum sending distance, discussed in-depth in previous research [5]. However, the channel load handles the transmission quality by rating the messages from a single ITS-S. It merely depends on the transmission power. The second approach is rating the distance of the sent content. The GN layer allows the distribution of messages outside the true geographical location and forwarding messages beyond the true location. All, of course, within the specified geographical validity.

For $R_{RI_{dist}}$, defined in Equation 7.9, the distance between the location of the ego ITS-S is rated at the time of reception and the location of the event. In the case of messages with multiple events, such as with multiple objects in CPMs, the target location is the location of the central element, in this case, the central reference, i.e., ego vehicle or RSU. One can expect a parabolic-shaped rating, with 250 m having the best rating, as this is beyond the FoV of most used sensors but still close enough to be relevant for most driving scenarios. Closer distances cross the 100 m mark, where received information is already available via local sensors. Conversely, information exceeding 400 m may change until an ego vehicle is close. For example, highway speeds are too fast for such distant information to be highly relevant, and in cities with low speeds, information may change or be detected by onboard sensors way in advance.

$$R_{RI_{dist}} = \frac{\left(\frac{range_{max}}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{range_{max}}{2} - x\right)^2}{\frac{1}{r}\left(\frac{range_{max}}{2}\right)^2} \quad (7.9)$$

Novelty of Information

The AD stack uses information for planning that must be available within specific periods. Reaction time for operational planning is around 100 ms, path planning takes around 1 s, and mission planning can be larger than 10 s. The complement is true for input data. Sensor data, such as the exact positions of pedestrians on the road, should have a maximum estimated lifetime of 100 ms because movement prediction for longer times will be difficult. The acceptable lifetime for the end of a traffic jam is 1 s, as there should be the possibility that oncoming vehicles relay this information. The position of a construction site or speed limit is larger than 10 s because it's persistent.

If information is already there and it is repeated, it is not novel. Hence, time should have passed if the same information is received again. Hence, the existing data decays following a half-life-like rating for the algorithm. The rating for new information is the inverse of this half-life-like decay. The novelty of information rating $R_{RI_{novel}}$ for new information is $r = 5$, the highest rating level. For existing information, t is the current lifetime and $t_{max} = [0.1, 1, 10]$ the maximum lifetime validity, as defined in Equation 7.10. Therefore, the plot for repeated information would have the shape modeled in Figure 7.4.

$$R_{RI_{novel}} = r - \left(r * e^{-\ln(r+1)\frac{t}{t_{max}}}\right) \quad (7.10)$$

7.1.4 Trustworthiness of Information

Trustworthiness is a matter of security and data correctness. Security mainly concerns protecting the V2X channel against adversaries. Data correctness deals with verifying data that does not have malicious intent. Trustworthiness of information R_{TI} is the sum of trustworthy sources and the available, trustworthy data, as defined in Equation 7.11 and Figure 7.5.

$$R_{TI} = \frac{\omega_{TI_{srcs}} R_{TI_{srcs}} + \omega_{TI_{data}} R_{TI_{data}}}{\omega_{TI_{srcs}} + \omega_{TI_{data}}} \quad (7.11)$$

Trustworthy Sources

The rating on trustworthy sources $R_{TI_{srcs}}$ indicates the trustworthiness of data from ITS-Ss. Expected is a Gaussian distribution of the trustworthy ratings for each source. The ratings for a single source can be sampled as defined in Equation 7.12 and Figure 7.5. A rating of three is a basic trust via certified sources. Towards a rating of one, there is distrust with ITS-Ss that can not provide enough security. Towards a rating of five, one can say ITS-Ss are verified using additional V2X security. Generally, the rating of trustworthy sources results from ongoing research in V2X cyber security challenges [100,101,102,103].

Figure 7.5: Relevance of Information metrics for the V2X field rating algorithm. Trustworthy Sources (left). Trustworthy Data (right). As shown in Pilz et al. [10].

$$\text{Expected } R_{TI_{data}} \text{ distribution} = e^{-(r-2.5)^2} \quad (7.12)$$

Trustworthy Data

The rating on trustworthy data deals with the correctness of data [70,104,105,106]. Specifically, incoming data may not necessarily be wrong due to malicious intent. Trustworthy sources can filter malicious intent. However, data may be wrong due to sensor malfunctions or sending ITS-Ss that are not perfectly localized. Yet the information may still be valuable. One way to approach trustworthy data is cross-confirmation with other incoming sources. Similar to the onboard sensors of an automated vehicle.

Hence, the trustworthy data rating $R_{TI_{data}}$ is chosen to follow a saturation, increasing with the rate σ , as defined in Equation 7.13. For the plot, modeled in Figure 7.5, $\sigma = 5$ is chosen, as this fits well with estimations of Zheng et al. [126], about the channel load causing issues, with more than 20 vehicles. Figure 7.5 shows that $R_{TI_{data}}$ has a good set of confirming data before saturating.

$$R_{RI_{itss}} = r(1 - e^{-\frac{x}{\sigma}}) \quad (7.13)$$

7.1.5 FoV of Information

The FoV is not yet integrated into Figure 7.1 as a metric element, as it needs to be further analyzed and discussed. The measurements around the FoV extension revealed two core elements of the FoV. However, as the following discussion will show, they need some work before being integrated into a simple metric.

FoV Coverage

The sensor coverage is the first element to rate the quality of the extended FoV. Specifically, what area is covered by the sensors of another ITS-S? The sensor coverage itself influences the metric. Speaking only of CPMs, the sensor coverage can be given by the parameters of the sensor setup that can be distributed with the CPM.

However, the sensor image contains blind spots due to obstructions. For a true picture of the sensor coverage, information must be provided by something, such as occupancy grids, which increases the effort in communication from high-level sensor data to feature-based data, as discussed by Pilz et al. [2]. Other messages, such as CAMs, may only provide information for a certain bounding box, or DENMs may only provide meta information of the area. How can we interpret the latter for FoV coverage?

To reveal another question, let one solution be that there is a message describing the FoV. The metric to rate the FoV Coverage could then calculate the FoV increase by comparing the ego FoV with the FoV provided by other ITS-Ss, whereas the FoV of the other ITS-Ss has to be corrected for overlaps first. This method would raise two questions: (i) How should one handle the gaps between higher and lower quality between two FoV areas, and (ii) how should one handle the gap in trustworthiness between FoV areas?

Finally, how do we pinpoint the quality of the resulting FoV coverage? Where can it be put into the 0–5 Rating scale? What is the difference between bad and good FoV coverage and excellent coverage?

FoV Occupancy

The previous chapter indicated a need for this metric by discussing the differences between DENMs, CAMs, and CPMs. We introduced V2X-as-a-sensor by claiming that factual information may always increase one's perception of one's environment. However, the mentioned messages also primarily spread information that is there, but what is missing is information that is not there, most prominently free spaces.

The onboard sensors of an ego vehicle detect objects, and due to sensor placement and characteristics, they can also provide information about the surrounding free space. For example, if one takes a lidar, the space between the sensor and the object is typically free. Exceptions apply, of course, if it is a mirror or similar optical effect.

This means, in turn, that much information for calculating the FoV occupancy may be missing. Occupancy calculations are, at their base, already computationally intensive. If there is an additional lack of information, the calculation may not benefit the system. Future research must analyze the domain of AD planners and occupancy grid calculation and compare them to the limited bandwidth and information gained through V2X.

7.2 Metric Application

This section will summarize examples published in Pilz et al. [10] to discuss the viability of V2XaaS in common use case scenarios. It will discuss (i) a standard highway drive with low traffic, (ii) a big city scenario during rush hour, and (iii) a parking lot scenario at a mall. These

scenarios will cover situations with low and high traffic and information density and a specific use case scenario that is only manageable with V2X.

The expectations of input values are taken from the studies in Chapter 6, and the resulting ratings are provided in Table 7.2 for all scenarios. Additionally, all weights are default weights of $\omega = 1$.

Table 7.2: Expected input values and resulting ratings for the discussed scenarios. Weights ($\omega = 1$), as shown in Pilz et al. [10].

Scenario	Load	Quality	Relevance	Trust	V2XaaS
Highway	4	4	3	2	3
Rush Hour	3	5	1	5	4
Parking Lot	4	5	1	4	4

7.2.1 Highway Scenario

For this scenario, we expect a rural highway with sparse traffic where the only changing V2X traffic is caused by oncoming traffic. At 100 km/h, we can expect a vehicle to join our communication range every ten seconds. With a perfect line of sight, we estimate the maximum communication range to be around 400 m [5]. This means that one vehicle has around 30 s within the communication range. With this traffic density, we would have around four vehicles in the oncoming traffic and two in our lane for communication. On the highway, the frequency for CAMs would decrease in the lower third of the 10 Hz from field experience. The CPMs would be in the upper third of the 10 Hz because of the rapidly changing positions of detected vehicles. Hence, for our example, we can expect below 10 Hz of messages per ITS-S and 70 Hz in total for all surrounding ITS-Ss without packet loss. The packet loss will bring both numbers slightly down, which means the rating for the number of incoming messages per ITS-S is $R_{CL_{msg}} = 3$ and per channel is $R_{CL_{ch}} = 5$. The final rating is then $R_{CL} = ((7^{-1}(3 * 7)) * 1 + 5 * 1) / (1 + 1) = 4$.

For the quality of information, we know that the localization accuracy has to be better than 1.4 m for highways [141], and we also know that the accuracy for CPMs can be off 1.9 m at low speeds [6]. Both have an accuracy rating of $R_{QI_{acc}} = 3$. The rating for the age of information will be $R_{QI_{age}} = 5$ because when the message is sent, it is recent. The final rating is $R_{QI} = (3 * 1 + 5 * 1) / 2 = 4$.

We have distances up to 400 m for the relevance of information. The average rating of the information of all seven vehicles is $R_{RI_{dist}} = 4$. For the novelty of information, one can see that multiple CPMs will confirm the position of vehicles. CPM redundancy specifications will cause better novelty of information but a higher age of information. Higher CPM frequencies will lead to more loaded channels and packet loss. Hence, a novelty rating of around $R_{RI_{novel}} = 2$ is applicable. The final rating is $R_{RI} = (4 * 1 + 2 * 1) / 2 = 3$.

For the trustworthiness of information, we expect a rating of $R_{TI_{src}} = 3$ for trustworthy sources. Onboard the ego vehicle, we can only process the signature of incoming messages. Everything else needs a backend system that is not yet available. For the data itself, we can either put $R_{TI_{data}} = 0$ because there is too little traffic to confirm the positions of vehicles, or we can put $R_{TI_{data}} = 1$ because there are too few stations to confirm the data. To engage in a discussion, we do the latter. The final rating is $R_{TI} = (2 * 1 + 1 * 1) / 2 = 2$.

The overall final rating is now $R = (4 * 1 + 4 * 1 + 3 * 1 + 2 * 1) / 4 = 3$. One can see from the process of acquiring this rating that multiple incoming sources must be considered. Each message within the time for calculation needs a separate rating. Our example puts it easy and estimates a rough outline. One can also see that the rating should depend on the driving situation. As we drive on the highway, e.g., the novelty of information may be rated differently. Also, the configuration of importance weights for the ratings may change the trustworthiness of information down to $R_{TI} = 1$.

7.2.2 Rush Hour Scenario

In this scenario, we expect a traffic jam or slow traffic during rush hour in a bigger city like Vienna/Austria. We have a road with four lanes in one direction, towards an intersection crossing a similar road. There are hardly any pedestrians because it is an industrial area. Furthermore, as it is a city scenario, we can expect less range due to obstructions [5]. Still, the overall transmission power will also be reduced by the ITS-Ss [143].

We can expect each ITS-S to send hardly any messages for the channel load. The traffic is slow. Hence, the CAMs are down to 1 Hz. The CPMs will also be on the lower end because vehicles are not moving, and there are hardly any pedestrians on the main traffic way. The rating of incoming messages for all ITS-Ss is $R_{CL_{msg}} = 1$. The rating for the overall channel load now also depends on the interpretation. In such a scenario, the regulations for message generation of CAMs and CPMs and the transmission power reduction may allow a channel load rating of $R_{CL_{ch}} = 4$. However, this may drastically change if people walk between vehicles, as this would be considered dangerous and important, to which extent multiple vehicles would increase the transmission of messages. The final channel rating is hence $R_{CL} = (1 + 4) / 2 = 3$.

For the quality of information, we can expect highly accurate data at a standstill and with low speeds [6]. Also, the age of information can be expected to be low with the above channel expectations and field results gathered in this paper. Hence, the final quality rating is $R_{QI} = (5 + 5) / 2 = 5$.

For the relevance of information, we can expect a low rating of $R_{RI_{dist}} = 1$ for the distance of information, as most messages are received from surrounding vehicles in a range that onboard sensors could cover. The novelty of information will also be poor, as multiple vehicles detect each other, resulting in multiple updated surrounding objects. Even with CPM redundancy mitigation on each vehicle, one may expect a novelty of information rating of $R_{RI_{novel}} = 1$. Hence, the final relevance of information rating is $R_{RI} = (1 * 1) / 2 = 1$, which can be expected in a traffic jam.

For the trustworthiness rating, ultimately, the opposite can be expected. For the trustworthy sources, we can expect $R_{TI_{src}} = 5$, as there is the chance to confirm messages of one vehicle

multiple times, and other vehicles could confirm the trustworthiness of single sources. Similarly, the trustworthy data rating will be $R_{TI_{data}} = 5$ in normal conditions because we can verify incoming data easily with cross-correlated information from other vehicles. Hence, the final trustworthiness rating is $R_{TI} = (5 + 5)/2 = 5$.

In this scenario, one can see that the weights have to be adapted for specific traffic situations. One can expect the quality of information to be high. However, the relevance of information should have a much higher impact on the overall rating, as the V2XaaS information is mostly unnecessary computing overhead during rush hour. Digging deeper, the channel load itself is on a split. One should argue that the quality rating is more a 2 than a 3 because while the overall channel load is good, individuals have less capacity for the overall channel.

7.2.3 Parking Lot Scenario

In this scenario, we discuss the quality rating of the V2X field on a busy day at a shopping center's parking lot. There are many objects, from vehicles to bicycles to pedestrians. The load of information is high. However, parked vehicles will not communicate in our scenario. Only the vehicles driving between the lanes and looking for a parking spot will.

We can expect rapid updates of 10Hz for the channel load for CAMs as vehicles maneuver. We can also expect rapid updates of 10 Hz for CPMs, as pedestrians will walk around, triggering the generation. Hence, the individual channel load rating is $R_{CL_{msg}} = 5$, right in the optimal center. However, the overall channel load is most likely at $R_{CL_{ch}} = 3$, up to around 20 vehicles. Also, $R_{CL_{ch}} = 2$ is realistic on a busy day. In both cases, the channel rating is $R_{CL} = 4$ with $R_{CL} = (5 + 3)/2 = 4$ and $R_{CL} = (5 + 2)/2 = 4$.

The quality of information is tricky to estimate. As we showed in previous research [6], the accuracy of detected vehicles is low when the dimensions can not be fully detected. Hence, the accuracy rating can be expected as $R_{QI_{acc}} = 4$ on average. The age of information is dependent on the channel load. If CPMs are going to starve in the sending queue, the age of information is increased. However, most messages are likely coming through with low delay, as the channel is only half full, leading to $R_{QI_{age}} = 5$. Hence, the final quality of information rating is $R_{QI} = (4 + 5)/2 = 5$.

The relevance of information is similar to the rush hour scenario. The information distance is $R_{RI_{dist}} = 1$, as most of the critical parking lot movement can be detected with onboard sensors. Also, the novelty of information is down at $R_{RI_{novel}} = 1$ because the movement of pedestrians requires frequent updates of the position and their heading, but the object itself is already known. Hence, the final relevance rating is $R_{RI} = (1 + 1)/2$.

The trustworthiness rating is again expected to be high. The trustworthiness of sources can be verified in multiple updates, as the ITS-Ss stay long in the communication range. This results in a rating of $R_{TI_{src}} = 5$. The trustworthy data rating is also high because multiple vehicles confirm each other. However, due to standstill vehicles parking between the active vehicles, it is more likely that only a handful of vehicles can verify each other, which is a rating of $R_{TI_{data}} = 3$. Hence, the final trustworthy rating of $R_{TI} = (5 + 3)/2 = 4$.

The parking lot scenario is another good example of V2X-as-a-sensor. V2X can track traffic around the corner, such as open parking spots. However, as one can see from the relevance of

information ratings, repeated information can be a downside. This scenario also shows that the weights for the overall V2X field rating inputs must be adapted for each use case. For example, individual channel loads may be more prominent, similar to the information age. Also, the novelty of information may be less relevant than the trustworthiness of information to guarantee the safety of pedestrians.

7.2.4 Discussion

The structure of the proposed rating approach aims at ease of use and the possibility of separation. Ease of use is important to not fill the AD system with unnecessary computational load. Even more, the ease of use and the possibility of separation allow the calculation to be done already at the component level and export of the rating as a status indicator. The separation also allows a differentiated view of the complex quality of the surrounding V2X field.

The evaluation scenarios were selected to highlight this differentiated view. Where applicable, the scenario discussion highlighted which parts are most important for the scenario at hand and where the calibration of weights could improve the overall indication of performance. In that regard, it is also important to note that the ease of use, together with the separation, allows the comparison of different views on quality by selecting different weights and comparing the resulting ratings.

One limitation of the current algorithm is the missing input for the concrete implementation of the trustworthiness metrics. To our knowledge, there is no clear path towards rating trustworthiness in the sector of CCAM. Hence, there is an estimation of how the trustworthiness indication could be shaped. Nevertheless, it is included in this proposal of this rating metric, as it is a highly important factor, as visualized by the use cases.

Finally, we look forward to using the metric output to study the quality behavior of the surrounding V2X field during runtime and active test cases. We are also looking forward to using the found data to train AI models to predict the rating of the V2X field for some time into the future. It will also be interesting to compare this to active network performance prediction.

7.3 The Importance of the V2X Field Quality

Discussions revolving around the future of vehicles and transportation always include the human factor. We started with the example of K.I.T.T. and Knight Rider and introduced the human factor as part of the SAE levels [1] in Chapter 1. We continued to compare the performance of AVs to the capabilities of humans, especially when talking about delay and reaction times [5], but also when discussing the extension of the FoV [10].

To complete this human factor perspective, we took the opportunity to include tests for CCAM and C-ITS scenarios in a parallel study. *Shaping Automated Driving to Achieve Societal Mobility Needs* is a human systems integration approach of Mörtl et al. [9], where we describe novel human-systems integration approaches to improve acceptance, safety, and comfort of AVs.

V2XaaS is a part of this human systems integration approach. The human passenger of an AV or driver of a legacy vehicle expects explainability from the used system. V2XaaS can provide explainability by sharing information of AVs. This thesis mainly discussed CA and CP as use cases, but V2X also supports the exchange of Maneuver Coordination Messages (MCMs), which allows humans to follow the intentions of AVs. Even more, if the system relies on information from V2X communication networks, the rating of QoS parameters helps indicate trustworthiness and, in turn, increases user acceptance. Hence, the following sections will provide a short overview of the analysis of V2XaaS in situations where the human driver is assisted and challenged by information provided via V2X.

Introduction

The publication by Mörtl et al. [9] describes the conduct and results of two field demonstration studies where the HADRIAN innovations, among others a Human Machine Interface (HMI) for driver information, were integrated into real vehicles, and their effectiveness in terms of the human driver role was evaluated. In the first field demonstration, twelve participants evaluated HADRIAN innovations intended to improve the safety and comfort of using AD at SAE L2 and L3. The study was performed in a passenger vehicle in an open road environment where participants compared interactions with a baseline automated vehicle with the HADRIAN innovations. In the second field demonstration, ten participants experienced HADRIAN innovations intended to facilitate older drivers in a small passenger vehicle while driving on a test track in Spain. Both studies' results confirmed the HADRIAN approach's key assumptions and identified limits and opportunities. We discuss these lessons learned and conclude with what these findings tell us about the benefits and problems of adopting a holistic, user-centered approach to AD solutions.

Problem Statement

When switching between SAE [1] L2 and L3, the user must be informed about what is happening. Especially in case of a fallback from L3 to L2, the user has to be informed in advance. This requires, on the one hand, an actively working V2X communication system that provides information about driving levels via IVIMs and a good approach towards explainability for the user via the HMI of the HADRIAN innovation.

Method

In this context, we implemented an AD scenario where a vehicle switches between L2 and L3 functionality and vice versa, with the approval of infrastructure. In other words, infrastructure informs the AV that L3 functionality is available or will terminate. The AV then informs the user and activates/deactivates the system as intended.

The user reaction is aimed to be evaluated towards the explainability provided by the AV. For this thesis, especially, the trustworthiness of the V2X connection and the delay of information are highly important to indicate a good user experience from the perspective of infrastructure-assisted AD.

The study aims primarily at the human perspective. Hence, the implementation focused on the HMI. However, they provide insight into what the quality rating of the surrounding V2X field can provide to the user.

Setup

All user tests are executed within an ADD as discussed in Chapter 3. The vehicleCAPTAIN toolbox provides low delay V2X communication with the RSUs on the highway. This is a critical component, as the information delay is critical to the user experience. However, the AD stack is a simpler software stack designed for lane keeping as the complexity of Autoware is not needed for these tests. A small HMI was also assembled to be presented to the user via a tablet. This HMI also accesses the data provided by the vehicleCAPTAIN toolbox.

The relevant demonstration in this study deals with improving L2 and L3 AD. In other words, the user is confronted with an AV switching between L2 and L3. One scenario is the perfectly working L3 environment, while the others confront the user with unexpected situations, such as lane changes or termination of L3 AD. The reactions of the users are evaluated empirically.

Results

The study participants could rate the experience in six dimensions: safety, joy, usefulness, assistance, displays, and takeover, as shown in Figure 7.6. The goal was to rate the baseline experience of AD compared to the HMI experience provided in this study. The scale was from -10 to $+10$, from a high rating of the baseline system, crossing zero, to a high rating of the proposed explainable HMI.

Significantly, the users rated safety around 7.5 with $p < 0.001$, simply by being informed about the surroundings. Similar values apply for usefulness with 5.5 and $p < 0.05$. It shows that for humans, information and explainability are key.

Figure 7.6: Comparative Ratings between Baseline and HADRIAN System (* $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$), as shown in Moertl et al. [9].

Discussion

From a technical perspective, the system performed as intended. Previous sections show that the performance of V2X is high enough not to interfere, e.g., with a human's comparatively slow reaction time. However, the advantage of having information in advance, as suggested by the concept V2XaaS, is key in this scenario. The AV can know in advance about a simulated traffic situation around the corner and allows informing the user in advance about the situation, as discussed in other publications [5,10].

The study highlighted the advantage of early information [5] and extension of the FoV [10], which is provided by V2XaaS. The study indicates the need for explainability to the user, which can be done by the designed rating metric that can directly be provided to the user to indicate the status of the surrounding V2X field.

CHAPTER 8

Discussion

The core contribution of this thesis is related to the components, performance, and rating of V2XaaS. The component analysis discussed in Chapter 5 found in its core the degradation of information within sensing, communication, and fusion. The cause of degradation was discussed in Chapter 6. The analysis was then assembled to provide a metric for rating the QoS, as discussed in Chapter 7. Finally, this chapter discusses the RQs formulated in this thesis.

AVs depend on the information obtained from their surroundings, as discussed for the SPA cycle in Chapter 2. In the context of V2X, V2XaaS can be used to two extremes. One can argue that an AV has to navigate its surroundings using exclusively onboard perception, similar to how humans operate a vehicle. However, with good V2X communication connectivity, one could also expect an AV to be able to rely on information gathered from V2X communication sources. In reality, the optimum lies somewhere in between. Having information beyond the onboard FoV can be of many advantages to increase efficiency, safety, and comfort, as discussed by the research presented in this thesis [5,6,10,9].

The following sections highlight the core contributions made with the work presented in this thesis. Section 8.1 starts with a recap of the vehicleCAPTAIN toolbox as a core component of the V2XaaS AD system we created. Section 8.2 follows with a summarizing discussion on the central RQs guiding this work. Section 8.3 closes with a few final statements on the possible impact of this work on the future of mobility.

8.1 The vehicleCAPTAIN Toolbox

The technical implementations presented in this thesis followed the vision of K.I.T.T. from Knight Rider, aiming to give an AV the ability to communicate. The AD system as a basis, operating on the ADDs as discussed in Chapter 2, was a major implementation team effort in recent years. The ability to communicate and share sensor data is now made possible by the vehicleCAPTAIN toolbox [4], as discussed in Chapter 4. The vehicleCAPTAIN toolbox is a collection of FOSS software components that ease integration of V2X communication in general and CA/CP functionality in specific. The importance of the vehicleCAPTAIN toolbox is highlighted by many publications that form the basis of this thesis [3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10]. Even more, the vehicleCAPTAIN toolbox was an Open Innovation Contest Laureate, awarded by the

InSecTT project in 2022 and won the Styrian Innovation Award in 2024. It received positive feedback from the V2X community, and other research teams actively use several parts.

However, aside from all the benefits provided by the vehicleCAPTAIN toolbox, there is the limitation of manpower in development. Specifically, we must integrate ROS 2 gateway features message by message. Also, we are far from being able to have permanent unit tests to check full standard compliance. However, as stated throughout this work, the vehicleCAPTAIN toolbox provides a solid basis for early-stage research and development and is already available as FOSS.

8.2 Research Questions

The three core contributions of this work are presented in Chapters 5–7. Each focuses on one of the central RQs discussed in Section 1.2. The following sections will revisit the three RQs to highlight the main findings in those respective core parts of this thesis.

8.2.1 RQ1: The Components of V2X-as-a-Sensor

The first RQ aimed at the identification and analysis of the components of V2XaaS. In Chapter 5, we identified the three core components of V2XaaS, sensing, communication, and fusion, as shown in Figure 8.1. We also identified the three factors describing the respective components. The data is described in all cases by its achievable accuracy, the delay involved, and the format provided. These parameters are interdependent. Their mutual influence depends on the approach selected in the other components.

Figure 8.1: The components of Cooperative Perception are (i) Sensing, (ii) Communication, and (iii) Fusion, as discussed in Chapter 5, as shown in Pilz et al. [2].

The description of components and their identified description parameters lead to a broad approach on how V2XaaS could be implemented. Discussed are two main approaches, both depending on the selected communication interface. For this work, the cmWave protocol currently under standardization was highlighted as the most versatile approach, with mmWave as an alternative for high data accuracy. The selected cmWave technology then leads to an analysis of existing systems and approaches of SOTA AD systems. It was found that the cmWave technology integrates well with existing SOTA AD systems. Based on this analysis, an evaluation framework was created, as introduced in Chapter 3.

In conclusion, RQ1 is answered with input from Chapter 5, which identified the components of V2XaaS and their interdependencies. Even more, the discussion on interdependencies

provided the basis for the design and implementation of a prototype discussed in Chapters 3 and 4.

8.2.2 RQ2: The Performance of V2X-as-a-Sensor

The first RQ aided the definition of a V2XaaS system, based on SOTA AD systems, as introduced in Chapter 3. The second RQ aided the evaluation of its performance.

Specifically, a prototype was implemented and analyzed for the core parameters of accuracy and delay, as discussed in Chapter 6. The accuracy analysis was set in the perspective of comparison with the onboard performance of SOTA AD and localization systems and compared with safety requirements derived from the literature.

In a parallel step, the full delay chain was analyzed from an event happening until the receiver is aware of that event. The delay was also analyzed with a specific focus on loaded channels, which resulted in important insights about the risk of message starvation in busy channels.

Based on the analysis of accuracy and delay, V2XaaS was integrated in other use cases to show the benefit of increasing the FoV of an AV by using data received via V2X communication. Even more, this thesis discussed the benefit of having factual information in advance compared to onboard sensors of SOTA AD systems, but also compared to the human perception and reaction capability.

From a distance, these results complete the picture of many publications, as discussed in Chapter 6. However, as also mentioned, a much broader view invites discussions on details, such as the pre-selection of data or the discussion of trustworthiness and the risk of adversaries. Focused related literature on these and more topics are highlighted in Chapter 9.

The basis for RQ2 are the performance indicators identified by RQ1. These indicators were systematically analyzed by RQ2, focusing on accuracy and delay. The analysis reviewed expectations from the literature and combined them with the analysis of an implemented prototype. The results show the expected performance and limitations of systems with comparable technologies.

8.2.3 RQ3: The Rating of V2X-as-a-Sensor

The analysis of the performance of V2XaaS shows that the quality of the surrounding V2X field depends on many factors. The quality of the provided V2X data is not obvious by simply looking at parts.

To solve the issues of complexity and uncertainty, the work presented in this thesis analyzed the performance data for commonalities and edge cases. This analysis revealed a certain independence for evaluation and important parameters that needed highlighting. There are eight parameters in this first approach, clustered into four groups, as shown in Figure 8.2.

We defined metrics for each parameter and aggregated them together with configurable weights. This final weighted metric immediately describes the quality of the surrounding V2X field, as demonstrated in Section 7.2.

Figure 8.2: Components of the algorithm rating the V2X field, as shown in Pilz et al. [10].

The metric discussion highlights the benefits and the need for a broader simulation study to confirm applicability in a bigger scenario involving more AVs. Additionally, related research still needs some time to discuss the influence of adversaries and the prevention of attacks, which are a core component of trustworthiness.

The rating metric presented in this work is a first step towards the explainability of the QoS of V2XaaS, as intended by RQ3. The metric has means to provide an accuracy- and delay-focused rating for the QoS of V2XaaS in Chapter 7. The discussion is also opened towards improving metrics in trustworthiness and FoV. The latter is the most challenging. However, the accuracy and delay-centric approach fits SOTA AD systems in allowing them to rate the provided QoS of the current V2XaaS data.

8.3 Final Remarks

From a top-level perspective, V2XaaS provides viable information. Pilz et al. [10] discussed the extension of the FoV and the inherent gain of information. As summarized in Chapter 7, the AD system can use underlying performance metrics to decide, in principle, how viable the available information is. However, as also highlighted, the rating system is only an indicator of viability.

Additionally, as discussed in Section 7.3, AVs will change the future mobility concept to improve our societal needs. This includes efficiency, safety, and accessibility to traffic. V2XaaS contributes to this, by allowing AVs to interact on a higher cooperative level. Even more, V2XaaS opens the window towards explainability to road users, especially VRUs.

With our work presented in this thesis, we were among the first to provide a basis for the discussion of V2XaaS components, followed by much literature on developing CP prototypes. We were then also able to fill gaps in research on the accuracy and delay perspective of V2XaaS in general and CA and CP in specific. Finally, we are the first to present a necessary QoS rating system for V2XaaS to improve the explainability of challenges in general and the performance of implementations in specific.

CHAPTER 9

Related Research

This work used primary sources of related research for the discussion of V2XaaS components and their performance in Chapters 5 and 6. This chapter summarizes core related literature in the following paragraphs, followed by specific sections highlighting more specific related literature, separated into additional sections. Sections 9.1, 9.2, and 9.3 directly map to the components, sensing, communication, and fusion. Section 9.4 then provides details on other V2XaaS applications. Section 9.5 provides related research not directly involved in the work provided in this thesis but strongly related.

Rauch et al. [47] provide an excellent early basis for the definition of the V2X delay chain, with a focus on CP. In parallel to this thesis, the research group around Schiegg et al. [66, 144,88] provides much in-depth analysis into CP from a simulation perspective. Their work is especially interesting, as Schiegg is within the standardization consortium of the ETSI for the CP service.

The following listing of related research is structured towards the essential components of V2XaaS, as defined in Chapter 5. This should aid the structure and highlight the influence of this related research.

9.1 Sensing

Sensing starts with the sensors themselves. The core of the information is the datasheet vendors provide, such as Flir [113] or Ouster [112,28]. These datasheets are backed with broad studies on sensor accuracy [145,146,147,148,149]. Additionally, sensors need calibration [39,150,151,152,153], to fix many issues with accuracy, caused by intrinsic characteristics of sensors and extrinsic characteristics from mounting positions.

Object detection is integral to SOTA AD stacks. Default configurations of SOTA AD stacks, such as Autoware [13], use a combination of You Only Look Once (YOLO) networks and CNN networks for detection and classification. Wen et al. [115] are one source for comparing inference times of such algorithms. Papers with Code [154] link many more papers and benchmarks on detection databases and performance.

9.2 Communication

The primary source for specifications is, again, the standardized documents. In the case of ITS-G5, these are the documents provided by the ETSI. For a summary, Ulbel [11] provides a solid primary source on all four cmWave interfaces.

Interfaces with more bandwidth in the mmWave domain are still highly theoretic, as the practical development is mainly focused on mobile networks and seems halted in the automotive domain. However, technology simulation sources, such as Sakaguchi et al. [155], Fukatsu et al. [46,34,35], and Yin et al. [33], provide a basis.

From a delay perspective, Rauch et al. [47] is again a good primary source, followed by Volk et al. [89]. However, as publications presented in this thesis point out, the focus is tailored towards a simulation scenario, with a too-perfect view of the underlying AD stack.

Miller et al. [57] and Thandavarayan et al. [44] both provide insight into the delay behavior with a focus on CP. Thandavarayan et al. [73,45] are also a good opening point for discussing redundancy mitigation, a major factor in reducing the channel load. In detail, related research deals with methods to mitigate redundancy [97], pack detected objects into one instead of multiple messages [74,45], and decide which objects might be necessary at all [77,98,99]. However, a deeper analysis of this is beyond the scope of this thesis.

Another evolving parameter is the discussion around security, especially the trustworthiness of CP data. Related research deals with V2X cyber security challenges [100,101,102,103], but also the need to reflect trustworthiness in the data [104,70,105,106]. All security is delay overhead when solely looking at the delay chain of V2XaaS applications. However, while details are not explicitly discussed in the work of this thesis, it is a core factor for the quality of the V2X field, as pointed out in Chapter 7.

9.3 Fusion

This thesis does not explicitly discuss different fusion algorithms. However, others provide general introductions [156,157] and reviews of challenges [158,159,160]. This thesis concentrates on SOTA AD stacks, such as Autoware [13]. Autoware provides references in its sources. Among others, multi-task multi-sensor fusion, in general, [161] and camera-lidar data fusion [162] in specific. For this work, we extend Autoware with data fusion, which uses object data. Hence, complex fusion, such as particle filters [163,164], is used primarily when using similar sensors, such as lidars. The output of sensors is then fused after object detection. Here, simple Kalman filter approaches [165,166,167,168] are used. Finally, the planner can use the data to calculate occupancy grids if required. The implementation of particle filters and occupancy grids are discussed, e.g., by Godoy et al. [169].

Byproducts of sensor fusion are AVR applications [84,85,86,87]. AVR applications use the CP data to extend the FoV of drivers and passengers. This is usually done by merging 3D point clouds but can also be done artificially by creating renderings within the bounding boxes.

9.4 Applications

Several companies worldwide already realize SAE level 4 AD, mainly focused on bigger cities in China and the USA. Within the research domain of V2XaaS capable AVs, the ADDs discussed in Chapter 3 are one of the more complete AVs. Most related research in the domain of CP and, therefore, V2XaaS focus on simulations. However, one of the first publications with a fully running system by Shan et al. [83] has to be mentioned.

Apart from the automotive perspective, one has to mention that CP and V2XaaS were already a hot topic within other fields, such as robotics [78], and unmanned aerial vehicles [79]. For AVs, the discussion is more focused on the integration with libraries, such as CarSpeak [80], AutoC2X [81], or the vehicleCAPTAIN toolbox [4]. For research purposes, accessibility and modifiability are key features. Pereira et al. [82] propose to release such a system. But also Autoware [13] is planning to integrate V2X capability.

Finally, existing research in the domain of platooning can contribute much to the control analysis by analyzing the control loop in connected vehicles [170,171,172,173], of course also dealing with unknown communication-related delays [174,175], or fixed expected frequencies, [176].

9.5 Beyond this Work

This work focuses on the current standard of CPMs. However, related research also deals with issues strongly connected to the applicability of CA/CP. Issues that influence accuracy, methods that can improve accuracy, and methods that use CA/CP in other ways that need accuracy. The following paragraphs provide an overview. This section points out related research, which was not directly looked at in this work but influences the usage of V2X in general or CP in specific.

The discussion about dynamic scenarios in Chapter 6 indicated that delay influences the accuracy of information if it is not compensated. The sending frequency is related to delay and, therefore, the mechanisms to prevent congestion [97,74,45,77,98,99]. The accuracy of a single message is the same, independent of congestion control. However, more messages allow the AD stack to increase detection accuracy. The more information the fusion algorithms have, the more precise the result.

The validity of the data also influences the accuracy. In other words, when malicious data is received, it will corrupt the overall perception accuracy. Related research deals with cyber security threats [100,101,102,103], and methods to guarantee the trustworthiness of data [104, 70,105,106].

Technologies under development may increase the accuracy of CP. This work uses 802.11p for data exchange, a cmWave protocol. Related research deals with mmWave protocols [33,34, 35], which have a much broader bandwidth and allow sharing of raw data. Overall, as stated in related research [2], the accuracy can be increased; however, with the results of this work, the necessary effort may be discussed.

This work discussed the mitigation of GNSS accuracy using lidar HD maps, in Chapter 6. If one aims to achieve similar results by using GNSS for localization, one has to improve the

accuracy. This can be done with RTK data or by cooperative methods [107,108].

One parameter not directly looked at in this work is channel load and congestion. If the V2X channel is congested, a CPM is not guaranteed to arrive, as it could be overridden by multiple high-priority messages, such as DENMs and CAMs. However, preventing congestion caused by CPMs is well-studied. Many studies deal with data selection to decrease the size of CPMs. Methods are to mitigate redundancy [97], pack detected objects into one instead of multiple messages [74,45], and decide which objects might be necessary at all [77,98,99]. These methods decrease the channel load, which is essential to not increasing the channel-busy ratio.

Another evolving parameter is the discussion around security, especially the trustworthiness of CP data. Related research deals with V2X cyber security challenges [100,101,102,103], but also the need to reflect trustworthiness in the data [104,70,105,106]. Depending on the methods used, delay times for CP may increase. The systematic approach to evaluating the CP delay chain presented in this work allows a discussion on the influence of this delay.

We also did not directly address different forms of fusion algorithms, i.e., the implementation of particle filters and occupancy grids, as discussed by Godoy et al. [169]. Autoware's planner works with a map. This map can either be generated with perception from the onboard sensors or preinstalled. We tested the perception stack for this work, as discussed in Chapter 6, as the planning algorithm is unnecessary for the CP delay evaluation.

We focused on cmWave protocols for data transmission, with ITS-G5 as an example. The lower modulation of the transmission frequency results in a limited bandwidth, which only allows the transmission of object data, as specified by ETSI [48]. However, there is also the evolving mmWave standard with ten times higher frequency in the 60 GHz area. This frequency allows the transmission of the raw camera and lidar data, as discussed in the related literature [33,34,35]. As discussed in other related research [2], using raw data for transmission will also influence the fusion. It will be interesting to see how the CP delay chain must be adapted when this technology is ready to be integrated.

Finally, we did not dig deeper into the domain of controller theory. As discussed, our implementation uses Autoware as the AD stack. Autoware is a collection of best practices to balance the overall system's performance. In that regard, analyzing Autoware from a control perspective would be interesting. Platooning can contribute much to the control analysis by analyzing the control loop in connected vehicles [170,171,172,173], of course also dealing with unknown communication-related delays [174,175], or fixed expected frequencies, [176].

CHAPTER 10

Conclusion and Future Work

This thesis investigated the application of V2XaaS in the domain of AD. This has been done by first shaping the relevant domains of AD and V2X to define the core components of V2XaaS. These core components were then analyzed to provide performance metrics in the relevant areas. The performance indicators were then used to shape a common metric for rating the quality of the surrounding V2X field.

Factual information about the environment is necessary for an AV to fulfill its mission, i.e., reaching a specific destination. This relevant information is provided using onboard sensors in classic robotics. Shared perception via V2X can also provide this information in cooperative fields, as discussed in Chapter 2. In this thesis, we used an existing AD stack and extended it with a novel V2X toolbox, as discussed in Chapters 3 and 4. The first of three goals was commonly defining the necessary components for such a V2XaaS system, as discussed in Chapter 5. The implementation of components has then been tested for their performance in identified key areas, as discussed in Chapter 6. The acquired performance metrics were then used to create an algorithm that rates the quality of the surrounding V2X field to provide a metric for an AV to decide to which extent the V2X information can be used, as discussed in Chapter 7. The resulting algorithm is then applied to three examples to showcase the advantage of providing meaning to the acquired data, as discussed in Chapter 8. Finally, this work takes a step back to provide an overview of the most influential publications and related research not directly involved in this thesis in Chapter 9.

The following sections will highlight and summarize this work's core contributions and impact in Section 10.1. Before finishing with an outlook on future work in Section 10.2.

10.1 Conclusion

The research linked to this thesis aims to provide a thorough overview of V2XaaS, as addressed by RQ1, with the primary goal of objectively rating the quality that can be provided in a given situation. However, as stated in multiple sections, the matter of V2XaaS is complex, with many interdependencies. This ranges from the availability of different physical interfaces over their transmission performance to the definition of messages exchanged in use cases.

The vehicleCAPTAIN toolbox, presented in Chapter 4, is a core element to assist the

integration of V2XaaS into SOTA AD software stacks. The vehicleCAPTAIN toolbox is designed to integrate with SOTA V2XaaS architectures as presented in Chapter 5. The vehicleCAPTAIN toolbox also provides high accuracy for the data in transmission and low delay, as highlighted in Chapter 6. This work was a core element. I am proud it was an Open Innovation Contest Laureate, awarded by the InSecTT project in 2022, and won the Styrian Innovation Award in 2024. Furthermore, it receives positive feedback from the V2X community, and other research teams actively use several parts.

The ADDs of the Virtual Vehicle Research GmbH are equipped with the V2XaaS system developed throughout this thesis. As pointed out in Chapter 3 and especially in Chapter 6, we were able to optimize the V2XaaS system to provide as high of an accuracy as possible and as low of a delay as possible. The process allowed us to discuss the areas of possible improvements and to highlight the importance of accuracy and delay in discussing the applicability of V2XaaS.

Moving onward to the performance and RQ2, we were able to show a CA/CP accuracy of 0.2 to 0.3 m at close distances of 10 m and 0.88 to 1.73 m at high lidar sensor ranges of 60 m. We discussed the root cause of problematic depth perception with sparse lidar point clouds and poor sensor data leading to underestimated vehicle bounding boxes. Even more, we were able to show that these inaccuracies are the root cause for low V2XaaS accuracies.

In the domain of delays, we could confirm the low latencies of V2X in close distance scenarios with low channel load, estimating 5 ms of transmission time. On top of this delay, we discussed the asynchronous delay between sender and receiver. We argued that the delay is within the receiver fusion cycle, not the receiver V2X distribution cycle. However, the 100 ms delay caused by the respective 10 Hz cycle is added in both cases. We found the basic V2XaaS delay to be around 120 ms extra delay compared to the onboard perception.

We then discussed the potential for packet loss to influence the information delay. Specifically, in city scenarios, one packet may be lost occasionally, meaning that information may be received only in the second transmission, leading to a 100 ms extra delay. Three consecutive packets may be lost in higher-distance scenarios, such as with highways, leading to a 400 ms extra delay. Next, we found the analysis of loaded channels to render even worse results, indicating that the delay is unbounded. Unbounded, meaning that with enough ITS-Ss trying to send simultaneously, a single ITS-S is prone to starve, i.e., unable to send at all.

Overall, the work in this thesis found a huge gap between expectations from the V2X domain claiming to have an important solution for AVs but worrying too much about the imperfections of wireless channels. On the other side, in many parts, the AD domain rejects the idea of sharing information between vehicles, mostly not being aware of potential benefits. Hence, we demonstrated the benefit of the FoV increase when V2XaaS is done right. Specifically, we argued that using V2XaaS in many scenarios is a high benefit.

To improve the basis for discussion in the field of applications, we needed a more high-level view of the QoS, as addressed by RQ3. The detailed insights for accuracy and delay behavior are too specific to provide a discussion basis. Hence, we aimed to create a rating metric to visualize the QoS of the active surrounding V2X field in Chapter 7. The metric focuses on the channel load, the most critical component for a wireless communication system, such as V2X communication. Other components are then the quality and relevance of information, which

are necessary indicators, depending on the scenario, as discussed in Chapter 7. In its first version, the metric can also provide feedback on the trustworthiness of information. However, this step has yet to be integrated when related research can provide metrics, as discussed in Chapter 9.

10.2 Future Work

The development of the rating metric involved the discussion on trustworthiness. The metric includes ratings for trustworthy sources and trustworthy data. The latter, trustworthy data, aims to rate the trustworthiness of single data points. However, the rating of trustworthy sources is still an open research field. Specifically, there is no common ground on evaluating the trustworthiness of single ITS-Ss other than checking their transmission signature to filter out adversaries. If an attacker hijacks the AD system, the malicious intent has to be discovered with different approaches.

The discussion on the metric development also leads to the need for a FoV rating. FoV evaluations highlighted that FoV sensor coverage is not trivial, as there is a difference in resolution depending on distance and the high likelihood of occlusions. The second issue is that the absence of information does not equal free space. This leads to the need for FoV occupancy ratings. However, also a FoV occupancy grid is not trivial, as this, in turn, raises the question of the other QoS parameters in the metric influence the FoV occupancy grid. For example, if a specific area is covered by a highly loaded ITS-S, that cannot send any more important messages. Or worse, if a specific part of the FoV is described by a single adversary ITS-S. Overall, we suggest analyzing the potential for a 2D QoS grid for V2XaaS. The computational effort will increase drastically, but the benefit may be even better for use cases. Specifically, changing the weights in the rating for specific use cases may improve performance. Virtual towing would, for example, benefit vastly from a route with low V2X channel load. The routing could be adapted in that case.

The application of use cases leads to the point of integration. The results presented in this thesis discuss the metric using hypothetical scenarios. The next step is to integrate this metric into our ADDs and into simulations. Simulations would especially be beneficial in tuning the rating weights for specific use cases, as the simulations are less dependent on physical devices. In a later stage, the results can then be integrated again into physical AVs to investigate identified core applications.

This integration could also allow ready-to-use blocks, such as ROS nodes, to be shared within the community. Simulation datasets and ready-to-use building blocks would, in turn, foster research on tuning rating weights and extending the metric, which would allow a discussion on the importance of specific QoS parameters for specific driving scenarios. Combined with parallel studies, this could lead to a more widespread application of the rating metric and probably even an introduction to the standardization of ETSI. Certain QoS ratings could even be provided within the QoS message.

Aside from the rating metric, we see the need for more light in other parts of the core topics discussed in this thesis. Among others is the upcoming technology of mmWave communication. The higher operation frequency would allow for much higher data throughput,

even though the directional characteristic of the transmission technology would limit the ease of use. At this time, we do believe that the general V2XaaS setup would not be completely redesigned. However, mmWave would be a highly beneficial technology to improve the accuracy and FoV parameters, as data with much greater detail could be exchanged.

Finally, having a more detailed look at certain performance parameters, we believe that using V2N needs a more detailed analysis. V2N was highlighted to possess higher delay but potentially better information filtering. Specifically, if vehicles shared their data centrally, this central system, e.g., a RSU, or a city management backend, could combine that information and provide a single perspective without the need for all ITS-Ss having to relay the information and load the channel. However, V2N is still at a starting point where a backend management system is needed. We briefly mentioned that RSUs might handle such information or that city backends could handle the data. However, related research is still involved in the early stages of finding solutions.

Finally, the ongoing integration of V2X services by infrastructure and vehicles will allow more complex field tests in the future. Advancing progress increases the availability of physical interfaces, allowing a more thorough analysis in field environments, including the potential for cross-dependency analysis and the integration of more complex use cases.

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List of Abbreviations

1PPS	one Pulse Per Second
2D	two-dimensional
3D	three-dimensional
3GPP	3rd Generation Partnership Project
4G	4th Generation Mobile Networks
5G	5th Generation Mobile Networks
AD	Automated Driving
ADD	Automated Driving Demonstrator
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AIFS	Arbitration Interframe Space
API	Application Programming Interface
ASFiNAG	Autobahnen- und Schnellstraßen-Finanzierungs-Aktiengesellschaft
ASN.1	Abstract Syntax Notation One
AV	Automated Vehicle
AVR	Augmented Virtual Reality
C-ITS	Cooperative Intelligent Transport System
C-V2X	Cellular Vehicle-to-Everything
C2C-CC	car2car Communication Consortium
CA	Cooperative Awareness
CAM	Cooperative Awareness Message
CBR	Channel Busy Ratio
CCAM	Cooperative Connected Automated Mobility
cmWave	Centimeter Wave
CNN	Convolutional Neural Network
CP	Collective Perception
CPM	Collective Perception Message
CPU	Central Processing Unit
CS	Computer Science
CSMA/CA	Carrier Sense Multiple Access with Collision Avoidance
CW	Contention Window
DCC	Decentralized Congestion Control
DCF	Distributed Coordination Function
DDS	Data Distribution Service

List of Abbreviations

DENM	Decentralized Environmental Notification Message
DSRC	Dedicated Short Range Communication
E2E	End-to-End
EDCA	Enhanced Distributed Channel Access
EM	Electromagnetic
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
FD	Field Driving
FL	Field Load
FOSS	Free and Open-Source Software
FoV	Field of View
FPS	Frames per Second
GN	Geographical Networking
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
HD	High Definition
HLA	High Level Architecture
HMI	Human Machine Interface
IEEE	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers
InSecTT	Intelligent Secure Trustable Things
IO	Input/Output
IoT	Internet of Things
IP	Internet Protocol
ITS	Intelligent Transport System
ITS-G5	Intelligent Transport Systems in the 5GHz band
ITS-S	Intelligent Transport System Station
IVIM	Infrastructure to Vehicle Information Message
K.A.R.R.	Knights Automated Roving Robot
K.I.R.A.	Knight Industries Road Agent
K.I.T.T.	Knight Industries Two Thousand
lp	locally perceived
LTE	Long Term Evolution
MAC	Medium Access Control
MCM	Maneuver Coordination Message
mmWave	Millimeter Wave
MQTT	Message Queuing Telemetry Transport
NDT-MCL	Normal Distributions Transform Monte-Carlo Localization
NTP	Network Time Protocol
OBU	On-Board Unit

OSI	Open Systems Interconnection
PDR	Packet Delivery Rate
PHY	Physical Layer
PLB	Packet Loss Burst
PLR	Packet Loss Ratio
PTP	Precision Time Protocol
QoS	Quality of Service
RAM	Random Access Memory
RL	Reinforcement Learning
RMSE	Root Mean Square Error
ROS	Robot Operating System
RQ	Research Question
RSSI	Received Signal Strength Indication
RSU	Roadside Unit
RTCMEM	Radio Technical Commission For Maritime Services Extended Message
RTK	real-time kinematic
SAE	Society of Automotive Engineers
SOTA	State of the Art
SPA	Sense Plan Act
TCP	Transmission Control Protocol
UART	Universal Asynchronous Receiver Transmitter
USA	United States of America
V2I	Vehicle-to-Infrastructure
V2N	Vehicle-to-Network
V2V	Vehicle-to-Vehicle
V2X	Vehicle-to-Everything
V2XaaS	Vehicle-to-Everything-as-a-Sensor
vehicleCAPTAIN	vehicle Communication Platform to Anything
VRU	Vulnerable Road User
WAVE	Wireless Access in Vehicular Environments
WIFI	Wireless Fidelity
YOLO	You Only Look Once
ZMQ	Zero Message Queuing

*Everything is going to be fine in the end.
If it's not fine, it's not the end.*

– Oscar Wilde